

FOSTERING INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS FOR A SUSTAINABLE RESOURCE
INTENSIVE INDUSTRY ACROSS THE EXTENDED CONSTRUCTION VALUE CHAIN

First Publications regarding living lab for FISSAC model

June 2018 (M34)

D7.1: First Publications regarding living lab for FISSAC model
WP 7, T 7.1

Author: Lena Heuts (RISE)

H2020-WASTE-2014-two-stage

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 642154.

Technical References

Project Acronym	FISSAC
Project Title	FOSTERING INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS FOR A SUSTAINABLE RESOURCE INTENSIVE INDUSTRY ACROSS THE EXTENDED CONSTRUCTION VALUE CHAIN
Number	642154
Start date	01/09/2015
End date	29/02/2020

Deliverable No.	D7.1
Dissemination level ¹¹	
Work Package	WP 7 – Industrial symbiosis replicability and social aspects
Task	T 7.1 Establishment of a Living Lab for replicating FISSAC model and development of transition process from linear to circular economy
Lead beneficiary	22 (RISE)
Contributing beneficiary(ies)	ACC, ACR, UNE, AKG, BEF, BGM, CBI, RINA-CSM, RINA-C, EKO, FAB, FEN, FER, GEO, GTS, TRI, HIF, KER, OVA, RINA-S, SYM, TCM, TEC, ECO
Due date of deliverable	30 June 2018
Actual submission date	30 June 2018

Document history

V	Date	Beneficiary	Author
01	21/05/2018	RISE	Lena Heuts, Deliverable Draft Structure
02	24/05/2018	ACCIONA	Blanca Juez, Contributions to Deliverable Structure
03		OVAM, Geonardo, TRINIUS, RINA Consulting, Símbiosy, HIFAB, TCMB, GTS and BGMC	Living Labs leaders contribution, Chapters 4 – 12.
03	17/06/2018	RISE	Lena Heuts, Deliverable 1 st Draft
04	20/06/2018	RINA Consulting	Elena Rocco, Deliverable review
05	20/06/2018	ACCIONA	Blanca Juez, Deliverable review, Chapter 3.3 General overview
06	27/06/2018	RISE	Task leader, comments/requested changes integration
07	28/06/2018	RISE	Task leader, Deliverable Final Version
08	28/06/2018	WP leaders	SC review
09	30/06/2018	RISE, ACCIONA	Final document

¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

0. Summary

The main objective of WP7 “Industrial Symbiosis replicability and social issues” is to demonstrate the replicability of FISSAC model. An important tool for this is through the Living Labs, user-centric platforms that involves different stakeholders in a real life context with the aim to facilitate user influence in an open and collaborative innovation process. Within the FISSAC Project, LLs aim to exploit knowledge about technological and non-technological factors that could impact Industrial Symbiosis and to co-develop with LLs participants the FISSAC Model, based on circular economy, with a special focus on developed eco-innovative products. Nine LLs are set up in UK, Germany, Sweden, Czech Republic, Hungary, Turkey, Belgium, Spain and Italy.

Task 7.1 is in the start up phase but some features can be distinguished already at this stage. The Living Labs all reflect the priorities of the stakeholders in the different countries. This means that different value chains and challenges, barriers and drivers related to this are investigated. Each Living Lab has its own starting point and has set its own development and goals. For some this might be to establish a network for knowledge sharing whereas others might wish to reach a more consolidated phase to obtain real “co-creation”. This is still too early in the process to know. Nevertheless, all LLs have their own challenges and must be managed in line with this.

From this first publication regarding Living Labs can be stated that there is not one over-all goal to align the Living Labs in the sense that they should all work in the same way. A comparison between Labs must only be made in order to share experiences and knowledge on how to overcome barriers and to find inspiration through experiences made by the other Labs. All Labs must strive to find the best way to increase cooperation and industrial symbiosis. This will create long term competitiveness and profitability for their stake-holders and a more sustainable construction sector. The European industry is facing a huge challenge in becoming part of a circular economy. Cooperation in the format of Living Labs can be one important tool in this.

Table of content

0. SUMMARY	3
1. WP 7 - INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS REPLICABILITY AND SOCIAL ISSUES.....	8
2. TASK 7.1: ESTABLISHMENT OF A LIVING LAB FOR REPLICATING FISSAC MODEL AND DEVELOPMENT OF TRANSITION PROCESS FROM LINEAR TO CIRCULAR ECONOMY.....	8
3. LIVING LABS – THE FISSAC WAY	8
3.1 THE COMMON APPROACH.....	12
3.2 LIVING LABS GUIDELINES	12
3.2.1 LIVING LABS AS AN INPUT TO THE FISSAC PROJECT	13
3.2.2 A STAKEHOLDER-CENTRIC APPROACH.....	15
3.2.3 THE FISSAC APPROACH TO LIVING LABS - COMMON ELEMENTS OF THE APPROACH.....	15
3.2.3.1 STAKEHOLDERS	15
3.2.3.2 TOPIC SELECTION.....	16
3.2.3.3 THE LAB STRUCTURE	18
3.2.4 DIFFERENT CONTEXTS, DIFFERENT LIVING LABS	19
3.2.5 PROJECT MANAGEMENT, REPORTING AND FOLLOW-UP.....	19
3.2.5.1 MEETINGS	19
3.2.5.2 MILESTONES	20
3.2.5.3 DATA CAPTURE AND REPORTING	20
3.2.6 TOPICS OF INTEREST BASED ON CONSULTATION WITH WP LEADERS	20
3.3 LIVING LABS – GENERAL OVERVIEW	22
4. BELGIUM.....	25
4.1 THE SECTOR AND THE LIVING LAB – STARTING POINT	25
4.2 THE LIVING LAB TODAY	26
4.2.1 PURPOSE AND GOAL.....	26
4.2.2 SCOPE.....	26
4.2.3 IDENTIFYING STAKEHOLDERS	27
4.2.4 STAKEHOLDER INTERACTIONS AND ACTIVITIES	27
4.2.5 IDENTIFYING BARRIERS AND DRIVERS	28
4.2.6 OTHER RESULTS	29
4.2.7 THE LIVING LAB AND THE FISSAC MODEL	30
4.3 CONCLUSIONS.....	30
4.4 PLANNED FUTURE WORK	30
4.5 LIST OF APPENDICES	30
5. CZECH REPUBLIC.....	31
5.1 THE SECTOR AND THE LIVING LAB – STARTING POINT	31
5.2 THE LIVING LAB TODAY	32
5.2.1 PURPOSE AND GOAL.....	32
5.2.2 SCOPE.....	33
5.2.3 IDENTIFYING STAKEHOLDERS	33
5.2.4 STAKEHOLDER INTERACTIONS AND ACTIVITIES	33
5.2.5 IDENTIFYING BARRIERS AND DRIVERS	33
5.2.6 THE LIVING LAB AND THE FISSAC MODEL	34

5.3	CONCLUSIONS	34
5.4	PLANNED FUTURE WORK	34
6.	GERMANY	35
6.1	THE SECTOR AND THE LIVING LAB	35
6.2	THE LIVING LAB TODAY	35
6.2.1	IDENTIFIED BARRIERS AND DRIVERS	35
6.2.2	FISSAC LIVING LAB APPROACH IN THE GERMAN CONTEXT	36
6.3	CONCLUSION	36
7	HUNGARY	37
7.1	THE SECTOR AND THE LIVING LAB – STARTING POINT	37
7.2	THE LIVING LAB TODAY	40
7.2.1	PURPOSE AND GOAL	40
7.2.2	SCOPE	40
7.2.3	IDENTIFYING STAKEHOLDERS	40
7.2.4	STAKEHOLDER INTERACTIONS AND ACTIVITIES	40
7.2.5	IDENTIFYING BARRIERS AND DRIVERS	41
7.2.6	OTHER RESULTS	42
7.2.7	THE LIVING LAB AND THE FISSAC MODEL	42
7.3	CONCLUSIONS	42
7.4	PLANNED FUTURE WORK	44
7.5	LIST OF APPENDICES	44
8	ITALY	45
8.1	THE SECTOR AND THE LIVING LAB – STARTING POINT	45
8.2	THE LIVING LAB TODAY	45
8.2.1	PURPOSE AND GOAL	46
8.2.2	IDENTIFYING STAKEHOLDERS AND ACTIVITIES	46
8.2.3	IDENTIFYING BARRIERS AND DRIVERS.....	47
8.2.4	THE LIVING LAB AND THE FISSAC MODEL.....	52
8.3	CONCLUSIONS AND PLANNED FUTURE WORK	52
9.	SPAIN	53
9.1	THE SECTOR AND THE LIVING LAB – STARTING POINT	53
9.2	THE LIVING LAB TODAY	53
9.2.1	PURPOSE AND GOAL.....	53
9.2.2	SCOPE.....	54
9.2.3	IDENTIFYING STAKEHOLDERS	54
9.2.4	STAKEHOLDER INTERACTIONS AND ACTIVITIES	54
9.2.5	IDENTIFYING BARRIERS AND DRIVERS	54
9.2.6	THE LIVING LAB AND THE FISSAC MODEL	54
9.3	CONCLUSIONS	55
9.4	PLANNED FUTURE WORK	55
9.5	LIST OF APPENDICES	55
10	SWEDEN	56
10.1	THE SECTOR AND THE LIVING LAB – STARTING POINT	56
10.2	THE LIVING LAB TODAY	56
10.2.1	PURPOSE AND GOAL.....	57

10.2.2	SCOPE.....	57
10.2.3	IDENTIFYING STAKEHOLDERS	57
10.2.4	STAKEHOLDER INTERACTIONS AND ACTIVITIES	57
10.2.5	IDENTIFYING BARRIERS AND DRIVERS	58
10.2.6	THE LIVING LAB AND THE FISSAC MODEL	59
10.3	CONCLUSIONS.....	59
10.4	PLANNED FUTURE WORK	59
10.5	LIST OF APPENDICES	59
11.	TURKEY.....	60
11.1	THE LIVING LAB TODAY	60
11.1.1	PURPOSE AND GOAL.....	60
11.1.2	IDENTIFYING STAKEHOLDERS	60
11.1.3	WORK PLAN	60
11.1.4	IDENTIFYING BARRIERS AND DRIVERS	60
12	UK.....	61
12.1	THE SECTOR AND THE LIVING LAB – STARTING POINT	61
12.2	THE LIVING LAB TODAY	62
12.2.1	PURPOSE AND GOAL.....	62
12.2.2	SCOPE.....	62
12.2.3	IDENTIFYING STAKEHOLDERS	62
12.2.4	STAKEHOLDER INTERACTIONS AND ACTIVITIES	62
12.2.5	IDENTIFYING BARRIERS AND DRIVERS	63
12.2.6	THE LIVING LAB AND THE FISSAC MODEL	63
12.3	CONCLUSIONS.....	63
12.4	PLANNED FUTURE WORK	63
12.5	LIST OF APPENDICES	63
13.	LIVING LABS ANALYSIS.....	64
14.	DISCUSSION	65
15.	RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FURTHER LIVING LABS	65
APPENDICES	66

List of Figures

Figure 1: WP 7 Tasks and objectives	8
Figure 2: Results of the Partner survey about methodology and process, completed before the GA of March and updated June 2018	11
Figure 3: Element zero of the Common approach presented during the 4 th General Assembly.....	12
Figure 4: Relationships between Living Labs and WP5 (Demonstrations).....	14
Figure 5: Relationships between Living Labs and WP6 (FISSAC Tool).....	14
Figure 6: Suggested Milestones	20
Figure 7 Development of Living Labs - countries	22
Figure 8 General overview of FISSAC LL experience	24
Figure 9: Belgium Living Lab Participant by category	27
Figure 10: Belgium Living Labs meetings - content.....	28
Figure 11: Czech Republic Living Lab Barriers and Drivers - Legislation	33
Figure 12: Czech Republic Living Lab Drivers and Barriers - Science and research, education/sharing of knowledge and best practices.....	34
Figure 13: Czech Republic Living Lab Drivers and Barriers - Cooperation and construction material recycling/marketing and use of eco-innovation on the market	34
Figure 14: Hungary Living Lab. The volume of construction output in Hungary, seasonally and working day adjusted data (2010=100%).....	37
Figure 15: Hungary Living Lab. Building permits - sqm of useful floor area, (seasonally- and calendar-adjusted data, 2010=100%)	38
Figure 16: HU LL 1st event evaluation results.....	42
Figure 17: Italian Living Lab Logo	45
Figure 18: Italian Living Lab organization meeting	46
Figure 19: First Italian Living Lab Flyer.....	47
Figure 20: Italian Living Lab. Non-technological barriers.....	48
Figure 21: Italian Living Lab Photos	49
Figure 22: Italian Living Lab. Topic discussed during the First Italian Living Lab	51
Figure 23 Italian Living Lab and FISSAC Model relation	52
Figure 24: Hungary Living Lab. Minister of state speaks at the event	75

Abbreviations and acronyms

LL – Living Lab

CemBeton – Hungarian Cement Concrete and Lime Association, a national umbrella organisation for businesses of this field

CDW – construction and demolition waste

CDM – construction and demolition materials

ÉMI - [ÉMI Non-Profit Limited Liability Company for Quality Control and Innovation in Building](#) (ÉMI Non-profit Llc.)

HOI – Herman Otto Institute Nonprofit Llc., a background institute of the Ministry of Agriculture in Hungary to assist implementation of legislation in the fields of agriculture, nature conservation and environment.

IS – industrial symbiosis

WPC - wood-rubber-plastic composites

TIS – Technological Innovation System analysis

1. WP 7 - Industrial Symbiosis replicability and social issues

The main objective of WP7 “Industrial Symbiosis replicability and social issues” is to demonstrate the replicability of FISSAC model. In particular, technical and non-technical aspects that could affect an Industrial Symbiosis are analysed in this WP and the necessary steps to change from linear to circular business models are defined for the most representatives EC countries and FISSAC related industries. At this purpose, several concepts and instruments are applied such as Living Labs (LLs), interviews and Technological Innovation System (TIS) analysis. The WP7 activities are divided in three main tasks, whose objectives are shown in the following figure.

Figure 1: WP 7 Tasks and objectives

2. Task 7.1: Establishment of a Living Lab for replicating FISSAC model and development of transition process from linear to circular economy

A Living Lab is a user-centric platform that involves different stakeholders in a real life context with the aim to facilitate user influence in an open and collaborative innovation process. Within the FISSAC Project, LLs aim to exploit knowledge about technological and non-technological factors that could impact Industrial Symbiosis (investigating different value chains, countries and stakeholders, etc.) and to co-develop with LLs participants the FISSAC Model, based on circular economy, with a special focus on developed eco-innovative products. LLs will be set up in UK (BGM), Germany (IBT), Sweden (HIF), Czech Republic (FEN), Hungary (GEO), Turkey (TCM), Belgium (OVAM, ACR+), Spain (SYM) and Italy (DAPP). According to the common strategy defined within the first reporting period, the Living Labs should reflect the priorities of stakeholders in the different countries; investigate relevant aspects of the FISSAC model; and bring valuable inputs to solve problems and explore pathways within the project and in some cases beyond.

3. Living Labs – The FISSAC Way

Within the FISSAC project, a broad definition of what a Living Lab can be is taken into account, leaving every partner free to design and manage a lab that suits their industrial and stakeholder context.

The organization of the Living Labs in Sweden started in advance, in order to generate some first insights about methodology and process that might be relevant to the efforts to come in other regions.

After the First Swedish Living Lab, a survey about methodology and process has been shared with the other partners, in order to collect some important topics to discuss and to include in the guidance document to be developed.

In addition, during the 4th General Assembly of the Fissac project, held in Sheffield on March 2017, a discussion about a common approach for the Living Labs took place, in order to align the objectives of the different regional Living Labs.

On the basis on the first experiences gained during the Swedish Living Labs, of the results of the survey and of the outcomes of the discussion during the GA, a document called Living Labs Guidelines has been prepared by RISE and shared with the relevant partners. It is reported in a dedicated chapter.

Appendix 1: Partner survey about methodology and process²

Issue 1: Starting point

Each regional living lab has a unique starting point. Important issues to consider include:

Existing IS initiatives in the construction sector

Are there existing collaborative initiatives/platforms for the IS in construction in your region? Do you participate/are you in contact with these?

Yes/No/Don't know (Choose one, delete others)

Comments:

Existing IS innovation agenda in sector

Is there an existing innovation agenda, in terms of prioritized materials, technologies, or markets, for IS in construction in your region?

Yes/No/Don't know (Choose one, delete others)

Comments:

Issue 2: Stakeholder involvement

Some of the most important choices in designing the Living Lab relate to stakeholder involvement. Important issues to consider include:

Value chain coverage

How broad will participation in your lab be, in terms of value chain/circle coverage? In terms of different materials and functions?

Have already discussed/Important, will consider/Don't know (Choose one, delete others)

Comments:

Role of non-business actors

Will you involve non-business actors (research, government, civil society) in the Lab?

Have already discussed/Important, will consider/Don't know (Choose one, delete others)

Comments:

Stable vs. Evolving Group

Do you expect to maintain the same group of stakeholders over the life of the lab, or to evolve (for example from strategy-level to operational-level representatives)

Have already discussed/Important, will consider/Don't know (Choose one, delete others)

Comments:

² Shared among relevant partners before the GA of March 2017

Issue 3: Lab structure

Both the overall lab process and the individual meetings can be structured in a variety of ways. Important issues to consider include:

Role of open discussion

Do you expect that the Lab meetings will have an element of open discussion, to explore issues with stakeholders and identify the specific tasks to be worked on?

Have already discussed/Important, will consider/Don't know (Choose one, delete others)

Comments:

Role of practice-oriented activities

Do you expect that the Lab meetings will involve other activities such as problem-solving, site visits, data gathering/capture, task-oriented discussions?

Have already discussed/Important, will consider/Don't know (Choose one, delete others)

Comments:

Plenary vs task forces/committees?

Do you expect the lab to maintain a format that involves all participants in the same discussions and tasks? Or do you expect to create smaller groups to deal with specific issues?

Have already discussed/Important, will consider/Don't know (Choose one, delete others)

Comments:

FISSAC vs. Post-FISSAC work

Will the Lab seek to generate its results within the FISSAC project, or to create the conditions for stakeholders to manage their own labs outside of the project?

Have already discussed/Important, will consider/Don't know (Choose one, delete others)

Comments:

Issue 4: Subject focus

The subject matter or focus of the Lab will need to be determined, either in advance or as a part of the Lab process.

Which of the following do you expect to be a part of the Lab's focus? (Delete those that are not relevant)

- Material-specific analysis
- Material-neutral analysis
- Technical challenges
- Commercial challenges
- Intra- and inter-organizational issues
- Social/landscape issues
- Don't know/To be determined

Comments:

The results of the survey were summarized and up-dated for this report Figure 2

	SE	UK	CZ	TR	FL/BE	SP	HU	DE	IT
Issue 1: Starting point									
Existing initiatives	Known initiatives focus on reuse of interior product, mainly office related and also development of digitalized documentation systems for building materials.	Don't know	Some IS promotion under ENVICRACK, but no active platform	Don't know	Yes, OVAM coordinates multiple platforms	Not specific to the construction sector. We use to work with a multi-sectorial approach	Not aware of any initiatives in construction	International group established in a different R&D project, not focussing on industrial symbiosis but on identifying end-of-life routes, scenarios, technical, economic, legal and logistic constraints and incentives.	Yes. "Liguria Circular" Forum is IS-specific but not specific to the construction sector. Other potentially relevant 'green' initiatives exist
Existing agenda	Log book; documentation to support material recycling in the future. Recycled content in concrete. Reusing av interior office products.	Primarily within individual companies	Stakeholder knowledge and public awareness very limited.	our sectoral stakeholders, local waste suppliers and industrial partner's awareness is very low.	1. Matchmaking platform; 2. Tracing and quality issues; 3. Regulation on non-stony fractions; 4; Cyclical construction action plan. Following are	1. Existing database at Simbiosis; 2. Knowledge transfer support from the Catalonia Institute of Construction Technology (ITeC)	Not much activity since close of ISIM-TCC Life+ project (2012)	Agenda relates to the identification, quantification and delaration of building-product-related end-of-life routes and scenarios. Ambition to define a generic approach based on three product groups with different levels of complexity, to be generalized and transferred to other product groups. Aim to implement findings in normative works in CEN and ISO.	Broad agenda touching on IS and resource efficiency, but not construction-specific IS as yet.
Issue 2: Stakeholder involvement									
Value-chain coverage	Full	Focus on glass recycling - coverage TBD	TBD	focus on cement and concrete	Constructors, crushing plant operators, building material producers,	As wide as possible	Broad coverage especially important for post-FISSAC period	indirect. Focus on manufacturers placing products on the market	TBD, probably broad
Non-business actors	Government, research	Possibly Zero Waste Scotland. Promoters of change will be sought!	City authorities, universities, promotion to general public	environmental and urbanization ministry, legal authority and universities	Research	Representatives from R&D, Associations, Architects, Designers, Governmental	Especially research	R&D, governmental agencies, manufacturer associations, manufacturers, unfortunately difficult to involve deconstruction and recycling industry	Important, especially policy actors and business associations
Stable vs. Evolving	Core group stable, but evolving to complete cover of the value chain	TBD	TBD	TBD	Core group established	Likely to evolve	Evolving strategic -> operational	stable	Likely to evolve
Issue 3: Lab structure									
Open discussion	Important initially	TBD	Different discussion fora for different stakeholders	Yes	TBD	Yes	vital for challenging participants	open but guided. Key-note-presentations, clear defined targets for workshops (series of 3 workshops has been conducted in autumn 2017 and winter 2018)	Yes, especially for non-technical issues
Practical work	Site visits, 'material journey' logging	TBD	Likely	TBD	TBD	Not foreseen	Important depending on	practical in terms of identifying routes and describing models	TBD. Data collection likely.
Plenary vs. Groups	Both	TBD	TBD	TBD	Both	Both formats are suitable	Both depending on topic	both	Both
FISSAC vs. Post-FISSAC	Both	TBD	TBD	FISSAC	Continuation TBD	Both	FISSAC primarily catalyst	parallel to FISSAC and scope , agenda, time, goals etc "not directly related", no compulsory link or inter-dependency	Both
Issue 4 Subject focus									
Material-specific	Plaster in focus meeting 3-5 Probably focus on plastics, metal and concrete for coming labs.	Glass	TBD	Cement and concrete	Yes	No	TBD	Product specific	Yes
Material-neutral	Log book, general collaboration	No	TBD	No	No	Yes	TBD	Yes	Yes
Technical challenges	Related to plaster recycling Coming meeting will explore potential technical challenges for other materials in existing buildings	Yes	TBD	TBD	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Commercial challenges	Related to plaster recycling Coming labs could possibly adress commercial challenges with recycling of above mentioned materials	Yes	TBD	TBD	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Intra/Inter-organisational	Need for information sharing, multi-stakeholder meetings at 'building level'	Yes -- creating trust between supply chain partners key.	TBD	TBD	Yes	Yes	Yes	Related to pre-normative and co-normative R&D aiming to identify end-of-life scenarios to be applied in environmental product declarations	Yes
Social/landscape issues	TBD	Yes	TBD	TBD	Yes	Yes	TBD	Not in focus	Yes

Figure 2: Results of the Partner survey about methodology and process, completed before the GA of March and updated June 2018

3.1 The common approach

During the 4th General Assembly, held in Sheffield on March 2017, a common approach for the Living Labs organization and management has been presented. Indeed the objectives of the Living Labs can be summarized as follows:

- To exploit knowledge about technological and non-technological factors that could affect an Industrial Symbiosis
 - Different Sectors
 - Different Countries
 - Different Stakeholders
- To co-develop the FISSAC Model, based on circular economy, with a special focus on developed eco-innovative products

To do this, a common and shared strategy is needed, to cover all the relevant aspects of FISSAC Model, leaving partners free to organize their own labs. In particular, the definition of a common strategy ensures that the Living Labs depict and are representatives of different countries and investigate all the most relevant aspects of FISSAC model, bringing valuable inputs to solve problems and explore pathways within the project.

The elements zero of the Common approach is reported in Figure 3:

Figure 3: Element zero of the Common approach presented during the 4th General Assembly

This common approach wants to stress the necessity to bring valuable inputs to the project, through the Living Labs. To facilitate the identification of the needs of the project, the Living Labs Guidelines reports an Appendix (List of topics of interest based on consultation with WP leaders) with a list of possible inputs that the Living Labs could bring to the project, divided per WP.

3.2 Living Labs Guidelines

The “Living Labs Guidelines” document is meant to be read as a guidance, rather than an instruction, on how to set up and develop a Living Lab. It provides support, particularly related to:

- Alignment of the Living Labs so that shared knowledge is leveraged and the FISSAC project objectives are met
- The identification of key issues to consider in design and execution of a Living Lab, including potential challenges and trade-offs
- General guidelines for project management of the Living Labs

The section is structured as both a reference, collecting the knowledge and insights gathered so far in the project, and as a guide, with information that is particularly actionable highlighted and called out in text boxes throughout. For users looking to use this guide in practice, reviewing these boxes can be a pragmatic approach. The guidelines were developed and tested in an iterative process together with the Swedish Living Lab.

According to the statement above: “A Living Lab (LL) is a user-centric platform that is based on every day practices and experiences and research. It facilitates user influence in an open and collaborative innovation process engaging all pertinent stakeholders in real life context, aiming to create validated and sustainable value, and often operating in a territorial context.”

It is important to note that the ‘user’ is not necessarily, or even most probably, the end-user of a sector’s product or service. In the case of industrial symbiosis, the ‘users’ of the innovations are typically the firms working to establish symbiotic relationships.

It is also important to point out that ‘collaborative innovation process’ can be focused on both hard and soft technologies. To the extent that a lab is designed to ‘test’ a hypothesis, in the case of ‘soft’ technologies the collaborative process itself may represent the ‘test’.

Leminen (2015) cites four types of Living Labs: Utilizer-driven, Enabler-driven, Provider-driven, and User-driven. As part of a publically funded project with a regional concept, the FISSAC Living Labs fit the Enabler driven model, characterized by:

- Strategy development through action
- Network forms around a region/project
- Information is collected and used together and knowledge is co-created in the network
- Guided strategy change into a preferred direction

The partners responsible for managing the nine national Living Labs have the freedom and responsibility to manage their own Living Labs in accordance with the conditions in which they must operate.

3.2.1 Living Labs as an input to the FISSAC project

The fundamental overarching objective of FISSAC Living Lab is defined in ‘Element Zero’ of the Common Approach³:

“[To generate] input to the FISSAC Model in the form of, for example, support to other Work Packages; case studies; exploitable results; market development; input to the FISSAC platform; development of new products or services; etc.”

More specifically this objective can be achieved through ‘Element 7’ of the Common Approach, which specifies four additional objectives in the management of the Living Labs:

- **Creating and maintaining trust.** This objective relates to the interaction with and between stakeholders in the Living Lab. While creating and maintaining trust is important to the success of the Living Lab activities, it is also an outcome of value in and of itself, to the extent that positive interactions can be the foundation for relevant work outside the context of the project (see 4.1.1 below).
- **Collecting data and specific information.** Data can be of various types and serve various purposes but capturing relevant qualitative and quantitative data is essential to transferring value from the Living Labs to the FISSAC project/model.
- **Identifying and analyzing barriers and drivers.** This objective can be the most important from a stakeholder perspective, and will be important input into task 7.2.
- **Validating the work of the other WPs.** To the extent possible, working with issues raised in other Work Packages will create value for the FISSAC project. This must be considered in balance with the need to ensure stakeholder relevance. Figure 1 below illustrates the relationship between the Living Labs and WP5 and WP6

³ Previously described as the ‘Common Strategy’ in presentation to GA March 2017.

(a similar logic can be applied to WP3).

7.1 Living Labs and FISSAC Demos

Figure 4: Relationships between Living Labs and WP5 (Demonstrations)

7.1 Living Labs and FISSAC Tool

Figure 5: Relationships between Living Labs and WP6 (FISSAC Tool)

3.2.2 A stakeholder-centric approach

The starting point of the Common Approach is the FISSAC project and model. However, to a large extent, the success and impact of the Living Labs depends on successful engagement of stakeholders. Throughout the implementation of the Common Elements in section 3 below, it will be crucial to balance the priorities of the project with the priorities of the stakeholders participating in the Living Lab. In general, however, stakeholder preferences should come first. In cases where stakeholders choose to raise new issues related to IS that are not dealt with elsewhere in the project, this is an opportunity to the project to gain new insights.

Recommendation: Stakeholder interests and needs should set the priorities of the Living Lab, especially in terms of topic selection.

3.2.3 The FISSAC approach to Living Labs - Common elements of the approach

The following elements of the FISSAC Living Lab approach should be considered by all partners responsible for Living Labs. Specific decisions within these elements will vary in different national contexts.

3.2.3.1 Stakeholders

Stakeholder identification

In order to ensure that the Living Lab is stakeholder-centric and relevant in a 'Real Life Context', a stakeholder identification effort should be the starting point for activities.

Recommendation: Begin the Living Lab with a Stakeholder identification process. To ensure flexibility, identify a broader selection of stakeholders than you initially plan to invite.

One useful approach is to begin by inventorying existing networks, projects, and industry groups who have a stated or potential interest in industrial symbiosis. These might include other research consortia investigating IS; construction and materials industry representatives and lobbying initiatives; and sustainability initiatives involving construction and materials industries. For initiatives that are highly relevant (i.e. both involving the construction sector and industrial symbiosis) collaboration in planning and executing the Living Lab should be considered. Interacting with existing networks may entail trade-offs, for example between surrendering control and gaining access to already engaged stakeholders. In the Swedish Living Lab, these trade-offs have been worthwhile, as there was little consensus about the topic for investigation and ideas from existing initiatives were treated as welcome suggestions.

Examples of relevant multi-actor groups or initiatives identified by the partners so far

- BAMB project (Swedish participant engaged)
- Re: Source Circular Economy platform Sweden (Participants consulted)
- Sveriges Bygginstitutier (Branch organisation, leading role in Swedish lab)
- PLAN C/SUMMA/Agenda 2020 (Flanders Materials Programme)
- Liguria Circular (IS initiative in Italy)
- Zero Carbon Scotland

Trade-off: Working with existing platforms and initiatives may speed up your process and save resources, but will also entail giving those platforms extra influence over the Lab's management.

In identifying potential individual participants, one useful approach is to map stakeholders along one or more value chains. We recommend creating a stakeholder list that is relatively comprehensive and includes more actors than are likely to participate in the resulting Living Lab, as this will allow for some flexibility to respond to topic interests.

Inclusion of non-business stakeholders

In general those with experience of Living Labs and IS work have been positive towards the inclusion of non-business stakeholders. In many labs policy issues have come to the fore, and access to policy makers and/or civil society organisations can help to handle this. Additionally, while companies will inevitably have some issues regarding commercial sensitivity, giving active roles to non-business participants can help build trust among businesses.

Recommendation: Include non-business stakeholders from the start. They can provide important perspectives on e.g. policy and also can advocate for action that is perceived as risky by commercial actors.

Evolution of participant group

Over the course of the Living Lab, there may be reason to consider revising the participant group. Many factors can affect this decision, but a typical trade-off may occur between maintaining a strategic perspective vs. bringing operational expertise to deal with specific issues. We recommend initiating the Living Lab with participants who have a 'strategic' perspective within their organization or initiative. This will aid in getting buy-in and in identifying truly relevant topics. However as the Living Lab evolves more specific operational knowledge may be required. A typical trade-off faced in the Living Labs involves securing the most appropriate participants vs. maintaining continuity in the group. Most organizations will struggle to justify the active participation of multiple representatives.

Trade-off: Living Labs will have to strike a balance between working with the same individuals throughout (continuity) and adding persons with needed expertise (specificity).

3.2.3.2 Topic selection

Selecting a topic for a multi-stakeholder Living Lab can be challenging. An important starting point is the FISSAC model and topics from the other Work Packages that may benefit from exploration/validation in a Living Lab context. There is the necessity that LLs bring valuable inputs to the project, investigating WP needs and issues. The leaders of Work Package 7 have consulted with leaders of Work Packages 3, 5, and 6 to compile a list of relevant topics, available in the document's Appendix.

Existing industry or civil society initiatives like those mentioned above may have already established agendas related to IS in the construction sector, or particular value chains. In the Swedish Lab, for example, multiple parties were already active around the issue of a 'log book' for materials, and the need to standardize across several existing/competing solutions. In the Flemish context, a four-part agenda has already been developed, which the Living Lab will build on:

1. Creating a matchmaking platform
2. Tracing and quality issues
3. Regulation on non-stony fractions
4. Cyclical construction action plan

Drawing on existing agendas entails a trade-off between leveraging existing engagement and tailoring the Lab activities to FISSAC.

Recommendation: Initiate discussion on topic selection (including important FISSAC topics) with a few key stakeholders in advance of launching the Living Lab, but do not pre-determine the topic.

We recommend identifying a small number of key stakeholders and discussing the both relevant FISSAC topics and existing external research/innovation/policy agendas in advance of the initial Living Lab. This can provide some insight into how to steer the initial discussions with the broader stakeholder group. However we do not necessarily recommend launching the lab with a fully defined topic, as this may limit buy-in from participants.

Material focus. In general, choosing a single material around which the lab will be based will be advantageous. This helps with scoping the discussions, finding the right participants, and generating specific information/data. In the Swedish Living Lab there was significant interest in material-neutral topics, including the log book standard, and general mechanisms for value chain collaboration in advance of the construction phase. In the end, however, focusing the discussions and generating data required a material focus. In the Swedish lab this involved pursuing a 'material journey,' following a specific material (plaster) through the construction value chain, undertaking site visits, and documenting issues related to material circulation.

Recommendation: Orient at least some portion of the Living Lab around a single material, as this will allow for more specific data to be captured. A 'Material Journey' that follows the material through the value chain is one approach if the agenda is not clear among participants.

Technological and non-technological topics. Partners indicated varying views as to whether technical or non-technical topics will be prioritized. In the Swedish Living Lab both have been discussed to date; as noted above, the agenda in the Flemish/Belgian platform has been focused on non-technical issues primarily. In order to meet the overarching objective of analyzing barriers and drivers, it is particularly important to document non-technical issues even if a technical topic is the lab's core focus.

- **Inter- and Intra-organizational issues.** The Living Lab method has been chosen, in part, to identify the ways in which different actors, both within and between organizations, need to change behaviours in order to make IS possible. It is important to capture these learnings, and the approach to data capture (see 5.3 below) will include documentation of these learnings.

- **Social/landscape issues.** The social dimension of IS needs to be integrated in all FISSAC activities. The definition of social issues used by Work Package 1 includes inter- and intra-organisational issues, which are inherent in the Living Labs and are likely to be a key part of the findings as noted above. However social issues at the 'landscape' level – such as consumer awareness and acceptance, civil society advocacy, etc. – will not always be an obvious element of the topic definition. For this reason we recommend going through a 'checklist' of questions as the topic of the Living Lab is being defined. These questions will be followed up in the data capture and reporting process (see box below).

Recommended questions regarding Social Issues at the Landscape level

1. Do the technical and non-technical innovations being 'tested' in the Living Lab raise issues that are likely to be of interest to consumers and citizens at large such as
 - a. Safety concerns
 - b. Health and toxicity concerns
 - c. Changing environmental footprint
 - d. Impact on local employment
 - e. Impact on public services and infrastructure e.g. waste collection, energy infrastructure
2. Is there a case for proactively educating consumers and citizens at large about the innovations in question?
 - a. If yes, what are some of the key messages?
3. Are there existing advocacy groups (business or non-business) who could be involved in consulting and communicating with consumers and citizens?
 - a. If yes, have they been involved in the Living Labs?

3.2.3.3 The Lab structure

Each responsible partner will have to determine the structure of the Living Lab, in terms of meeting agendas and modalities. Some elements that should be considered include:

Open discussion. Allowing participants to meet and discuss industrial symbiosis with only a loosely-defined agenda can create risks in terms of delay and loss of focus. At the same time, participants should be given the chance to participate in the topic selection, and may require a more general discussion to become familiar with one another's perspectives and priorities. In the case of the Swedish Living Lab, most of the first meeting was given to a general discussion of industrial symbiosis, with the primary objective of securing the participants' engagement going forward.

Trade-off: Open discussion can be necessary to generate buy-in from participants, but can work against a focused Living Lab investigation.

Data gathering. Depending on the topic selection, sessions of the Living Lab may be explicitly structured to capture data. For example, if a Living Lab is looking at issues of Life Cycle Assessment, participants may need to bring (non-sensitive) data to the table for comparison and discussion of needs related to IS. If a Living Lab is working with the FISSAC tool, participants may be asked to assess functionalities in relation to their own data availability and needs, with both qualitative and quantitative data captured in the meetings. In the Swedish 'material journey,' participants document findings and insights via a journal that is submitted to the organizers.

Site visits. Understanding challenges, particularly technical ones, may be helped by site visits, which help actors from one part of the value chain better understand what their colleagues in the Living Lab are facing in their daily operations.

Workshopping. For some innovations, understanding barriers and needs will be difficult without actually trying to solve the problem. Creative problem-solving or design-oriented exercises can bring participants closer to an understanding of what each party needs to contribute.

A good place to start is by defining the question or challenge that will be the focus of the living lab. Two methods to try are “Problem Definition” and/or “Framing your Design Question”. Another valuable method to use is “Value Mapping”. This is recommended for creating greater understanding and cohesion between the participant organisations of the Living Lab. All of these methods are described in Development, Impact and You (DIY) 08, Problem Definition. This report is bundled with this Guidance document in the distribution to partners.

The Swedish Living Lab’s focus on a material journey was inspired by service design methods like Customer journey Mapping [<https://hbr.org/2010/11/using-customer-journey-maps-to>] and the method “Experience Tour” is a good place to start when setting out on a new journey, be it in material, processes or customer experiences.

Throughout the Living Lab process, the “Partnership Map” can be very useful, to check the motivations of each partner and how they align with that of the Living Lab.

3.2.4 Different contexts, different living labs

It is worth emphasizing again that every Living Lab context is different: the Common Elements listed above should be treated as a menu of options that each partner should consider. In some cases, however, many of the choices will be clear due to the starting point for the Lab.

For countries where the construction sector is already exploring industrial symbiosis and may have an existing agenda for research and innovation in this area, it is likely that FISSAC partners will want to build on this agenda. Here the challenge may relate to generating specific findings that are highly relevant to the FISSAC model.

For countries where there is less existing engagement with IS from the construction sector, more time will likely be spent on open discussion of priorities and challenges, and finding ways to get stakeholders committed to participation in the Lab.

3.2.5 Project management, reporting and follow-up

The responsible FISSAC partners in each country have the freedom and responsibility to manage the Living Labs in the way they deem appropriate. What follows is a brief description of considerations for project management, along with a description of the reporting process within WP7.

3.2.5.1 Meetings

Multi-stakeholder, enabler-driven Living Labs are primarily composed of meetings. From the experience in the Swedish Living Lab, we note the following:

- Setting expectations – and getting commitment – regarding the frequency of meetings and the duration of the process is important. In the Swedish Living Lab bi-monthly meetings were agreed, with an expected duration of 1 year.
- There may be need for different ‘levels’ – all-stakeholder meetings to make big decisions and share findings, and ‘working group’ meetings tackling specific problems in specific constellations. The latter, if necessary, will have to emerge as a result of the former.
- Facilitation and presentation – Meetings may be facilitated by a FISSAC partner. Facilitation should focus on getting input from stakeholders rather than communicating to them. Neutrality regarding commercial issues is essential. While interaction should be prioritised over presentation, allowing stakeholders to act as ‘hosts’ for certain meetings and giving dedicated presentation time can increase buy-in. This role should rotate among the group.

3.2.5.2 Milestones

While the timing of the Living Lab process will vary from country to country, we can suggest the following general milestones:

Percent of total project time passed	10%	20%	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%	80%	90%	100%
M1: Creation of 'complete' stakeholder list										
M2: Living Lab Meetings										
M3: Definition of topic(s)										
M4: Interim review of findings with Lab participants										
M5: Options for post-project continuation (if any)										
M6: Final review of findings										

Figure 6: Suggested Milestones

3.2.5.3 Data capture and reporting

In general, the WP7 and task 7.1 leaders will keep internal project reporting from the Living Labs to a minimum. The task 7.1 leader (RISE) will arrange for bilateral check-ins on an ad-hoc basis, and telcos with all LL responsible partners will be held less frequently (on a quarterly or biannual basis, to be determined).

RISE will develop a light reporting template, including an assessment checklist and summary capture of findings to date. This can be filled jointly between RISE and the LL partner as part of the bilateral check-in process.

More detailed data capture is an essential responsibility of the Lab organizer, but the format for capturing qualitative and quantitative findings will depend to a large extent on the nature of the topics and the modalities used in the Lab. Some minimum expectations include:

- Completed assessment checklists and summary findings (expected quarterly, coordinated by RISE)
- **Stakeholder and participant lists:** Partners should maintain a comprehensive list of relevant stakeholders, including those identified but not participating in the Lab, as well as information about which individuals attend which meetings.
- **Meeting agendas and summary reports:** Partners should share agendas for Living Lab meetings as well as a brief summary report with both participants and WP7 and task leaders.

Input to deliverables: later in the project, when the contents of D7.1 and D7.3 are better understood, partners will be expected to provide information in accordance with the structure of these reports.

3.2.6 Topics of interest based on consultation with WP leaders

WP	TOPIC	NEEDS
WP1/WP2	IS opportunities identification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To better define and study IS opportunities • To identify new IS opportunities • To collect technical e non-technical data to better characterize IS opportunities • To complete and validate the template containing technical and non-technical requirements and constraints
WP1/WP2	Social acceptance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To establish a local network of stakeholder • To investigate social engagement and acceptance
WP3	ECO-DESIGN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To make stakeholders aware of eco-design process • To investigate interest of stakeholders in the use/choice of eco-designed products
WP3	ETV certification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To make stakeholders aware of ETV certifications • To identify interest of stakeholders in the use/choice of technologies

		with ETV certification
WP4	Logistic issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To investigate logistic issues related to waste transport
WP6	ICT Platforms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To identify existing ICT platforms for IS opportunities identification and to ask for stakeholders feedback To present FISSAC Platform and to ask for stakeholders feedback
WP6	FISSAC Platform opportunities: data gathering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To collect relevant data (e.g. CAS Number, CER code, etc.) to better identify material flows within the FISSAC matrix To collect relevant data for performing LCA and LCC of all the IS opportunities
WP6	FISSAC Model and Platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To investigate FISSAC Model and Platform userfriendliness To collect suggestions for improving FISSAC Model and Platform
WP7	TIS analysis and Replicability assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To collect information for evaluating the extension of the model application to different fields and types of products To identify non-technological barriers that may hamper the replicability of IS models and possible solutions to overcome them

Table 1 List of interest based on consultation with WP leaders

3.3 Living Labs – general overview

Several Living Labs has been developed within FISSAC Project. The main objective of Task 7.1 is to replicate FISSAC model through Living Lab development in different countries. Here a list of Living Labs that will be detailed on the subsequence sections:

- Belgium: ICT platform for industrial symbiosis. and exploration of possibilities of ‘urban mining’ for the construction and demolition sector
- Czech Republic: identifying barriers to Eco-innovation in building industry
- Germany: efficiency and the effective use of resources in an enlarged system view.
- Hungary: the role of construction and demolition materials in the circular economy
- Italy: Strategies to promote industrial symbiosis from steel, cement and concrete sectors
- Spain: Role of the Circular Economy and the Industrial Symbiosis within the construction and demolition sector
- Sweden: Circular Economy and Industrial symbiosis (focused on gypsum/plasterboards – Material journey).
- Turkey: Raise awareness of stakeholders and related participant sectors about industrial symbiosis, focus on cement and concrete production by using secondary raw materials.
- UK: Increase sheet glass recycling in the UK. Possibly setting up pilot scale projects

These experiences have facilitated an open and collaborative innovation process engaging pertinent stakeholders in real life context, aiming to create validated and sustainable values and often operating in a territorial context involving 9 countries over Europe and Turkey.

Figure 7 Development of Living Labs - countries

The nine living labs addressed different topics focused on the replication of an improved Industrial Symbiosis model in the construction scenario learning from different industrial sector. The high heterogeneity of the initiatives has allowed exploring technical and non-technical issues and social implications at regional scale.

The Figure 8 includes a short overview of Living Labs including their real-life context, purpose, main outputs and references.

<p>BELGIUM: Organizer: OVAM, the Public Waste Agency of Flanders region of Belgium. Context: The Living Labs within FISSAC build on the existing networks and ongoing existing platforms: The Flemish symbiosis platform, Consultation platform with the construction and demolition sector, Consultation platform with research and knowledge institutions Purpose: Explore possibilities of ‘urban mining’ for the construction and demolition sector. And to provide Input to FISSAC WP 6 Activities: <u>IS management tool:</u> Two workshops organized on IS management tool/methodology, June 22nd and 29th 2017. Discussions on expectations on WP6 ICT platform. Experiences, added value, advantages etc of ICP platform. <u>Urban mining:</u> Two Workshops, august 25th and December 18th 2017. Discussing challenges related to urban mining: Demolition and treatment of materials, Policy and regulations, Businessmodel/market, Eco-innovation, Cooperation along the value chain. Barriers and Drivers: See chapter 4.1.5 Planned work: Presentation of FISSAC platform will be presented to LL. LL meetings to discuss research proposals and new work practices. http://fissacproject.eu/en/category/ll-belgium-en/</p>	<p>CZECH REPUBLIC Organizer: FENIX in collaboration with the Institute of Circular Economy INCEN Context: Circular economy, construction, demolition waste, industrial symbiosis, resource efficiency. Material has not been chosen yet. Purpose: The main aim of the Living Lab in Czech Republic is to identify barriers and drivers for the industrial symbiosis and to identify key stakeholders for the value chain. Activities: Workshop June 21st 2017. Discussing and identifying Barriers and how to overcome them. A questionnaire regarding acceptance of FISSAC model was distributed. Barriers and Drivers: Legislation, Lack of knowledge, cooperation and construction material recycling, increased use of eco-innovation on the market. Planned work: Results from questionnaire to be presented by FENIX. Workshop September 20th 2018 will discuss how the FISSAC model can be introduced to the Czech industry http://fissacproject.eu/en/living-labs/czech-republic/</p>	<p>GERMANY Organizer: Trinius Context: Align FISSAC workshop with on-going activities e.g. German sustainable building Council (DGNB), Institut Bauen und Umwelt, German federal environment agency (UBA) Scope: Following the open workshop approach, LL activities are carried out in the already existing network. This is a resource efficient way of knowledge transfer between the many on-going activities in Germany and the FISSAC project. Activities: The FISSAC Living Lab project group are conducting and participating in a range of discussion fora in already on-going activities in all of Germany. - How to address recycling issues as part of the environmental life cycle assessment, life cycle costing, responsible sourcing - Discussing routes how to include end-of-life aspects into sustainability communication related to organisations and products - Identifying end-of life routes and issues related to this http://fissacproject.eu/en/living-labs/germany/</p>
<p>HUNGARY Organizer: Geonardo Ltd. Context: Teamed up with Herman Otto Institute (HOI), Environment Division of the Ministry of Agriculture and ÉMI Purpose: To raise awareness of circular economy, industrial symbiosis in construction sector and how the FISSAC method could facilitate this. Identify drivers and Barriers. Activities: Stakeholders have been contacted and bilateral meetings have been held. Aiming at finding the right topic. One LL workshop organized in April 13th 2018.</p>	<p>ITALY Organizers: RINA Consulting S.p.A. Context: Steel and cement sectors in different regions in Italy. Purpose: Promote Industrial symbiosis and the validation of the FISSAC model. Scope: Together with stakeholders reflect on industrial symbiosis opportunities, share experiences and knowledge, identify solutions for overcoming non-technological barriers. Activities: A Logo for the living lab was developed to ensure visual identity for the LL. A <u>Workshop</u> was organized on November 10th 2017.</p>	<p>SPAIN Organizer: SÍMBIOSY Context: In the start up phase a broad approach on the sector was taken. No specific value-chain in focus. Purpose: Create a space for reflecting on industrial symbiosis in the construction and demolition sector. To identify tools needed to make IS happen. To gather feed-back for the FISSAC platform. Activities: One LL workshop have been organized. Topic discussed: How can companies in construction and demolition sector optimize their resources by means of industrial symbiosis tools.</p>

<p>HUNGARY (cont.) “Resource efficiency in the domestic construction industry: Best practices in circular economy and eco-innovation”. Questionnaire have been sent out to explore areas of interest for the continued LL process</p> <p>Barriers: Hard to draw interest to the topic..Language is a barrier towards the FISSAC project/model since many stakeholders don’t speak English. Planned work: Two focused workshops are planned for autumn 2018. Topics: “Demolition and recycling of concrete” and “wood, rubber, plastics as secondary raw materials”. At both events FISSAC platform will be discussed.</p> <p>http://fissacproject.eu/en/category/ll-hungary-en/</p>	<p>Italy (cont.) “First Italian LL: Fostering circular economy and industrial Symbiosis” Topics discussed were primarily non-technical barriers like economic i.e. low profitability, legislation e.g. lack of standards, distrust e.g. towards product quality, Structural barriers. Discussions concluded that FISSAC platform/model could help overcome some of these. Planned work: For coming LL meetings the LL partners consider following topics: 1) Extending the analysis to other Italian regions and focusing on IS opportunities in different sectors. 2) Further investigate the FISSAC project/platform. 3) Analyze the social acceptance of new products.</p> <p>http://fissacproject.eu/en/category/ll-italy-en/</p>	<p>SPAIN (cont.) The workshop had a general approach so no direct feed back for the FISSAC model was given. Barriers and Drivers: The most common comment from the first LL was that “It’s about people too”. To be successful the right people must be participating in the LL. Other barriers were lack of trust and collaboration, lack of knowledge about “Best practice”. Lack of good examples and education. Planned work: A second LL workshop is planned after the summer. Focus on this occasion will be social aspects.</p> <p>http://fissacproject.eu/en/category/ll-spain-en/</p>
<p>SWEDEN</p> <p>Organizers: HIFAB AB and RISE Context and scope: Starting with a broad approach the first LL focused on gypsum plasterboard. The LL was used to develop guidelines for the other LLs and how to apply TIS-analysis for developing Living Labs and industrial symbiosis. Purpose: Creating better understanding of the value chain and how to design a better framework for data needed to increase circularity of materials in the value chain. Activities: Five LL workshops have been organized.1) Introductory meeting. 2) Topic: Material log book of the future. What information is needed to be a helpful tool for increasing circular material flow.3-5) Following Gypsum as a case study. The Swedish LL was set up as a pilot case within the project. Planned work: Workshop no 6 is planned after the summer. This time the plan is to use an existing building as a case study. The LL aims at identifying drivers and barriers for recycling and re-using materials.</p> <p>http://fissacproject.eu/en/category/ll-sweden-en/</p>	<p>TURKEY</p> <p>Organizer: TCMB Context: Cement and Concrete industry. Production of eco-cement from waste like steel, glass, ceramics etc Purpose: To raise awareness of stakeholders and related participant sectors about industrial symbiosis and best practices applications, focus on cement and concrete production by using secondary raw materials. Activities: Stakeholders have been identified. Barriers: The LL concept is not well-known. It might be difficult to convince people of the potential finding profitable business opportunities through the LL process. Planned work: 1) Questionnaire for both technical and non-technical topics.2) Preparing leaflet about LL. 3) Organizing a pre-workshop with our technical committee consisting quality managers of Turkish Cement Sector. 4) Evaluating the results of questionnaire. 5) Finally organizing LL meeting with our FISSAC partner Ekodenge for testing FISSAC software platform with participants.</p> <p>http://fissacproject.eu/en/living-labs/turkey/</p>	<p>UK</p> <p>Organizers: British glass and Glass Technology Services (GTS) Context: Sheet glass Scope: find solutions to barriers such as economically viable business case, rolling out infrastructure, educating supply chain. Purpose: To identify how to increase collection of sheet glass and recycling in the UK. Bring partners together with the possibility to setting up pilot scale projects in Scotland, financed by Zero Waste Scotland funding. Activities: British Glass and GTS spoke to over 30 stakeholders and visited 4 sites as part of the research for FISSAC. A Living Lab workshop was organized in partnership with Zero Waste Scotland and Scotland Innovation Center. A consortium was formed and a research proposal for the Circular Economy investment Fund on increasing sheet glass recycling. Barriers: Hard to commit people. Lack of data on available volumes of sheet glass. Planned work: A future lab will investigate efficient ways to collect construction waste, and in particular glass, recycling data.</p> <p>http://fissacproject.eu/en/living-labs/uk/</p>

Figure 8 General overview of FISSAC LL experience

4. Belgium

Over the years OVAM, the Public Waste Agency of Flanders region of Belgium has taken the lead in several multi-stakeholders initiatives to stimulate Circular Economy and Industrial symbiosis. As of March 2016 the role of OVAM as a key player to realize the transition to a circular economy was confirmed by the Flemish government. The OVAM considers industrial symbiosis as an integral part of the transition to a circular economy.

The Living Labs within FISSAC build on the existing networks and ongoing consultations of:

- The Flemish symbiosis platform
- Consultation platform with the construction and demolition sector
- Consultation platform with research and knowledge institutions

OVAM acts as initiator and facilitator within these platforms.

Although OVAM is responsible for the transition to circular economy in Flanders, the Living Labs are open to all participants in Belgium. Many stakeholders are active in the different regions of the country or even abroad. There is also an open dialogue with similar initiatives in Brussels and Walloon regions of Belgium.

4.1 The sector and the Living Lab – starting point

The sector

In 2006 the Public Waste Agency of Flanders initiated a small but engaged working group to make its materials management more sustainable. This initiative, born out of a sense of urgency - since Flanders has limited own natural resources and largely depends on import – gave rise to the creation of the Flanders’ Materials Programme (FMP). It’s working methods and approach - combining vision shaping, policy research and concrete action - is at the base of OVAM’s multi-stakeholders approach with different sectors⁴. The Living Labs within FISSAC build on its experiences and networks.

From the start the building and construction sector represented an important cluster in OVAM’s multi-stakeholders approach. The construction sector has a significant impact on the total use of materials in Flanders: 30 to 40% of the total waste quantity comes from the construction. The way we build and live has a very high impact on our carbon footprint. While the sector has advanced in terms of recycling, especially for stony materials (up to 90%), many challenges remain for the valorisation of non-stony materials. Although the flow of non-stony materials is much more limited, it often contains high quality materials, deserving a longer or second life.

The building and construction sector is a typical environment where various actors need to work together to achieve optimal results. If we want to close the value chain, a global and systemic approach with all the actors in the chain is very relevant.

Status today.

Urban developments such as demographic growth but also climate change and circular economy challenge cities to re-think their urban planning and question how to adapt existing buildings and large infrastructures works to new and future realities. Renovation and large construction works will increase the demand for raw materials as building materials and at the same time make a large amount of ‘waste’ materials available. In a circular approach, we must endeavour to connect the demand and supply within the urban environment and as such close the cycle of materials. We aim for recycling and the optimal reuse of parts of buildings, building elements, components and building materials

Flanders is a region of limited natural resources. To optimize the use of its resources/waste a symbiosis platform was created bringing companies producing residual waste in contact with those looking for materials as resource or input for their production process. The platform builds on an extensive database, workshops with enterprises and visits and

⁵ FISSAC Project – Deliverable 1.3 “Inventory of raw materials, waste and energy flows in industrial sectors (Metallurgic, Ceramic, Glass, Chemical and Natural stone) considered in a dynamic scenario”, February 2016

individual coaching projects with companies. As of 2017 OVAM has been looking for the possibility to transform the existing database to a more user friendly and online platform, meeting the needs for matching between companies and at the same time respecting the demands for confidentiality of companies. This process offers important insights to the FISSAC project and vice versa.

The Flemish region has been conducting active policies to support the development of recycling. Sorting of the waste streams and recovery of materials is a well-established practice in large and small-scale businesses in Flanders. For more than a decade the policies and efforts have been geared towards increased resource efficiency and the closing of material cycles. Businesses and authorities are well versed in these concepts and apply them readily. The recycling rates for construction and demolition waste exceed the European targets, especially for the stony fraction. Within the now completed Flemish Materials Program several projects were completed, which aimed at encouraging business to seek optimal solutions for their waste streams. Industrial symbiosis is considered as part of the more circular approach to the management of resources.

For the start-up of the living lab this had given the Flemish region a good head start. During the running of the Flemish Materials Program and linked to several prevention plan of specific waste streams platform for discussion and interaction between government, business, social actors and expert institutions were established. From these forums it was rather easy to draw and encourage partners to participate in the living labs. A lot of time was saved explaining the concepts involved as most participants were fully aware of them.

Start-up of the LL

The Living Lab of FISSAC are embedded in the ongoing debate and activities of OVAM with the building and construction sector and scientific and knowledge centres. For the input to WP6 on the Industrial Symbiosis management software tool, we build on the former experience from the industrial symbiosis platform in Flanders.

4.2 The Living Lab today

4.2.1 Purpose and Goal

The purpose of the Living Labs is twofold:

- To give input to WP6, concerning the expectation and relevant features of an ICT platform for industrial symbiosis.
- To explore possibilities of 'urban mining' for the construction and demolition sector, with special emphasis on non-technical aspects such as: legal, business model, employment, challenges related to the construction site in an urban environment.

4.2.2 Scope

The starting point for the Living Lab on the Industrial Symbiosis Management Software tool was the experience with the Flemish Symbiosis platform, combined with the questionnaire for the Industrial Symbiosis Management Software tool, developed by WP6.

The Living Lab 'Urban Mining' focuses on the potential for optimal reuse and recycling of parts of buildings, building elements, components and building materials in an urban environment. During the first Living Lab the participants mapped the challenges and questions they encounter while (re)valorizing resources/waste from construction and demolition.

OVAM organised 2 workshops to gather information from various stakeholders on the necessity for and the functions of a Software Tool to be developed within the scope of industrial symbiosis. The sessions took place at OVAM in Mechelen, on 22 and 29 June 2017.

4.2.3 Identifying stakeholders

Both Living Labs, on the Industrial Symbiosis Software Tool and on Urban Mining, gathered stakeholders from different sectors. The intended diversity of the participants, closely monitored throughout the plenary session and the debates in smaller working groups, was considered a real added value. It offered the opportunity to consider different aspect and viewpoints and lead the way for an cross-sectorial and interdisciplinary debate.

The invitation for the Living Labs were addressed to stakeholders already taking part in the different OVAM multi-stakeholders platforms, enlarged to people showing a specific interest in FISSAC.

- The Living Labs on the software tool mainly involved participants already having experience with industrial symbiosis, or at least being favorable to the idea. We opted not to limit the invitation to stakeholder from the building and construction sector, given the potential interest of the tool for a broad range of sectors/companies. However, special efforts were made to involve waste traders in the debate.
- The invitation for the Living Lab on Urban Mining was more generally distributed but focused on the construction and demolition sector. It attracted a more diverse audience, in line with the many challenges related to the concept of 'urban mining'.

IS Management software tool	Urban mining
Production: different sectors (retail, construction, production)	Construction and demolition federations
Technology / solution providers	Material producers / contractors
Waste traders	Government
Research institutes	Research institutes
Public Waste Agency	Consultancy and others

For detailed overview of the participants: see Appendix 1 and 2, Minutes of the living labs

Figure 9: Belgium Living Lab Participant by category

4.2.4 Stakeholder interactions and activities

For the Living Lab on the Industrial Symbiosis Management software tool two identic small scale sessions were organised. The focus was on past experiences with industrial symbiosis and an exchange of views on expectations and possible use of a software tool.

The first Living Labs on Urban Mining started with a plenary session on Circular Economy and Urban Mining, defining both concepts for the following work sessions in interdisciplinary, but smaller groups. All groups looked into the following issues: selective demolition, value chain of materials, business models and vision for the future: design, urban planning. The session ended with feedback from the different sub-groups.

The aim of the session was:

- To get insight on the questions and challenges encountered while (re)valorising waste/resources form construction and demolition,
- Identify research questions to take up in follow-up labs and eventually in trial projects,
- Explore the willingness to engage and contribute to the follow-up process.

The second Living Lab worked on the outcome of the first meeting using a challenge tree method. The aim was to identify clear objectives and priorities for the follow-up process.

IS Management software tool		Urban mining	
Meeting	Tool/methodology	Meeting	Tool /methodology
22/06/2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Questionnaire WP 6 on expectations and relevant features ICT platform - Debate on advantages and disadvantages of current industrial symbiosis model OVAM - Debate on added value ICT platform 	25/08/2017	Small, interdisciplinary working groups debating the following issues, to identify challenges related to urban mining: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Selective demolition - Value chain of materials - Business models - Vision for the future: design, urban planning
29/06/2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Questionnaire WP 6 on expectations and relevant features ICT platform - Debate on advantages and disadvantages of current industrial symbiosis model OVAM - Debate on added value ICT platform 	18/12/2017	Debate on challenge tree on the following issues (see <i>Appendix 3</i>): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Demolition and treatment of materials - Policy and regulations - Businessmodel/market - Eco-innovation - Cooperation along the value chain Identification of objectives and key questions for follow-up by scientific research, on small scale building and demolition sites, or during follow-up Living Labs

Figure 10: Belgium Living Labs meetings - content

The Living Labs are embedded in a larger trajectory. Some of the challenges and solutions discussed during the living labs, will be monitored on small scale sites and supported by academic/scientific research. While the latter phases are not part of the FISSAC project, we consider them essential to engage participants in the living labs and to guarantee a follow-up of the debate.

4.2.5 Identifying barriers and drivers

Barriers and drivers for the Industrial Symbiosis Management Software tool :

- Industrial symbiosis aims at giving a higher value to waste from one company by using it as raw material for another, and thus contributing to a circular economy. The software tool should be seen and used as a tool to enhance the valorisation of waste and not as a mere instrument to search for alternative/cheaper waste treatment solutions, without added value from an environmental or social perspective. How will the tool safeguard the higher valorisation of waste? Which indicators will be considered in the deliberation? When looking at it in an European context: how will transport/distance be taken into account?
- As to avoid misuse of the platform it is considered essential to have a clear set of rules concerning the use of the platform and a clear engagement of the participating companies.
- In the long run it will be essential to guarantee the financial liveability of the software tool. Since the success of the platform very much depends on the number of participating companies and the amount of available data, it is essential for companies to have free access to (at least parts of) the platform, to discover its potential and its added value. This should be possible even without registration. In a later phase, a system of (paying) membership to the platform could be envisaged.
- The software tool is a matchmaking tool, facilitating companies to connect. The subsequent process leading to the realisation of the symbiosis, is a process between individual companies. In order to evaluate the success of the software tool as a platform for industrial symbiosis, feedback is needed on the actual outcome of the initial contacts. This should be envisaged at the initial design of the software tool.

- The software tool should be more than just a platform connecting companies. It should be connected to a network offering advice or research on innovative opportunities, looking at ways to overcome practical barriers related to symbiosis, stimulating and supporting less obvious symbiosis initiatives. This ‘help-function’ could encourage potential participants to join the platform, even when a fee is envisaged.
- The debate on industrial symbiosis and circular economy is still a very academic debate. In order to stimulate industrial symbiosis it is essential for the platform to be easy accessible and user-friendly.

Barriers and drivers for urban mining

Demolition and treatment of materials

- Small sites are confronted with specific challenges when engaging in selective demolition: from separate sorting on site (what are the best practises) to temporary storage of materials and transportation. Practical solutions need to be envisaged, taking into account local regulations.
- Certification and validation of secondary raw materials still remains a challenging issue. The use of particular building materials and techniques may have an adverse effect on the scope for selective demolition and recovery of materials. For the non-stony fraction the optimal organisation of transport to treatment plants remains a big challenge and restricts the opportunity to use them as secondary raw materials.

Business model

- Is there a market for secondary raw materials from construction and demolition sites: why or why not? How can we guarantee quality standards concerning security, safety... ? Where in the value chain are the cost and the benefits: can we develop a viable business model for all stakeholders involved?
- How can we stimulate a market for secondary raw materials: do we need to review the existing regulations, the financing policies?

Cooperation along the value chain

- While the concept of industrial symbiosis seems attractive at first sight, many practical problems remain to convert it to a business context. A platform is a useful tool to connect supply and demand, but will this be sufficient to realise symbiosis? Do we need brokers to accompany the process? How do we stimulate trust for recycled materials? How do we guarantee the quality of recycled content? How do we stimulate reuse for more generic materials? A model based on circular economy will need knowledge sharing and transparency between different stakeholder of the value chain: how can we improve this cooperation?

Social aspects

- Urban mining, demolition with due consideration for re-use and recycling will create new and other job. Do we have a clear view on the necessary skill? Are those skills available and are there sufficient training opportunities to meet these newly created opportunities? How does this affect the already existing jobs?
- Demolition with due regard for re-use and recycling requires intensive manual labour and time. How does this affects the business model?

4.2.6 Other results

On industrial symbiosis no further studies or surveys were conducted until present. The development of an electronic platform for symbiosis of the Flemish Region is on-going.

For the development of a circular economy in the construction sector, businesses and research institutions were surveyed to determine their willingness to participate in trial projects and studies on the development of new business models based on value chains of materials.

4.2.7 The Living Lab and the FISSAC model

The Living Labs on the development of industrial symbiosis are very much a prolongation of the work established within the framework of a circular economy by Flanders' Materials Program. The network and working relationship with most of our partners and stakeholders continues. However the FISSAC project introduces new questions and different methodologies to the debate. At the same time the experience of the Flemish model are shared within the FISSAC project.

During the discussions we have observed that quite often the stakeholders do not diverge from their initial positions towards the development of a circular economy. There is often scepticism about the feasibility of the proposals. In addition it is hard to make the participants imagine the full benefits of the exchange linked to symbiosis and the development of value chains. The trust and readiness to share information, two essential conditions to make progress, are too often lacking. It is important for the living labs to have tools and methods to encourage trust and openness between participants.

4.3 Conclusions

In the Flemish Region the impetus is great to steer the economy in a more circular way. Many businesses and social actors are convinced of the benefits to the economy and society of the development of closed value chains for most materials. However, many partners and stakeholders are unclear about the step they can take. For many businesses industrial symbiosis is a specific path to make a contribution. The exchange and use of secondary materials is an established practice, but more emphasis should be put on sustainable and responsible production and consumption. At this stage the development and demonstration of new business models is crucial. Only this could encourage especially the smaller companies to take the plunge and work toward the transition to a circular economy.

We continue the journey we started a decade ago. We consider the development of industrial symbiosis and the closing of value chains as an necessary step in the transition to a circular economy. We hope that the project can help in convincing more stakeholders to join in.

4.4 Planned future work

The testing version of the FISSAC IS management software tool will be presented to the Living Lab for additional user feedback.

On the basis of the questions and challenges noted in the lab 'Urban Mining' we want to initiate research on the steps needed to close the value chains. Within the Living Lab we want to encourage the stakeholders to develop answers and proposed work practices as to remove known stumbling blocks. The labs will be a platform for the proposals for new business models.

In a further stage these proposals and new work practices will be tested in trial projects. The results of these trials will be discussed in following sessions of the living lab.

4.5 List of Appendices

Appendix 1 Belgium LL: Minutes of Living Labs Industrial Symbiosis Management Software tool

Appendix 2 Belgium LL: Minutes of Living Labs Urban Mining

Appendix 3 Belgium LL: Challenge trees Urban Mining

5. Czech Republic

FENIX in collaboration with the Institute of Circular Economy (INCIEN, <https://incien.org/>) manages the Czech Living Lab. The Institute of Circular Economy has unique experiences and relevant connections in the field of circular economy in Czech Republic and thus is a valuable partner. Since the industrial symbiosis falls under the umbrella of circular economy, the Institute became significant actor for spreading the ideas of the FISSAC project to their clients, i.e. FISSAC target audience.

The Institute of Circular Economy is a non-governmental non-profit organization that focuses on innovative environmental management. INCIEN, together with its partners, is working on projects that allow the transition from linear to circular system. INCIEN's mission is to inform, educate, interpret best practices, and jointly create ground breaking projects while moving from a linear to a circular economy. In cooperation with businesses, municipalities, the government sector, non-profit organizations and other interest groups, they implement dozens of projects a year.

5.1 The sector and the Living Lab – starting point

The sector

INCIEN organizes several interesting workshops during the year concerning the topic of circular economy, construction demolition waste, industrial symbiosis, resource efficiency, and other. FENIX participated at the workshop called “Eco-innovation in building sector” on 21st June 2017 in Prague, which was a suitable event to firstly introduce FISSAC project and organize a brief Living Lab workshop with all participants (the group of experts in building, as well as construction and demolition waste). Generally, the building sector in the Czech Republic is extremely conservative and any new approach even if innovative is hardly accepted by stakeholders in the whole value chain.

Status today.

So far, one Living Lab workshop was organized in the Czech Republic. The workshop aimed at mapping and surveying relevant stakeholders’ needs and wishes. A group of different stakeholders (20 participants) – representatives of SMEs, construction company, Ministry of Environment, municipality, associations, and media – actively participated during the workshop. The workshop did not touch topics only regarding the industrial symbiosis but also legislation and finances, science and research, education and sharing of best practices, and marketing and use of eco-innovation on the market. During the workshop, the project FISSAC, and in particular, IS platform was introduced by Fenix. The outcomes of the workshop were relevant for the purposes of the Living Lab.

Start-up of the LL

The main goal of the first workshop was to identify barriers to Eco-innovation in building industry. Stakeholders have been working in three separate groups proposing specific steps to overcome these barriers. These steps are interlinked by a vision, which has been created based on a question: “If everything works perfectly, what would it be like in 5 years’ time?”. At the end, there was a space for networking and creating connections for possible future cooperation among the participants.

Barriers were divided into 3 specific categories. Similarly, also the participants formed 3 groups and discussed the topic of positive VISION OF ECO-INNOVATION IN THE BUILDING INDUSTRY BY 2022. Specific steps of an ACTION PLAN to fulfil the vision has been identified as well.

5.2 The Living Lab today

Prior to second workshop organization, a brief questionnaire was prepared online (<https://www.surveymonkey.com/survey/d/N0H5Q1V1Q1U1O8N4A>) in order to gather inputs from stakeholders (questions such as: what is the nature of your business, what sort of materials are you working with, were you offered to participate in the past in a similar project regarding the industrial symbiosis, would you deem IS relevant for your business, would you be willing to take part in such initiative, etc.). The questionnaire was shared through INCIEN channels and also on their website as a short press release (<https://incien.org/cirkularni-novinky-ze-stavebnictvi-pokracovani-kulatych-stolu-projekt-fissac-i-moznost-zapojeni/>).

Second workshop is planned to be organized on 20th September 2018 in Prague in cooperation with INCIEN and Business Innovation Centre (BIC) within the event “ECO-Innovation Forum II”. This will be the second edition of this event which had very big success last year (about 150 participants, <https://incien.org/event/incien-ekoinovacni-forum-udrzitelne-technologie-pro-budoucnost/>). The morning session will be dedicated to presentation of projects and companies related to the topic of construction demolition waste and circular economy. In afternoon workshop participants will be divided into two groups – one will be discussing national project led by BIC and the second dedicated to FISSAC project and Living Lab in Czech Republic.

5.2.1 Purpose and Goal

The main aim of the Living Lab in Czech Republic is to identify barriers and drivers for the industrial symbiosis, key stakeholders for the value chain, on which material/s to focus, get feedback on the FISSAC model and possibility/willingness to test it by stakeholders.

5.2.2 Scope

We did not yet specify a material (such as concrete, wood, or steel) to work with. The conservative construction sector proved to be a huge barrier as none of the participants showed interest in the FISSAC model testing. However, we created questionnaires in which we try to, among others, identify an interest of participation. This questionnaire was shared with wider range of stakeholders and we are awaiting the responses. We hope to identify the scope and material selection based on the info from the questionnaires.

5.2.3 Identifying stakeholders

A group of different stakeholders were identified for the first living Lab workshop thanks to INCIEN contacts – representatives of SMEs, construction company, Ministry of Environment, municipality, associations, and media.

5.2.4 Stakeholder interactions and activities

Stakeholders were actively participating the first Living Lab workshop, where in three separate groups were discussing the vision how to overcome the three main barriers - “If everything works perfectly, what would it be like in 5 years time?”. At the end, there was a space for networking and creating connections for possible future cooperation among the participants.

5.2.5 Identifying barriers and drivers

The main barriers and how to overcome them were identified within the first Living Lab workshop. Barriers were divided into 3 specific categories. Similarly, also the participants formed 3 groups and discussed the topic of positive VISION OF ECO-INNOVATION IN THE BUILDING INDUSTRY BY 2022. Specific steps of an ACTION PLAN to fulfil the vision has been identified as well.

The vision for the year 2022	Action plan
1) Regulations and statements delivering the standards about construction products and waste management 2) Building designers know well the new norms, and have knowledge about secondary raw materials 3) The environmental aspects (such as the requirements on recycled materials and construction waste handling) are considerate while using EU funds 4) Investors do require recycled materials and proper handling (separation and recycling) of the construction waste 5) Good awareness about the possibilities to recycle construction material 6) Access to information about announced tenders (so that companies that were not approached by the contractor are informed as well) 7) Model for environmental standards and requirements that could be used for public tenders. 8) Recycled products are part of the documentation: PRODCOM, TP170 (technical regulations) 9) Voluntary protocol for building demolition works in practice	1) Common action plan between the Ministry of Environment and Ministry of Industry and Trade. 2) Being well informed about responsible management of resources and secondary raw material is part of the curriculum for designers, The Ministry of Industry and Trade (MIT) and Czech Technical University create together a catalogue of recycled material products. MIT also prepares an action plan for requalification, which are incorporated to the National Educational Concept by the Ministry of Education. 3) Preparation of assessment standards (to support use of secondary raw material within construction) 4) Increased awareness about the quality of secondary raw materials, demand stimulation, increased knowledge of investors. 5, 6, 7) Sharing awareness also on conference that are not particularly focused on construction industry and waste (Regionservis, Information for mayors about environmental topics from the regional councillors, Connection with activities and trends of Smart Cities, Local Agenda 21, Regional Development Agencies, The National Health City Network, etc.)

Figure 11: Czech Republic Living Lab Barriers and Drivers - Legislation

The vision for the year 2022	Action plan
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) There is a platform to connect science, research and the private companies (it is functional and up dated) 2) Use of best practices from abroad. Use of well-known technologies. 3) Change of evaluation criteria and involvement of environmental aspects 4) Legislation and methodology support for the use of recycled materials (these information are available for designers) 5) Environmental standards are part of the public tenders criteria 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ethical code applied within the science, research and private companies – research results are kept by the scientists themselves, but are available for the public as well; Financial motivation for researchers; working system of tax deduction (even without controlling by the Tax Office) - Quality control over the quantity - Awareness about the possibilities of cooperation (also for the Czech projects) - Decrease of the administrative burden (to support the research part not the administrative work). - Lifelong educational courses (for example for ČKAIT group). - Efficient use of financial resources for marketing and product promotion.

Figure 12: Czech Republic Living Lab Drivers and Barriers - Science and research, education/sharing of knowledge and best practices

The vision for the year 2022	Action plan
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Involvement of municipalities and public population in waste segregation 2) Support of the regional level 3) Certification of innovative materials 4) Price comparison between the traditional materials and eco-materials 5) Confidence in use of products from recycled materials 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Motivating the municipalities and public population 2) Creating information software, platform (supporting the industry symbioses) 3) Cooperation with the scientific platform from the beginning of innovation. Transformation of waste into resources. 4) Local collection, processing and distribution of products. 5) Sharing of information.

Figure 13: Czech Republic Living Lab Drivers and Barriers - Cooperation and construction material recycling/marketing and use of eco-innovation on the market

5.2.6 The Living Lab and the FISSAC model

So far, the stakeholders were briefly introduced the FISSAC project and FISSAC model in and nobody was particularly interested to test the model within their organization. We are hoping to get more inputs from the questionnaire and during the second Living Lab workshop.

5.3 Conclusions

The first Living Lab had a goal to identify barriers that Czech Republic faces in terms of eco-innovation in the construction and building sectors and to design an action plan of overcoming these challenges. The workshop fulfilled its purpose and the said goal was met. In addition, FENIX created questionnaires regarding the acceptance of FISSAC model and shared it with relevant audience. The outcomes will be shared with RINA who might find it beneficial for their work package.

5.4 Planned future work

First, we will like to analyze the outcomes from the online questionnaire and share these with the FISSAC model developers. Second, the second Living Lab workshop is organized for 20th September 2018, Prague. The topic of this Living Lab will revolve around prospect inclusion of the FISSAC platform in the Czech industry.

6. Germany

6.1 The sector and the Living Lab

The base-line situation depends strongly on the type of material contained in the waste streams. With respect to the economic value in secondary materials, or with respect to regulatory requirements on waste disposal, business models for the uptake of secondary resources are well established and common practice, e.g. recycling of metals and glass, energy recovery from plastics and other combustible materials. Waste incineration however is not a recycling option according to the EU waste directive, but a waste management approach.

For these materials and waste fractions, the establishment of “new secondary routes” are only meaningful when the new suggested route presents higher efficiency or enables the replacement of more scarce resources, or materials generated with higher environmental, economic or social impact.

The ultimate point of concern should not be the recycled content in a product, but resource efficiency and the effective use of resources in an enlarged system view.

6.2 The Living Lab today

6.2.1 Identified Barriers and drivers

Discussions with stakeholders clearly show that:

Building construction and demolition companies

- Waste management in construction and demolition is an issue of concern, largely covered by legal requirements and economic penalties
- The requirements on sorting waste correspond to the current uptake abilities of the recycling business
- Sorting of high value fractions results in an economic benefit for the construction and demolition businesses
- Work site conditions sometimes conflict with waste handling goals, e.g. time, available space, integration in the work flow and organisation of material routing on site

Product manufacturers (cradle to gate)

- The business model of many manufacturers includes international supply chains, where final steps of manufacturing or assembly are carried out by the producers
- The influence on the supply chains takes place through tendering and purchasing, “green purchasing” with established requirements on e.g. social standards or material qualities would need to be complemented with other topics, such as e.g. use of secondary resources

Product manufacturers (gate to grave)

- Typically, the responsibility of the manufacturer ends with the product delivered, or depending on the product, with the product installed and taken into operation as an integrated element of a building.
- With regards to life cycle concerns, some manufacturers apply expanded concepts, including monitoring and optimisation of performance in building operation, expanded warranties, service contracts, including leasing instead of purchasing, or even functional contracting models.
- Take-back at the end of life has been identified as both a topic finding interest in the market leading to image advantages, but also as a potential approach to regain resources bound in the products at their end-of-life.
- Main aspects of concern are
 - Long time difference between purchasing / installation and return of the product
 - Change of technical preconditions over time – what appears meaningful today does not necessarily need to be advantageous in the context of e.g. future energy systems
 - changes applied to the materials / products during the service life of the building
 - Impurifications or mixing caused during the use phase or during deconstruction, sorting, treatment and transportation processes
 - Matching requirements for the uptake of secondary resources with the qualities of materials supplied for recycling

- Legal concerns, especially that end-of-life “products” are not described with the term “product”, leading to a situation that entire groups (product communication to standardisation) do not – or can not – take wastes and secondary material streams into consideration
- Product specific “industrial symbiosis” – while the term “industrial symbiosis” often led to rejective reactions, for some deconstruction products the establishment of rather local “disassembly” centers was discussed as potential solution. On international workshops, manufacturer representatives (especially of functional components of multiple material ingredients in high complexity) argue that such centers could carry out disassembly, sorting and distribution to material recycling under controlled high quality conditions. Controlled and managed quality of secondary resources is key for high value application.

For established recycling routes, the business concepts are rolled out across Germany, leading to the claim that there is no need for direct local cooperation

→ exception: transportation efforts for low value but high weight or high volume material streams, e.g. secondary concrete

Facing new approaches (e.g. recycling of window glass into new float-glass instead of standard glass recycling processes) facilities developing, refining and establishing these approaches and technologies are single spot appearances, their resources rely on local supply and their products often serve a local user. First when market awareness is in place and a business model is established, these approaches may spread to a different factor of scale, become economically feasible and more widespread in allocation.

6.2.2 FISSAC Living Lab approach in the German context

There are already plentiful activities going on in Germany. Therefore, it was decided not to set up specific FISSAC workshops or regional groups but to align with the on-going activities. Conceptually, following the open workshop approach, we carry out living-lab-type activities within our networks.

- With the German Sustainable Building Council (DGNB) we are refining the Green Building Labelling Scheme, also involving discussions on how to address recycling issues as part of the environmental life cycle assessment, life cycle costing, responsible sourcing, easy for future deconstruction and recyclability
- With the Institut Bauen und Umwelt – a branch association addressing environmental subjects relating to construction products and environmental product declarations, with a broad membership of producers, manufacturers and associations, we are discussing routes how to include end-of-life aspects into sustainability communication related to organisations and products
- For the German federal environmental agency (UBA) we are conducting an R&D project on identifying end-of-life routes, setting up scenarios for significant routes in order to include these scenarios in the communication of environmental product performance. In the context of this R&D project, international workshops with a wide range of stakeholders are being held, addressing topics:
 - Identifying current practice and desirable end-of-life-routes
 - Identifying preconditions and detailing end-of-life-routes
 - Quantifying routes and demonstrate the influence on environmental performance of products
- At the same time, we are discussing with manufacturers on the trends to be expected from these and other approaches in their business environment, feeding their perspectives back into the discussions in the mentioned projects and activities.

6.3 Conclusion

The FISSAC Living Lab project group are conducting and participating in a range of discussion fora, not necessarily primarily carried out for FISSAC, but enabling us to contribute content to the FISSAC project.

7 Hungary

Geonardo Ltd. is the FISSAC consortium partner who is responsible for organizing the LL process in Hungary. Geonardo is an innovation and technology company active in the fields of energy, environment and sustainable development. It provides research, innovation, consultancy services and cutting-edge solutions in the renewable energy, resource efficiency, natural resources and climate change domains.

Across these sectors, Geonardo conducts state-of-the-art life cycle assessments (LCA), GIS/remote sensing and 3D terrestrial laser scanning (TLS) applications, develops web-based planning and decision support tools, and implements novel training, capacity building, institutional strengthening, and communication and dissemination actions.

Our mission is to co-create, share and convey knowledge about these systems at the highest quality.

Since its establishment in 1999, Geonardo has become a leading SME in Central and Eastern Europe with extensive experience in conceiving and implementing research and innovation projects co-financed under the EU programmes. Geonardo works closely with universities, research institutions, industry as well as public administrations and civil society organisations, providing innovative solutions to tackle complex societal challenges.

Today, Geonardo has a broad portfolio of European and international projects implemented by a dynamic and multidisciplinary team of experts with solid know-how and experience in project development and management, practice-oriented high quality interdisciplinary research development and outreach, policy advisory work, graphic/web design and IT solutions, as well as technical expertise in sustainable agriculture and rural landscapes, circular economy, environmental engineering, geothermal energy, bioenergy, energy efficiency, building energetics, geodata and satellite imagery processing.

7.1 The sector and the Living Lab – starting point

The sector

According to the Ministry for National Economy the output of the construction sector is rapidly increasing in Hungary (Figure 1) thanks mainly to the rising number of industrial and storage facilities as well as buildings for educational and sports purposes. Output at civil engineering works is also on the increase, mainly as a result of road and railway construction works.

The construction sector confidence index by GKI Economic Research Co shows that for the year 2017 stakeholders expected output growth of some 20 percent in the sector. Besides EU funded and state-funded projects, another major factor behind recent output growth has been the Family Housing Allowance scheme, which has substantially boosted housing projects since 1 July 2015. Since the programme's start, 50 000 applications have been registered in the value of HUF 126bn, the Minister for National Economy said. The performance of the Hungarian construction sector has been remarkable even from an international prospect. The Eurostat's floor-area index, which is based on the size of floor areas registered in building permits, shows that this indicator rose in Q1 2017 – compared to the low point reached in Q1 2014 – by 26 percent within the EU member states, by 24 percent in the eurozone and by 181 percent in Hungary (Figure 2).

Source: Hungarian Central Statistical Office (KSH)

Figure 14: Hungary Living Lab. The volume of construction output in Hungary, seasonally and working day adjusted data (2010=100%)

Source: Hungarian

Central Statistical Office (KSH)

Figure 15: Hungary Living Lab. Building permits - sqm of useful floor area, (seasonally- and calendar-adjusted data, 2010=100%)

Circular economy in Hungary in the sector: relevant findings

Status today

Circular economy, industrial symbiosis, recycling, resource efficiency etc are not well-known concepts at all in Hungary, although some good examples of initiatives -either in a form of EC supported projects or conferences - exist that deal with these topics meaning that awareness raising amongst stakeholders can never be underestimated. We describe some of these examples in the following.

Relevant Hungarian projects from the Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform

Good Practices related to Hungary were searched in the [database of the European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform](#). The European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform is a virtual open space whose aim is to promote the transition to a circular economy by facilitating policy dialogue among stakeholders and by disseminating activities, information, and good practices on the circular economy.

Two projects were identified:

- **Sharing materials to minimize waste: Industrial Symbiosis Project (Appendix 4).** Aims at supporting the transition towards a resource-efficient economy through industrial symbiosis, establishing territorial synergies to manage waste and exchange energy & by-products as secondary raw resources. This project is very relevant therefore they were contacted to participate in the HU LL.
- **Every can counts (Appendix 5).** Every Can Counts demonstrates the metal packaging industry's commitment to invest in programmes to drive lasting, positive behaviour change and maximise recycling performance. This project is not relevant for the HU LL.

Conference summary: The role of construction and demolition materials in the circular economy

A conference titled „[The role of construction and demolition materials in the circular economy](#)“ was organized for Hungarian stakeholders in Budapest by the [Association of Environmental Enterprises](#) and the Herman Otto Institute in October 2016. The presentations touched upon various legislative and practical technical challenges that are currently formulating areas - including certification of by-products, green public procurement, performance validation, national aggregate policies – all of which have effect on the whole system of waste management in the country.

Assessment of this conference from FISSAC point: some presentations of the conference are highly relevant to FISSAC. As a result, ÉMI was identified as potential key stakeholder to host the HU-LL, the Environment Development Division of the Ministry of Agriculture was first contacted in November 2017 and was informed about FISSAC and its LL objectives in HU that was well received. Read more in Appendix 6

Conference summary: How to move towards the circular economy?

A conference titled “How to move towards the circular economy” was organized by the Association of Environmental Enterprises (KSZGYSZ), Confederation of Hungarian Employers and Industrialists (MGYOSZ), and the National Confederation of Packaging and Handling (CSAOSZ) in November 2016 for Hungarian stakeholders primarily in the waste sector in Budapest to discuss economic and legal measures, as well as opportunities for the Hungarian environmental industry sectors in the European and domestic market. (Agenda and presentations in Hungarian are [available here.](#))

Assessment of this conference from FISSAC point: the presentations of the conference are moderately relevant to FISSAC as they are rather focus on the waste handling side of circular economy in general and in particular to packaging waste.

Start-up of the LL

Since circular economy especially regarding the construction industry is in a very initial phase in Hungary the ambition of the HU LL is to convene existing atomized initiatives to join forces in raising awareness of the topic AND complement, assist the processes (legislative and business) of realizing it with the FISSAC methodology as much as possible.

ÉMI was first identified as potential key stakeholder to host the HU-LL, the Environment Development Division of the Ministry of Agriculture was first contacted in November 2017 and was informed about FISSAC and its LL objectives in HU that was well received.

Two strategic meetings were carried out with ÉMI to discuss preparations for launching the LL HU with regard to its scope to focus on FISSAC related material streams: concrete and wood-rubber-plastic composites were identified to be focussed in Hungary. The ministry official was also consulted and he also approved these two waste streams as important issues that needs to be further advanced.

ÉMI made clear that to their experiences since the whole topic of circular economy in the construction sector in Hungary is in its very initial phase, and stakeholders currently have generally low interest in using secondary raw materials it will be very difficult to draw their attention and build trust and economic reasoning for this topic, however they are willing to use their network of contacts for inviting them to the HU LL.

A draft for a generic call for inviting HU stakeholders to participate in the HU LL series of forums was prepared and discussed with ÉMI (see Appendix: HU LL publications for both the HU version and the complimentary EN version)

Geonardo contacted the Herman Otto Institute (HOI) as it was one of the organisers of the 2016 October event on „[The role of construction and demolition materials in the circular economy](#)“ (see HU LL Q3 report). HOI is a partner in an Interreg Europe project on IS titled [TRIS: Transition Regions towards Industrial Symbiosis](#). (1 Apr 2016- to 31 Mar 2021) with the following objectives:

- Raising awareness on the concepts of IS and its economic and environmental benefits
- Causing a mind-shift and building a cooperation culture in the stakeholder groups (including SMEs and policy actors)
- Standardize IS practices into regional policy instruments
- Launching tangible initiatives in the regions: reaching out to more SMEs, supporting their business with new IS cases/projects, preventing industrial waste production, testing new governance models.
- Bringing IS to a higher position in the European political agenda.

We agreed with HOI to produce project synergies between FISSAC and TRIS to organize an event together by sharing costs of room rent and catering at the largest domestic annual venue place of the construction sector stakeholders, the CONSTRUMA 2018 international Exhibition and Fair.

7.2 The Living Lab today

7.2.1 Purpose and Goal

Since circular economy especially regarding the construction industry is in a very initial phase in Hungary the ambition of the HU LL is to convene existing atomized initiatives to join forces in raising awareness of the topic AND complement, assist the processes (legislative and business) of realizing it with the FISSAC methodology as much as possible.

ÉMI, HOI and the Environment Division of the Ministry of Agriculture were identified as key stakeholders who could assist the launch of the HU LL.

ÉMI is a state owned, non-profit company for quality control and innovation in building who – amongst others - issues authority certificates for construction materials also from secondary raw materials. It is a well-known organisation among all stakeholders in the construction industry in Hungary, it has therefore a wide database of contacts to reach the actors of the extended value chain.

The Environment Division of the Ministry of Agriculture is responsible for transposing relevant EU legislation into regulations in Hungary. The regulation on CDM is under preparation for a long time, and now with a new minister after the general elections in April 2018, the finalisation of this regulation has gained increased attention. The regulation is expected to be published in autumn 2018.

The Herman Otto Institute is a state owned, non-profit company for assisting the Ministry of Agriculture in implementing regulations in the field of agriculture, nature conservation and environment.

Bilateral strategic meetings were organised with these key stakeholders to discuss the main issues that the HU LL should focus on. When identifying the key LL topics we took into account legal, technical and practical aspects.

7.2.2 Scope

We teamed up with ÉMI, HOI and the Environment Division of the Ministry of Agriculture to launch the FISSAC Living Lab in Hungary with the aim of advancing resource efficiency, communication and circularity in the material streams of concrete and wood-rubber-plastic composites, as identified by these key stakeholders. Selective demolition and recycling of concrete as secondary raw material is an increasingly important evergreen topic that is if of -maybe not realized interest – of many actors. To this end CemBeton, Hungarian Cement Concrete and Lime Association as a national umbrella organisation was contacted to become a professional supporter of the HU LL concrete topic, to help widen the scope of actors actually involved. WPC is considered an innovative construction material that is gaining increasing importance and have high business potential in turning specific types of currently considered wastes into value added products requiring communication and collaboration between concerned actors of this value chain.

7.2.3 Identifying stakeholders

ÉMI was first identified as potential key stakeholder to host the HU-LL, the Environment Development Division of the Ministry of Agriculture was first contacted in November 2017 and was informed about FISSAC and its LL objectives in HU that was well received.

A draft for a generic call for inviting HU stakeholders to participate in the HU LL series of forums was prepared and discussed with ÉMI (see Appendix: HU LL publications for both the HU version and the complimentary EN version)

HOI being identified as a key organiser of the 2016 October event on „[The role of construction and demolition materials in the circular economy](#)“ and as a partner in an Interreg Europe project on IS titled [TRIS: Transition Regions towards Industrial Symbiosis](#) was contacted in February 2018. At a bilateral meeting we agreed with HOI to produce project synergies between FISSAC and TRIS to organize an event together by sharing costs of room rent and catering at the largest domestic annual venue place of the construction sector stakeholders, the CONSTRUMA 2018 international Exhibition and Fair. This is considered to be the largest annual event in the construction industry in Hungary and is a gives a hands-on opportunity to raise awareness of the topic in concern.

7.2.4 Stakeholder interactions and activities

Between November 2017 and February 2018 key stakeholders were contacted and bilateral meetings with them were organised to discuss the scope of the HU LL, and of the first LL session.

The organisation of the event was started in March. The aim of the event is to raise awareness of the wider topic and get buy-in for the later forums. The idea was to first attract the greatest number of people possible to this launching

event with interesting presentations relevant to the topic. The title of the event had to be catchy and less technical this is why we chose the “Resource efficiency in the domestic construction industry: Best practices in circular economy and eco-innovation”. HOI invited their contact the [CemBeton: Hungarian Cement Concrete and Lime Association](#) to act as professional supporter who are an umbrella organisation of cement, concrete, lime, admixture producers. They suggested several presenters related to the topic of selective demolition, concrete recycling. Geonardo invited [ÉMI Non-Profit Limited Liability Company for Quality Control and Innovation in Building](#) to act as professional supporter to the event.

ÉMI and CemBeton were invited as professional supporters for two reasons: 1) to justify the professional standard of the event in the eye of potential stakeholders 2) to get access and invite a wide network of stakeholders to the HU LL event as these two key companies have circulated the invitation to the event in their contacts database. CemBeton has also published the event invitation in its regular newsletter to its members. The conference invitation was also published in the official CONSTRUMA 2018 journal.

The conference scoping, invitation text and agenda (see EN version in Appendix) were developed together with the co-organiser, the professional supporters and were regularly consulted with the ministry officials of the Environment Division. The state minister in charge of environmental issues was invited to open the event and the Ministry was officially invited to participate in the FISSAC HU LL. The state minister has appointed ministry officers to contribute to the FISSAC HU LL.

Apart from the FISSAC HU LL page the conference invitation was also published at these sites:

- Greenfo, the largest Hungarian environmental news portal: <http://greenfo.hu/programok/print/2018/04/13/jo-gyakorlatok-a-korforgasos-gazdasag-es-az-okoinnovacio-teren>
- TRIS Interreg project website: <https://www.interregeurope.eu/tris/events/event/1689/fissac-invitation/>
- <https://www.interregeurope.eu/tris/news/news-article/2996/fissac-conference-registration-open/>
- CONSTRUMA’s website: <http://construma.hu/hu/konferencia-programok>
- HOI’s website: <http://www.hermanottointezet.hu/800860>
- CemBeton’s newsletter: <http://www.cembeton.hu/hirlevel/2018-03-27/cembeton-hirlevel-2018-marcius/41/eroforras-hatekonysag-a-hazai-epitoiparban-jo-gyakorlat-a-korforgasos-gazdasag-es-az-okoinnovacio-teren/201>

A registration form for the conference was created in HU (see printscreen in Appendix.)

21 people registered through our reg.form. Without our prior approval the Construma organisers had also opened a registration sheet on their site of conferences, where 86 people registered. It only turned out at the event that the high registration rate at the Construma website to our conference is mainly due to taking advantage of the reduced fee entry tickets offered to the exhibition. This fact unfortunately has highly distorted our aim of measuring the interest in the conference’s topic. Finally, 34 people actual participants showed up including the presenters.

Photos of the event, see Appendix.

HU LL website developments

Generic text for the LL website was translated into Hungarian in November 2017.

Between December 2017 and April 2018 the HU LL website was fully developed both in English and in Hungarian, including the invitation for the LL launch event, downloadable conference programme (HU, EN), call for interest to the series of HU LL for a (HU, EN versions).

A specific email address [forum.fissac \(at\) geonardo.com](mailto:forum.fissac@geonardo.com) was set up to welcome any questions, comments from stakeholders.

The presentations of the HU LL launching conference were made available through the HU LL webpage after the event.

7.2.5 Identifying barriers and drivers

We learnt from the first LL event that despite the facts that 1) we organised our LL launching event to the largest annual venue of the construction industry 2) we tried our utmost in targeting the largest number of stakeholders possible via emails of the conference invitation by our supporting partners and via professional newsletter to concrete industry companies it is very difficult to draw the actual attention, interest of the stakeholders to the topic of circular economy in their sector even with a very catchy economic title of the event like resource efficiency.

7.2.6 Other results

Technical questionnaire questions and results

A technical questionnaire in Hungarian was provided for HU LL participants at the 1st HU LL event both in Google form (see print screen in Appendix) and in printed versions as well. The aim of the questionnaire was on the one hand to explore the basic knowledge and opinion of respondents related to circular economy, industrial symbiosis and secondary raw materials exchange, and on the other hand to help the topic focus development in the LL process. See Appendix 6.

Event evaluation questionnaire results

The event itself was also evaluated by the participants, the results will be considered during the organisation of the further events. The translation of the evaluation questionnaire is available in Appendix.

Figure 16: HU LL 1st event evaluation results

Event evaluation N=8	inadequate	adequate	good	excellent
How do you evaluate the organization of a professional day?				
Preparation and implementation:	0%	13%	38%	50%
Location and circumstances of the event:	0%	38%	50%	13%
Atmosphere/mood of the event:	0%	13%	50%	38%
The usefulness of the information provided in the lectures:	0%	13%	0%	88%
Knowledge and experience exchange:	0%	29%	29%	43%

Positive experiences the participants mentioned included “professional atmosphere”, and “I found very useful the presentation about the legislation underway, the project presentations and practical examples matched well the topic, we received a full picture of the topic.”

Negative experiences the participants mentioned included “the venue is difficult to find”, “disappointment about the low number of participants present despite the importance of the topic”.

All respondents answered with yes to the question if they come to the upcoming forums with detailed and more focussed discussions.

7.2.7 The Living Lab and the FISSAC model

The FISSAC project was introduced in detail at the HU LL launching event. The Head of the Environment Division showed interest in the FISSAC Platform and in the opportunity it may offer for authorities to register secondary raw material streams. We agreed though that a Hungarian version of the platform is necessary as a prerequisite to enable Hungarian stakeholders to use this platform as the English literacy of this sector in particular is very low.

We plan specific bilateral meeting to present the FISSAC Platform in the Ministry and discuss how it could be further customized for their purposes.

7.3 Conclusions

Despite the fact that the output of the construction sector is rapidly increasing in Hungary thanks mainly to the rising number of industrial and storage facilities as well as buildings for educational and sports purposes circular economy, industrial symbiosis, recycling, resource efficiency are not widely known and applied concepts.

Some examples of good practices do exist either in a form of awareness raising projects or to a lesser extent actual collaborations between companies.

Legislation expected to come out by autumn 2018 is seen an important tool to break the current reluctance of the sector and advance resource efficiency by forcing construction sector actors to deal with the issue of circularity.

Since circular economy especially regarding the construction industry is in a very initial phase in Hungary the ambition of the FISSAC HU LL is to convene existing atomized initiatives to join forces in raising awareness of the topic AND complement, assist the processes (legislative and business) of realizing it with the FISSAC methodology as much as possible.

Between November 2017 and February 2018 key stakeholders were contacted and bilateral meetings with them were organised to discuss the scope of the HU LL, and of the first LL session

We teamed up with key stakeholders: ÉMI, HOI and the Environment Division of the Ministry of Agriculture to launch the FISSAC Living Lab in Hungary with the aim of advancing resource efficiency, communication and circularity in the material streams of concrete and wood-rubber-plastic composites, as identified by these key stakeholders.

Selective demolition and recycling of concrete as secondary raw material is an increasingly important evergreen topic that is if of -maybe not realized interest – of many actors. To this end CemBeton, Hungarian Cement Concrete and Lime Association as a national umbrella organisation was contacted to become a professional supporter of the HU LL concrete topic, to help widen the scope of actors actually involved.

WPC is considered an innovative construction material that is gaining increasing importance and have high business potential in turning specific types of currently considered wastes into value added products requiring communication and collaboration between concerned actors of this value chain.

We agreed with HOI to produce project synergies between FISSAC and TRIS to organize an event together by sharing costs of room rent and catering at the largest domestic annual venue place of the construction sector stakeholders, the CONSTRUMA 2018 international Exhibition and Fair. The event took place on 13 April 2018 in Budapest.

ÉMI and CemBeton were invited as professional supporters for two reasons: 1) to justify the professional standard of the event in the eye of potential stakeholders 2) to get access and invite a wide network of stakeholders to the HU LL event as these two key companies have circulated the invitation to the event in their contacts database. CemBeton has also published the event invitation in its regular newsletter to its members. The conference invitation was also published in the official CONSTRUMA 2018 journal.

We learnt from the first LL event that despite the facts that 1) we organised our LL launching event to the largest annual venue of the construction industry 2) we tried our utmost in targeting the largest number of stakeholders possible via emails of the conference invitation by our supporting partners and via professional newsletter to concrete industry companies it is very difficult to draw the actual attention, interest of the stakeholders to the topic of circular economy in their sector even with a very catchy economic title of the event like resource efficiency.

Our professional supporters have explained this lack of not getting enough actual attendees despite their efforts with the current lack of legislation or compulsory push of the industry to deal with this issue.

Basic legislation and practical challenges in the sector include

- monitoring the handling of construction/demolition wastes is difficult,
- distribution of responsibilities and liabilities is unclear
- deficiencies in the field of data register and data reporting
- there is no distinct legislation for CDWs generated during major investments and for those coming from small scale constructions of citizens
- no rules for selecting waste during demolition
- no rules for handling CDW whose generation rate exceeds 10 tonnes per day
- in the current system landfill is dominating.

Challenges in the field of reusing materials from demolition and preparation of secondary raw materials for reuse:

- production of construction materials from secondary raw materials is currently costly
- no public procurement obligation exist currently to use recycled construction materials for construction works
- detailed rules for construction products from CDW raw materials are lacking
- system for certifying end-of-waste status is lacking.

For the upcoming focus group type LL events with more specific topics we will take invitations down to individuals' level and with the help of our professional supporters identify the most appropriate persons of key companies to be invited both in writing (mail, email) and orally (telephone). We will also try to get more visual support and engagement from the Environmental Division of the Ministry to gain more attendance of concerned actors.

7.4 Planned future work

Two more focussed workshops are planned probably during autumn with the following specific topics

- separate demolition and recycling concrete, to be hosted at HOI's premises with professional support from [CemBeton: Hungarian Cement Concrete and Lime Association](#)
- wood, rubber, plastics as secondary raw materials for composites, to be hosted at ÉMI's premises with their professional support.
- At both events the FISSAC Platform will also be discussed.

The 4th LL event, a consolidation event is planned for the first half of 2019.

7.5 List of Appendices

Appendix 4 Hungary LL: Project descriptions

Appendix 5 Hungary LL: Conference summary

Appendix 6 Hungary LL: Questionnaire

Appendix 7 Hungary LL: Publications, photos related to the HU LL event

Appendix 8 Hungary LL: References

- Project description :
- HU LL invitation flyer
- Invitation to the 1st HU LL event and to the series of for a
- Programme of the 1st HU LL event
- Online registration page for the conference
- Project leaflet in HU with customized last page for the HU LL purposes
- Technical questionnaire in Hungarian provided for HU LL participants in Google form
- FISSAC HU LL X-banner
- Photos of the HU LL launching event (13/04/2018)
- GEO Twitter post about the HU LL launching event
- HU LL event evaluation questionnaire

8 Italy

In the framework of FISSAC project, several events will be organized in Italy with the aim of investigating the local context and defining together the most appropriate strategy to promote industrial symbiosis, tackling the main challenges for its establishment. More in details, Italian Living Labs have the purpose to:

- Gather and query stakeholders in the FISSAC scenario;
- Investigate the technological and non-technological factors that can affect the process of industrial symbiosis;
- Optimize the FISSAC model based on the experiences of the participants.

In order to ensure a recognizable visual identity for the Italian Living Labs, a logo were designed and it will be used in all the communication products and in official documents. The Italian Living Labs logo is shown in the following figure.

Figure 17: Italian Living Lab Logo

The Italian Living Labs are organized and managed by RINA Consulting S.p.A., the largest fully independent Italian firm providing consulting and engineering services to clients belonging both to the public and private sectors.

8.1 The sector and the Living Lab – Starting point

The starting point in the organization of the First Italian Living Lab was the definition of the sector and industrial symbiosis opportunities to be investigated. In this framework, since the Italian partners involved in the FISSAC project (FERALPI and CSM) are mainly related to the steel sector, it was decided to take advantage of their expertise, investigating the specific IS opportunities of this sector^{5,6}.

The steel industry is the second biggest industry in the world after oil and gas, with an estimated global turnover of 900 billion USD. Four routes are currently used worldwide for the steel production: the classic blast furnace/basic oxygen furnace route (BF/BOF), the direct melting of scrap (electric arc furnace - EAF), smelting reduction and direct reduction. In particular, the direct melting of scrap (EAF - Electric Arc Furnace) is the most diffuse route through which is produced approximately half of the steel manufactured in Europe (around 85 million tons of steel in 2004).

Furnace slag, the solid by-product from steel production, can be reused as raw material after recovery and processing. Under FISSAC project, main attention is given to EAF (Electric Arc Furnace) and LF (Ladle Furnace) slag that can be reused as aggregates and construction materials. According to the analysis performed within FISSAC WP1 "From current models of Industrial Symbiosis to a new model", the main reuse opportunities of steel slag are in pavements, in mortar, in ceramic, in cement and concrete.

8.2 The Living Lab today

In order to define the main purpose and scope of the Italian Living Lab as well as to identify the relevant stakeholders, RINA Consulting together with FERALPI, investigated the opportunity to involve in the LL organization the Industrial Association of Brescia (AIB – Associazione Industriale Bresciana - <http://www.aib.bs.it/>), city located in northern Italy

⁵ FISSAC Project – Deliverable 1.3 "Inventory of raw materials, waste and energy flows in industrial sectors (Metallurgic, Ceramic, Glass, Chemical and Natural stone) considered in a dynamic scenario", February 2016

⁶ FISSAC Project – Deliverable 1.5 "Assessment of BAT and emerging techniques to facilitate the collaboration across sectors", August 2016

where many steel and cement/concrete industries are sited. The meeting for facing LL planning took place in Brescia in August 2017 and it was attended by RINAC, FERALPI and AIB. During this meeting, RINAC presented the FISSAC project and in particular the activities related to the Living Lab organization, then thematic relevant for the AIB associates was discussed and taken as starting point for the LL detailed design. The presentation done during the meeting is shown in the following figure.

Figure 18: Italian Living Lab organization meeting

According to the discussion among RINAC, FERALPI and AIB representatives during the LL organization meeting, the following goals and stakeholders have been identified for the First Italian Living Lab.

8.2.1 Purpose and goal

The First Italian Living Lab aimed to disseminate FISSAC concept and to address themes related to the Industrial Symbiosis, with particular reference to steel and cement sector. The scope of the first Italian Living Lab was to collect feedback from different stakeholders to exploit their experiences, difficulties and necessity for optimizing and validating FISSAC Model. In particular, it was focused on:

- To reflect on industrial symbiosis opportunities;
- To share and analyze experiences, difficulties and needs;
- To identify routes and solutions for overcoming non-technological barriers.

8.2.2 Identifying stakeholders and activities

The event was developed for various exponents of Brescia Industrial reality, mainly related to steel, cement and concrete sectors, together with builders, university representatives and other professionals linked to these realities. The common objective and starting point was the desire to investigate opportunities for industrial symbiosis, with particular reference to the reuse of steel slag from EAF.

In order to engage as much stakeholders as possible, the First Italian Living Lab was publicized on the FISSAC website and through direct invitation. In particular, a flyer of the event has been developed by RINAC, including a short description of the FISSAC project and providing information about Living Lab objectives. The flyer is shown in the following figure.

Figure 19: First Italian Living Lab Flyer

8.2.3 Identifying barriers and drivers

The First Italian Living Lab, was held in Brescia at the AIB headquarter on 10th November 2017. The managing strategy and results are briefly summarized in the following.

The FISSAC project and its objectives, together with a general overview of the activities carried out so far in the project, were firstly presented during the Living Lab. In particular, to start the debate, the results of the research on non-technological barriers, carried out by the project partners, were illustrated. The barriers were presented divided into four categories (economic, legislative, social and structural), and together some possible solutions were proposed to overcome them. These barriers are shown in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Italian Living Lab. Non-technological barriers

The stakeholders were asked, starting from this preliminary list used as a starting point for the discussion, to provide feedback, based on their daily experience, in order to identify the main obstacles encountered in the Italian situation, and to identify together potentials mitigation actions.

10 novembre 2017

Brescia – Associazione industriale bresciana

Figure 21: Italian Living Lab Photos

What has emerged is that the participants of the event have long **looked with interest to the theme of the circular economy**, and study how to establish processes of industrial symbiosis in their realities. This need arises not only from the desire to make their processes more sustainable, but also from the **awareness** that the gravel of a quarry is a natural resource, which is expected for the future an increasingly limited availability of excavation due to environmental and protection aspects of land, and that the reception capacity of landfill sites will always be smaller. This leads companies to look for alternative solutions: steel mills are trying to reduce the amount of waste to be disposed of, and quarry workers and manufacturers of construction materials are looking for new alternatives to gravel, especially for less noble applications such as road foundations.

From this first comparison, however, it immediately became clear that, despite the desire to move to a circular economy, the industries of Brescia are often faced with **bureaucratic-legislative difficulties**, which make the re-use of steel slag a complex and not feasible option. This, according to the participants, is the main reason why a large part of the produced slag ends up in landfills.

On the basis of current regulations, steel mills are generally currently operating waste as a **waste or by-product**, and based on this decision, the regulatory framework changes completely; the **End of Waste route** is a road currently not yet viable, since there are still no directives concerning steel slag. However, according to the participants, the **regulatory framework is not clear**, but rather subject to different interpretations and applications that vary from region to region: even different dates of disposal/recovery can lead to different regulatory scenarios and different interpretations.

Hence the need to standardize the interpretation of the regulatory framework and related technical standards to the greatest extent possible.

In this sense, AIB in collaboration with Federacciai is carrying out, through Unisider, the proposal for a reference practice for steel slag aimed at better defining the methods for preparing samples to be submitted to the release test according to the UNI EN 12457 standard.

Other proposals, aimed at a more specific definition of the tests for the slag as a by-product to check its environmental compatibility and based on criteria and methods used at the level of European product registration (REACH), have already been discussed with the competent bodies.

In addition, at Ecomondo 2017 (International Fair for the recovery of materials and energy and sustainable development), the new **technical standards** were recently presented (on the use in concrete and combined materials), to try to facilitate companies in undertaking this path.

The difficulties encountered by companies, however, are not just laws and regulations: another obstacle that companies often face is having to overcome the **distrust** of customers, who often still consider the reuse of slag as an experimental application (e.g. inside concrete or asphalt). Based on experiences in the Brescia area, public commissions show that they do not appreciate this material, since it is almost impossible to find it in **public tenders**: it can even be specified that the slag cannot be used or at the limit included only in small percentages (10-20%). This fact obviously limits considerably the possible applications of this product, which could instead be encouraged in new specifications that enhance and promote the use of recycled materials, such as slag, in combined or uncombined manufactured products. On the other hand, this road is currently already taken in other regions, where it is accepted by large commissions, especially because of an actual lack of natural materials.

The distrust of customers could be, at least in part, also fueled by the **resistance of public opinion and some environmental associations**. To overcome this difficulty, it could be useful to carry out studies aimed at objectively quantifying the impacts/benefits of these solutions, promoting their use through **information campaigns** and involving citizens in the decision-making process linked to their implementation. In this regard, the University of Brescia is already moving in this direction, with the aim of increasing the volume and solidity of the studies supporting the re-use practices of steel slag.

If these barriers, often encountered by the participating industries, could be overcome, the entire annual production of EAF slag from the Brescia area could find a market, for example, in concretes, cemented mixtures and asphalts. In fact, there is no problem of volumes, but the lack of a recognized **market space**, deriving from a consolidated willingness to accept this material. The **interchange platform** that will be developed within the FISSAC project could at least partly respond to this need, especially if we could find a way to recognize or certify the exchanges that take place through it. Technological barriers are not considered as relevant by industrial stakeholders, since the use of EAF slag from steelworks in concrete or asphalt is now rather **technologically tested**, given that an adequate level of specialization it is always necessary to use this type of material. The only aspect that could create difficulties is that the products made with the slag **weigh more** (up to 30% more than the natural material) and therefore have a **lower volumetric yield compared to the use of natural inert**. This aspect has a greater impact on transport and must be taken into consideration also from a structural point of view; these materials are in fact more suitable for non-suspended horizontal **applications**, in which they can be used up to 90% and result also more resistant to wear and impact, while they are less suitable for applications that develop vertically and in height due to the higher specific weight of the artifacts.

In general, the challenge of competitiveness **from an economic point of view** remains open; the realization of a quality product currently leads to a final cost approximately equivalent to products made with traditional raw materials. This is one of the reasons why private companies hardly choose the products made with the slag. Also from the point of view of the slag producers who directly certify it as a building material, the cost of transport is certainly a critical factor for the sale.

The topics discussed during the meeting are summarized in Figure 22.

FOSTERING INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS FOR A SUSTAINABLE RESOURCE INTENSIVE INDUSTRY ACROSS THE EXTENDED CONSTRUCTION VALUE CHAIN

8.2.4 The Living Lab and the FISSAC Model

As described in previous paragraphs, one of the objective of the Italian Living Labs is the optimization of the FISSAC Model. In order to achieve this goal, aspects of the FISSAC model are discussed and validated during the Italian Living Labs and main results of the Living Labs are used to optimize the model itself. In this context, FISSAC Model and Italian Living Labs have a bidirectional exchange of data, information, challenges, drivers and solutions.

Figure 23 Italian Living Lab and FISSAC Model relation

As previously explained, the First Italian Living Lab started with the discussion of the non-technological barriers to the establishment of industrial symbiosis, analysed in WP2 “Closed Loop Recycling Processes to transform waste into Secondary Raw Materials” and included in the FISSAC Model (developed in WP6 “FISSAC Model for Industrial Symbiosis”). During the First Italian Living Lab, participants have provided their positive feedback about the work done, underlining the main aspects that they have to face in their real life context, when they manage the reuse of steel slag. According to the results of the discussion, several aspect should be managed or deeply analysed in the FISSAC Model, as summarised below.

- Bureaucratic-legislative difficulties resulted to be a relevant barrier to the establishment of IS opportunities in Italy. In particular, the participants made evidence to the importance to clearly identify if steel mills operate waste as waste or by-product, since the regulatory framework changes completely. This suggestion, extended also to other sectors in the FISSAC Scenario, directly affect the FISSAC Model and in particular the FISSAC Platform. In fact, when a “Facility user” searches possible IS opportunities on the FISSAC Platform should specify how its waste are classified or which kind of materials (waste or by-product) it can accept in entrance in its facility. This feature was not already included in the FISSAC Platform structure that will be updated accordingly.
- The distrust of customers, fueled by the resistance of public opinion and some environmental associations, resulted another obstacle that companies often face. To overcome this difficulty, FISSAC Model could provide valuable methodology for objectively quantifying the impacts/benefits of IS opportunities. Moreover, the data extracted from the FISSAC Platform could be used in information campaign for promoting Industrial Symbiosis.
- The lack of a recognized market space resulted an additional barrier that could be at least partially overcome thanks to the FISSAC Platform. In this framework, the main challenge of FISSAC Model is to find a way to recognize or certify the exchanges that take place through the platform.

8.3 Conclusions and planned future work

In conclusion, the main need identified by the participants in the Living Lab is to provide greater clarity in the regulatory framework and uniformity in its interpretation, so that the process of industrial symbiosis is not inhibited, due to bureaucratic-legislative difficulties. At the same time, the stakeholders also described other problems encountered rather frequently in this context: the distrust of public opinion and customers, the criticality of the economic aspect and the lack of a recognized market space. The technological aspect, although presenting some difficulties, is considered less critical by the participants in reference to the reuse of the EAF slag, since there is now a good number of practices tested for the industrial symbiosis with the production of concrete, mixed cement and asphalt.

For the future, the participants have shown interest in extending the analysis of drivers and barriers in others Italian geographical areas and in other context (investigation of other IS opportunities, among different sectors), and to further investigate the FISSAC project and in particular the platform that will be implemented, to evaluate if this tool could meet their needs. Moreover, they have suggested to analyze in detail the social acceptance of new products in order to find a solution to overcome the resistance of public opinion.

RINA Consulting, together with other Italian partners involved in Living Labs organization, are considering these topics as starting point for the Second Italian Living Lab, planned for the next months.

9. Spain

SÍMBIOSY is an environmental consulting/engineering company specialized in circular economy and its implementation tool for the industry: the industrial symbiosis. SÍMBIOSY is responsible for the Spanish Living Lab.

The role of SÍMBIOSY is being the facilitator within industrial symbiosis projects, assisting municipalities or industrial areas managers with the tools, methodology and knowledge to implement and develop synergies among companies/organizations of a territory: we identify possible synergies and work with the companies to make them happen, all from a territorial/ecosystem approach. The final goal: resource efficiency and industry competitiveness improvement.

9.1 The sector and the Living Lab – starting point

The sector & status today

The built environment sector is a major consumer of natural resources: the engineering and construction industry consumes worldwide more than 3bn tonnes of raw materials annually⁷. This implies that the design and development of circular strategies have already become a necessity.

Changes are beginning to be visible: some manufacturers are already designing products that are made out of secondary raw materials, which can be also reused or repurposed. On the other hand, new business models based on the return, rent, or sharing of products, spaces, and services are starting to come up.

However, there are no clear strategies of how individual companies will need to change across the industry yet. In order to make circular economy happen, different scales such as assets, buildings, infrastructures, cities and regions must be integrated into an interconnected whole. Without cross-sector collaboration and communication among the stakeholders of the construction and demolition supply chain, the implementation of the tools that the circular economy can provide, such as the industrial symbiosis, will never succeed.

Start-up of the LL

The organisation of the Living Labs was initiated within the FISSAC project. However, the team at SÍMBIOSY has been organising workshops/events with a similar methodology within the past years.

9.2 The Living Lab today

9.2.1 Purpose and Goal

The overall goal of the Living Labs is fundamentally to approach complex challenges that exist in an evolving real-life context through the collaboration, co-creation, and exchange of ideas among stakeholders.

The global objectives of the Living Labs Barcelona are:

- To create a proper environment to reflect openly about the role of the Circular Economy and the Industrial Symbiosis within the construction and demolition sector
- To apply a whole value chain approach
- To identify the tools needed to make Industrial Symbiosis happen
- To gather feedback for the development of the FISSAC Platform
- To provide continuity to the Living Lab experience. The aim is that the network created throughout the organization of the different Living Labs shall continue working together as a WG once the FISSAC project has finished.

⁷ https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Shaping_the_Future_of_Construction_report_020516.pdf

9.2.2 Scope

SÍMBIOSY has organized one Living Lab to date and is currently organising the second one.

The objective of the first Living Lab Barcelona had a general scope: to jointly debate about how companies of the construction and demolition sector can optimize their resources by means of industrial symbiosis tools. Using a participative approach, attendees had the opportunity to expose their points of view and discuss with the rest of stakeholders about the development of new business models that might transform the actual construction industry in a more circular one.

9.2.3 Identifying stakeholders

We need to get the whole supply chain together to show the opportunities, identify the necessities and discuss how to work together. Consequently, we paid special attention to the design of the participant list of the first LL and we divided the 25 participants in 6 different working groups: building promoters, material providers, building constructors, maintenance companies, deconstruction & waste management companies/agencies, and design & innovation representatives from universities and architecture studios.

Since we co-organised the event together with the ITeC (the Catalonia Institute of Construction Technology), we had access to their professional network and we could easily create a multi-sectorial participant list.

9.2.4 Stakeholder interactions and activities

The main structure of the first Living Lab can be divided in three parts: an introductory presentation, the workshoping/debate activities, and a conclusion part to summarize the main outcomes and define the topic of the next LL (the approximate length was 3 hours).

For the workshoping activities, and in order to discuss about the impacts (positive and negative ones), necessities and opportunities of both the current and the possible “more circular” scenario within the construction sector, we designed a template that served as a debate basis to encourage interaction among the 6 different working groups (see pictures and templates at the Appendix).

9.2.5 Identifying barriers and drivers

During the first Living Lab, the different working groups put their ideas together and discussed about possible solutions that might tackle current barriers related to the circular scenario. Some of the proposals were:

- Create an ecoinnovation observatory that allows interested stakeholders to know each other: promote collaboration and build trust among them
- Drive a cultural change: inform customers and users about the environmental traceability of the products/materials/services they acquire so that they become more active and conscious about the spaces they inhabit
- Reward and give visibility to local best practices
- Learn from successful initiatives from other countries
- Provide training in Circular Economy/Industrial Symbiosis

9.2.6 The Living Lab and the FISSAC model

Since the thematic of the first LL was rather general, we didn't gather any concrete information that may serve as direct feedback for the FISSAC model. However, we intend to do so at the next event.

9.3 Conclusions

To spend time defining the suitable participant list is fundamental for the success of the Living Labs. It is not only crucial to choose the appropriate entities/organizations/institutions, but to invite the right representatives: people who are already working on circular strategies (or that at least they are willing to do so!), creative, open minded, proactive, and collaborative people. These are the participants you need to make the most of a Living Lab.

9.4 Planned future work

“We all know that the circular economy isn’t just about resources; it’s about people too”. That was one of the main common outcomes of the debate carried out during the first Living Lab.

The reality is that the social dimension is often overseen during the implementation of projects, and the emphasis of the work is put mostly on more technical aspects. Therefore, we have decided to focus on social aspects at our next Living Lab.

The second Living Lab will take place after the summer break, so we are currently detailing the agenda, the methodology, and the participant list.

9.5 List of Appendices

Appendix 9 Spain LL: Templates

Appendix 10 Spain LL: Pictures from the first Living Lab Barcelona 23.01.2018

10 Sweden

10.1 The sector and the Living Lab – starting point

The sector

According to the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, one third of all waste and one-fourth of all hazardous waste produced in Sweden originates from the construction sector. Therefore, construction and demolition waste is prioritised in the national waste plan and in the waste prevention program.⁸ The most common materials in the waste fraction are wood, metal, plastics and concrete.

During the three living lab meetings (out of five), the goal was to look more into the sector of gypsum plasterboards. The material gypsum was chosen jointly by the participants in the living lab, with the rationale that it is a common material that is suitable for (material) recycling, but the recovery rate is low today. The biggest challenges to increase the rates are too few recycling companies on the market, low price of raw material and low level of knowledge on the construction and demolition site. However, there are no technological barriers today that affect increasing the recycling rates. Therefore it was really important to sit around the table with actors from whole value chain who could have an open discussion between each other what they could do in order to help the sector to get better.

Industrial Symbiosis in the sector

Industrial symbiosis and circular economy are not well-known expressions today in Swedish building sector, however, the topic is coming more and more on the picture. Therefore, it was important to start Living Labs with a general introduction of industrial symbiosis and circular economy. However, there are several research projects together with big building companies that have started to focus more on the problem. For example, Swedish company, NCC, that developed a platform *Loop Rock* for the smarter and more efficient handling of rock, earth and other secondary construction masses at construction site, between businesses and private individuals.⁹ Another example is Competence Centre Recycling that has a goal of being a network and catalyst for multidisciplinary R&D collaboration within the field of circular use of materials.¹⁰

Start-up of the LL

The concept of Living Labs in Sweden and the idea of inviting different actors from all building sector together around one table was initiated within the FISSAC project. Therefore, the aim of the first living lab was to introduce generally industrial symbiosis and circular economy, as well as FISSAC, and meet people who are working within the sector. Moreover, the idea was to get to know what different actors are waiting from the project and create a foundation to a network. The first meet-up gave a good input to a whole journey and today there has been 5 living labs in different parts of Sweden.

10.2 The Living Lab today

Living Labs in Sweden have been carried out since autumn 2016 and are jointly organized by Hifab and the Swedish Research Institute, RISE. The participants of the Swedish Living Lab represent a broad constellation of actors both from public and private sector. By gathering these different actors into conversations and joint activities in a neutral platform, we can create an open and cross-border climate where we develop new ideas and innovation for moving towards a more circular use of material resources.

The first, introductory meeting, led by Hifab and SP, aimed to generate interest to be part of the living lab events during the following two years and build a foundation to a network working with circular material flow.

⁸ Avfall Sverige (2017) Swedish Waste Management.

https://www.avfallsverige.se/fileadmin/user_upload/Publikationer/Avfallshantering_2017_eng_low.pdf

⁹ <https://www.ncc.group/our-offer/customer-values/digital-construction/loop-rocks/>

¹⁰ <https://www.chalmers.se/en/centres/ccr/Pages/default.aspx>

The topic for **the second meeting** (M18) was *“Material logbook of the Future - what kind of information should it entail and how should it be used so that it would function as a helpful tool for increasing circular material flow in the construction sector?”* that was proposed by the Swedish Construction Industries during Living Lab meeting #1 and welcomed by the other Living lab participants.

For **meeting 3-5**, the participants proposed to follow with a topic covering the **whole construction process of a building material**: from extraction of the virgin material, through production and usage, to waste and recycling. We had jointly decided to use gypsum/plasterboards as a case study on the flow of building material throughout the process, as this material has great potential for recycling without degrading in quality.

10.2.1 Purpose and Goal

The group consists of representatives from throughout the value chain with representation from municipalities, planning offices, architects, construction firms, material producers, demolition and recycling firms etc. Together the group members have created their own focus area for the lab gatherings, focusing on creating better understanding of the value chain and how to design a better framework for the data needed to increase circularity of materials in the value chain.

10.2.2 Scope

The scope for the Living Lab meetings have not been the same all five meetings, but important to note is that the scope have been suggested by the participants (except for the first introductory meeting). We believe that the participants have the best knowledge of the industry and know the main barriers for a circular use of materials and also have the best ideas to overcome the barriers.

10.2.3 Identifying stakeholders

In Living Lab SE, we have really made an effort to bring together participants representing all actors in the value chain of the construction sector. Together the participants represent a broad constellation of actors from both public and private sector; construction contractors and developers, property owners, material producers, municipality, architects, researchers, sustainability consultants and also a representative from the Swedish construction federation. This broad constellation was recognized already at the first meeting as an advantage for the Living Lab.

For each new meeting with the Living Lab SE, we have analyzed whether any stakeholder is missing, for example if the group has lack of competence in a specific area or if we lack a stakeholder to have full cover of the value chain. Key stakeholders have been asked to contribute to the agenda or in some cases host the meetings.

10.2.4 Stakeholder interactions and activities

The **first living lab, introductory meeting** (M14) aimed to generate interest to be part of the living lab events during the following two years and build a foundation to a network working with circular material flow. Together the participants represented a broad constellation of actors both from public and private sector that was also recognized as an advantage for the Living Lab.

The day ended in consensus that FISSAC’s living labs can in a longer perspective help to advance the efforts on creating circular material flow in the construction sector. The actors present expressed the need for more awareness-raising activities and more knowledge of good examples of material flow in the industry. There was also a consensus around the lack of relevant business models, policy instruments and standards today. Read more in Appendix 1.

The topic for **the second meeting** (M18) *“Material logbook of the Future - what kind of information should it entail and how should it be used so that it would function as a helpful tool for increasing circular material flow in the construction sector?”* was proposed by the Swedish Construction Industries during Living Lab meeting #1 and welcomed by the other Living lab participants.

A general interest of standardizing information about material content and characteristics was expressed. The idea was followed by a discussion of independent evaluation and a need for an organization to carry out the evaluation of quality, characters, content etc of (recycled) materials. One of the proposed ideas was to create or enjoin an existing public actor. Read more in Appendix 2.

The **third meeting** (M21) was the start of the journey to look the flow of a building material throughout the whole value chain. The participants of the living lab 2 had jointly decided to use gypsum/plasterboards as a case study. The focus of the meeting was on the recycling step and the participants were given a guided tour at SUEZ recycling plant in Kovic, Stockholm, where they learned about treatment of the material and recycling conditions. They also addressed the inflow of the material to the site by watching video clips with interviews with a carpenter, construction project manager and a demolition worker.

The learning point of the day was that gypsum has a big potential to be recycled. A plasterboard is completely recyclable and a new board may contain up to about 25% of recycled material. But according to the present representative from the material supplier, there is not enough recycled material available. Participants also learned that up to 20% of the plasterboards delivered to the construction site may become waste, meaning that every fifth plasterboard is manufactured unnecessarily. Read more in Appendix 3.

The **fourth Living Lab meeting** (M19) was a continuation of the gypsum journey and was conducted in the plasterboards manufacturing company, Gyproc, in Bålsta. The aim of the visit was to get an overview of the production of gypsum plasterboards, including the logistics of the raw material to the plant and finished boards out from the industry. Participants saw the possibility to develop (stricter) regulations and rules around recycling plasterboards. In addition, a better and less time consuming documentation would also help to increase the recycling rates. Read more in Appendix 4.

The **fifth meeting** (M22.) was the third and the last meeting to discuss the gypsum/plasterboards recycling possibilities and technological innovation system (TIS) was used to draw the final conclusions. The participants had an open discussion around possibilities and challenges of technology and knowledge, actors, network, institutions in the value chain of gypsum/plasterboards. All the participants were unanimous that today there are all the actors needed on the market and there is no lack of technology but the need to coordinate more different actors and create different links between them. In other words, more communication.

10.2.5 Identifying barriers and drivers

Even though the living labs in Sweden have been planned and coordinated by two actors, Hifab and RISE, decisions on how the lab should go further have been taken in consensus with the group members. The participants have been able to decide what topics they would like to know about and how the meetings should be built up. It has been a good benefit and a driver to include a lot of different actors from the whole value chain and to have open discussions among them. However, it has shown very clearly that a primary barrier are social factors, such as trust and experience of working cross-border, and the importance of these issues should not be underestimated.

Barriers and drivers in the studied value chain of plasterboards have been studied in Living Labs 3-5 and are described in detail in the *Report on Use of Adapted TIS Analysis in the FISSAC Project¹¹* (T7.2). The most important barriers to mention are lack of good statistics on waste and recycled amounts, few recycling companies, deficits in regulation and the low cost for virgin raw material. Among the drivers we see a high level of knowledge and good competency among the actors in the value chain and we also see that the technology needed to recycle plasterboards is already existing.

11 Report: <http://fissacproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/FISSAC-2018-Use-of-Adapted-TIS-Analysis-in-the-FISSAC-Project.pdf>.

10.2.6 The Living Lab and the FISSAC model

The Swedish Living Lab was set up as a pilot case to collect valuable information to the other Living Labs within the project. For that reason no tools or guidelines have been available.

10.3 Conclusions

In the fifth living lab, that also ended the gypsum journey, TIS analysis was used in order to discuss and conclude the findings from three previous living labs. It helped to learn more about possibilities and barriers to increase recycling of gypsum at deconstruction with representatives from gypsum producers, the construction firms, firms working with waste management and recycling as well as firms working with deconstruction of buildings.

The TIS analysis included the areas of Technology and Knowledge, Actors, Network, Institutions. Some of the biggest challenges are: (1) too few recycling companies on the market; (2) cheap price of the raw material that does not motivate plasterboard producers to use a recycled gypsum; (3) a lot of gypsum waste is ending up in the landfill fraction that could be sorted out already on the building/demolition site. Among others the possibilities to increase the recycling rates are: (1) increased knowledge; (2) modified gypsum plasterboard orders that would reduce the waste from building; (3) higher requirements from the top to recycling the old plasterboards.

More about the findings and conclusions can be read in *Report on Use of Adapted TIS Analysis in the FISSAC Project*.

In this case the non-technical factors have shown to be of great importance and it has been clear that social factors should never be underestimated.

10.4 Planned future work

The sixth meeting with Living Lab SE is preliminary set to September 2018. The plan is to use an existing building as a case study on a building as a “material bank”. This building has been used for industrial purposes and in a few years it will be demolished and the real estate developed into an urban residential area. The Living Lab works aim to identify opportunities and barriers for recycling and reusing of the materials in this specific building.

10.5 List of Appendices

Appendix 11 Sweden LL: Summary of the First Living Lab Meeting

Appendix 12 Sweden LL: Summary of LL2- 2017-02-01

Appendix 13 Sweden LL: Summary of LL3-2017-05-02

Appendix 14 Sweden LL: Summary of LL4 2017-06-17

11. Turkey

TCMB, as the common voice of the cement industry, is fully acting under the rules of free market economy and is representing a total of 68 enterprises in Turkey, as 49 of them being integrated facilities and 19 grinding plant. Thanks to this organizational structure, it is easy to address the whole cement/concrete and related sector in social issues in Turkey.

At FISSAC, TCMB is responsible for eco-cement production at laboratory/pilot and industrial scale. For these new eco-cement based materials production, waste materials from related construction sectors such as steel, glass, ceramic, nonferrous, chemical, and construction will be used.

11.1 The Living Lab today

Until today, the list of the stakeholders has been identified but no meetings organized yet. The plan is to organize the Living Lab together with Ekodenge, who will demonstrate the software platform.

11.1.1 Purpose and Goal

The Living Labs general scope is to raise awareness of stakeholders and related participant sectors about industrial symbiosis and best practices applications, focus on cement and concrete production by using secondary raw materials.

11.1.2 Identifying stakeholders

Ceramic, Glass, Iron&Steel Manufacturers, Cement Manufacturers and Ready Mix Concrete producers are the stakeholders of Living Lab in Turkey. Also policy makers can be added in the stakeholders in order to widen the participant circle.

After identifying the stakeholders list a related announcement about Turkish LL will be made and according to the feedbacks LL will be organized. Before the organization a pre-session will be arranged with all the possible stakeholders in order to create network between them.

11.1.3 Work plan

First draft of Turkish LL work plan is listed as below:

Identifying stakeholders ✓

1. Arranging questionnaire for both technical and non-technical topics
2. Preparing leaflet about LL
3. Organizing a pre-workshop with our technical committee consisting quality managers of Turkish Cement Sector
4. Evaluating the results of questionnaire
5. Finally organizing LL meeting with our FISSAC partner Ekodenge in order to have a chance for testing FISSAC software platform with participants.

Until today, only identifying of the stakeholders part of working plan can be completed. The rest of this working plan will be planned to complete till the end of this year.

11.1.4 Identifying barriers and drivers

Some barriers related with this LL have already been identified before hand. The Living Lab concept is not well-known in Turkey and most of the people in the construction sectors are not familiar with this way of working. Hence, it might be difficult to convince them about the potential of finding profitable business opportunities through Living Lab process. This is probably the biggest barrier for setting up Living Labs.

The same barrier might be found connected to the Fissac software platform. There is not a big demand for secondary raw materials yet. The market is not developed. Therefore it might be difficult to convince the stakeholders about the need for a platform. A technical barrier is also the lack of continuous and high speed network connections which might make it hard for stakeholders to use the tool.

12 UK

British Glass and Glass Technology Services (GTS) lead the FISSAC work on glass. GTS is a leading provider of innovation, analysis, mechanical and performance testing, due diligence support and quality assessment of glass. British Glass is a trade association that helps UK glass manufacturing and recycling industries have the influence, knowledge and skills to be world leading and globally competitive.

12.1 The sector and the Living Lab – starting point

The sector

8.5 million tonnes of sheet glass are manufactured in Europe each year for use in windows, architectural facades, internal partitions and vehicle windscreens.

Status today

Europe generates 1.5 million tonnes of waste sheet glass each year from building refurbishment and demolition projects¹². Whilst some of this glass is currently recycled back to glass manufacture or other higher end secondary uses, it is believed that most of this is crushed into aggregate or sent to landfill. There is no consistent collection of data in of recycling of glass from building and construction so estimates of recycling amounts are difficult.

Current demolition or deconstruction and transport techniques often make the glass too contaminated for higher end secondary or closed loop reuse.

Post consumer glass is a relatively low value material and therefore is often not considered economic to recover and do is often overlooked in circular economy discussions in the construction industry

If sheet glass could be collected for recycling, it can be used to make a variety of new glass products, or to manufacture secondary materials such as eco cement and eco concrete. Glass back to glass is the best environmental option in terms of carbon dioxide savings, but utilizing glass in any way is better than losing this valuable resource to landfill.

Some sheet glass recycling operations already exist in Europe. In the UK, which we are using as a deep dive case study in FISSAC, there are already good recycling systems for ‘pre-consumer’ waste sheet glass (offcuts from glazing manufacturing), and some recycling of ‘post-consumer’ waste windows.

The Netherlands has developed a highly successful, nationwide system of sheet glass collection and recycling, paid for by a levy.

Start-up of the LL

In the UK there is market demand for recycling sheet glass and hence, the supply chain is interested in exploring how to increase recycling.

GTS has carried out some in depth studies in this area a few years ago. This provided a starting point for our research and contacts for the living lab.

Zerowaste Scotland a government recycling organization in Scotland has worked extensively with British Glass and GTS in the past and is interested in developing a flat glass collection scheme in their country. They partnered with us to run the first living lab session in order to inform both the FISSAC project and their plans for flat glass recycling providing an additional incentive for attendance by stakeholders at the event.

¹² Report: Economic study on recycling of building glass in Europe, Deloitte, 2016

12.2 The Living Lab today

12.2.1 Purpose and Goal

The aim of the living lab is to identify how to increase collection of sheet glass recycling in the UK. This was developed as the next logical step following various individual discussions with the supply chain. Discussions with the stakeholders in the living lab was designed to identify the barriers perceived by them to flat glass recycling and to look at ways to overcome these barriers. Presentations by representatives of pilot projects and the Dutch flat glass recycling scheme stimulated discussions and provided evidence that it is possible to economically recycling glass from buildings. An aim of the Living Lab was to bring partners together with the possibility of setting up pilot scale projects in Scotland with the assistance of Zero Waste Scotland funding.

12.2.2 Scope

The key barriers to increasing recycling collections are developing an economically viable business case, rolling out infrastructure, and educating the supply chain. In our living labs, we aim to collaboratively discuss these topics and explore solutions.

12.2.3 Identifying stakeholders

Our living lab includes members of the glass supply chain, recyclers, and the construction & demolition supply chain and government representatives. These people have a good spread of knowledge, but we may need to include more specialist people as we move forwards.

12.2.4 Stakeholder interactions and activities

British Glass and GTS spoke to over 30 stakeholders and visited 4 sites as part of our research for FISSAC. We built on our contacts to form a partnership with Zero Waste Scotland and Construction Scotland Innovation Centre. We organized a large, professionally facilitated living lab which brought together 40 key stakeholders to discuss the issue. We also invited the operators of the Dutch sheet glass recycling system to speak at the event.

The workshop co-incident with the launch of a Circular Economy Investment Fund in Scotland which attendees could bid for to fund recycling activities. This was a good focus for action.

Article: <https://www.britglass.org.uk/news-comment/pooling-ideas-close-flat-glass-recycling-loop>

Feedback was collected from the different discussion groups which can be found summarised in the appendix.

12.2.5 Identifying barriers and drivers

The first living lab was a successful event as it was well attended and generated good ideas. As a result, some attendees formed a consortium and developed a high level proposal for the Circular Economy Investment Fund to increase sheet glass recycling.

However, one of the key barriers to progress is that most people are extremely busy in their jobs and struggle to spend the significant amounts of time necessary to develop such new initiatives.

Another barrier is the lack of data. We only have estimates of how much sheet glass waste is generated. A possible future lab will investigate efficient ways to collect construction waste and in particular glass recycling data. This may be investigated and trialled as part of a pilot project.

12.2.6 The Living Lab and the FISSAC model

Future living labs could be used to test whether the supply chain would find value in using the FISSAC model, how they would use it, and what information they would be willing to share. This conversation would need to be one topic in a living lab with a wider agenda in order to interest attendees.

12.3 Conclusions

Overall our living lab was a very successful day that achieved the objectives of getting people to discuss solutions to increase glass recycling, helping them to understand the funding on offer and starting to build consortiums to apply for it.

Things that led to a productive discussion included the use of a facilitator, a very interactive agenda and a wide range of interested attendees. It was also inspirational to have Vlakglass in the room; they are an organisation who already operates a successful flat glass recycling network in the Netherlands and attendees were able to ask them questions.

A lot of preparatory work was carried out before the event including a number of meetings with the various partner organisations and the facilitator to shape the agenda. We also spent a lot of time speaking to existing contacts, finding new people to invite and chasing everyone up. The high number and quality of attendees despite a short advertising period was probably due to this and the fact that the other partners advertised to their large networks. It is also a topic that seems to be of interest to many people.

To improve, we could have better considered how to capture and record the insights that emerged in the table discussions.

12.4 Planned future work

To carry this work forwards, we are organising living labs on specific ideas identified in the first discussion. These may include:

- A session to educate the wider construction industry about glass recycling and seek their ideas through collaboration in a webinar and workshop with the Green Building Council UK
- Organising a meeting for the construction team of a building refurbishment project to educate them about glass recycling and seek their ideas
- Organising a workshop in partnership with a university to explore innovative ideas to increase recycling with engineering and architecture students to learn from and inspire the next generation of construction professionals.

12.5 List of Appendices

Appendix 15 UK LL: Brains storming 1

Appendix 16 UK Living Labs: Brain Storming 2

Appendix 17 Opportunities and challenges

Appendix 18 CEIF Calls Proposal

13. Living Labs analysis

It was early in the process stated that the various Living Labs must be developed based on unique opportunities and needs in the participating regions. The Living Labs must reflect the priorities of the stakeholders in the different countries. The Living Lab is a user-centric platform which involves different stakeholders with the aim to facilitate user influence in an open and collaborative innovation process. This means that different value chains are investigated, involving different stakeholders in the various countries.

There are large regional differences when it comes to industry, stakeholders, policies etc influencing the drivers and barriers for developing industrial Symbiosis and Living Labs. In some of the regions participating in the FISSAC project there are already existing initiatives with the purpose of promoting industrial symbiosis and the development of a circular economy, at least within certain sectors. In some regions there is already a mature way of working with Living Lab concepts whereas there is not yet experience or even acceptance for this kind of cooperation in other regions or sectors.

So, there are differences in awareness of stakeholders and related participant sectors about industrial symbiosis, circular economy and Living Labs. The development of the nine regional Living Labs must be analysed and understood with all this as a background.

The Swedish Living Lab, led by Hifab, was a fore runner in the process of developing Living Labs in the FISSAC context. This was a process parallel to the development of the Living Lab guidelines. The guidelines are presented in [Chapter 3](#). The purpose of the guidelines is to align the Living Labs as far as possible given, the differences mentioned above, so that shared knowledge is leveraged and the FISSAC project objectives are met. The guidelines are also a help for the Living Labs on how to identify key issues to consider in design and execution of a Living Lab, including potential challenges and trade-offs, and also general guidelines for project management of the Living Labs.

The Living Labs are all in different phases. Some are in their start-up phase and others have finished a first round of LL and are starting up a second. They also have different barriers to meet on the way. Barriers can be found that are related to internal management issues like lack of trust and acceptance for the Living Lab concept. It can also be factors related conservative industrial culture or the society where for example policy issues are not promoting industrial symbioses over other business structures.

So, an analysis must not be made with the perspective that the Labs all have the same goal or their progress relative to a common goal. They all have not only different backgrounds and starting point but also different goals. For some Labs the goal has not yet been set, for some the goal is to establish a network and for some there might even be a wish to reach a mature Living Lab aiming at really working together with the aim of “Co-creation” in an established consolidation phase. All the different phases have their own challenges and must be managed in line with this. A comparison must only be made in order to see what can be learnt from each other and how the LLs can inspire each other to take one more step closer to increased industrial symbiosis.

Within the FISSAC Project, LLs aim to exploit knowledge about technological and non-technological factors that could impact Industrial Symbiosis (investigating different value chains, countries and stakeholders, etc.) and to co-develop with LLs participants the FISSAC Model, based on circular economy, with a special focus on developed eco-innovative products. How the Living Labs met this expectation varies. It has been handled in different ways in different Labs. For some of the Labs there has been a clear interest in the FISSAC software platform whereas other Labs have concluded that this is not at all interesting for the time being. However, the aim and the ambition, for all Labs is that the FISSAC model in part or in all its content will be included in discussions. The interest for this will most likely increase as the Living Labs get more established and more result come out from FISSAC project in general. And maybe especially when the content and business model related to the software platform is ready to be demonstrated.

Conclusions from LLs will be integrated in the definition of the final version of FISSAC model that aims to develop an integrated Industrial Symbiosis Management Software tool supported by an improved methodology in the construction sector scenario.

14. Discussion

After an initial delay, all the living labs are now up and running. Given that the work in WP 7.1 is still in an early phase and there are large differences in starting points and given regional conditions for the FISSAC Living Labs it is too early to draw conclusion on what is right or wrong. There is not one common goal for all the Labs. Instead they are all on their unique journey to promote industrial symbiosis and increase the circularity in their respective region and business sector.

The Labs have, to this point, chosen to work with the FISSAC model in different ways. It can be concluded that it is valuable for the FISSAC project to have the Living Labs as channels to reach out to the various stakeholders in the different regions participating in the project. Knowledge transfer is facilitated regardless if it is concrete discussions on software platform or maybe on more theoretical issues like Living Lab management or circular economy challenges. Knowledge transfer the opposite way could of course be equally important. Challenges and experiences from the stakeholders could more easily be shared with the FISSAC project.

From the analysis above it can be stated that it must not be an over-all goal to align the Living Labs in the sense that they should all work in the same way. A comparison should be made only to share experiences and knowledge on how to overcome barriers and to find inspiration through experiences made by the other Labs. All Labs must strive to find the best way to increase cooperation and industrial symbiosis. This will create long term competitiveness and profitability for their stake-holders and a more sustainable construction sector. The European industry is facing a huge challenge in becoming part of a circular economy. Cooperation in the format of Living Labs can be one important tool in this.

15. Recommendations for Further Living Labs

What makes a Living Lab successful? In the long term an answer to that is: A Living Lab that help the participants to stay competitive will be successful. For industry stakeholders the Living Labs will be successful if it helps companies to improve their business. So, for the Living Labs the stake-holder analysis is very important. Not only do we need to know who is the stakeholder, we also need to understand their challenges and their business.

When value-chains are discussed it is also of great importance that no “links” are missing. If industrial symbiosis in a value chain is to be developed it is of great importance that no “links” are missing. Sometimes the focus is on those already participating and the question on “who isn’t here” is forgotten.

The stake-holder analysis must not only be made in the start-up phase, it must be updated as the Lab develops.

In the context of the FISSAC project the scope of the Living Labs are twofold. They should not only be successful to the stakeholders in the LL. It should also contribute to the success of the FISSAC project and the development of the FISSAC model. Hence a successful LL brings valuable input to the project and to the co-creation of the FISSAC model.

To bench-mark with other Living Labs and find inspiration in others work is usually of great help. Here the FISSAC project can be valuable in helping the various regional Living Labs developing. WP7.1 has started up with quarterly telco meetings both with the entire group of Living Labs and bilateral meetings with the WP coordinator. These meetings will continue and will give opportunities to discuss various issues of common interest.

Appendices

Appendix 1 Belgium LL: Minutes of Living Labs Industrial Symbiosis Management Software tool

Living Lab: Stakeholder analysis for the “Industrial Symbiosis Management Software Tool”

About the Living Lab:

OVAM organised 2 workshops to gather information from various stakeholders on the necessity for and the functions of a Software Tool to be developed within the scope of industrial symbiosis. Whereas the first session gathered stakeholder from different sectors, the second session involved more stakeholder from the construction and demolition sector, both including waste traders and institutions offering innovative technology for symbiosis. The sessions took place at OVAM in Mechelen, on 22 and 29 June 2017.

The aim of the sessions was to get insight from stakeholders on their expectations and relevant features of an ICT platform for industrial symbiosis. The sessions built on the experience with the existing symbiosis platform that was initiated by the Flemish Public Waste Agency (OVAM) in 2012.

Both sessions gathered stakeholders from different sectors. The participants consider this as an added value, as well for the workshops as for the ICT-platform. It offers more opportunities for new and innovative solutions.

Participants

	SECTOR	COMPANY
Living Lab 22/06/2017	Production: supply and demand	Colruyt Group Monument Chemical Orbix
	Technology/solution providers	Ecosynth
	Public Waste Agency	OVAM
	Research institute	IMEC
Living Lab 29/06/2017	Production: supply and demand	Solvakem Renewi Go4Circle Vanheede Avemco DEME-Group Indaver
	Technology/solution providers	VITO
	Public Waste Agency	OVAM
	Research institute	IMEC

Target groups/users expectations of ICT Platform

The current symbiosis network in Flanders was the starting point for the discussion on an ICT platform for industrial symbiosis. It compared the advantages and disadvantages of the current situation with the possibilities of a future ICT platform.

In 2012, the Flemish Public Waste Agency (OVAM) initiated the platform to encourage symbiosis, especially in those sectors not yet covered by the European or regional legislation. It is a matchmaking tool, built on an extensive database, workshops with enterprises and visits to individual companies. It aims to bring companies that produce residual (waste) streams in contact with other companies that can use these materials as resources or input in their production process. It is not limited to a specific sector.

Most participants to the workshops participated at one time in the process of the Flemish Symbiosis platform. As such they all have experience with industrial symbiosis or are at least they are favourable to the idea.

TARGET GROUPS/USERS	EXPECTATIONS FROM AN ICT PLATFORM	RELEVANT FEATURES OF AN ICT PLATFORM
a. Producer/Industrial firms	Supply <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduce waste and costs waste management - Extent knowledge of market across sectors - Stimulate and finance technological research - Support to establish cooperation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Find online match based on EURAL codes - Provide information: - Anonymous mailing/chat systems indicating interesting material flows - Gradual release of data (safeguard confidentiality)
	Demand <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduce waste and costs waste management - Extended knowledge of supply with specifications of materials (possibility to upload reports), quantities, quality, frequency of supply. - Stimulate and finance technological research - Get to know supply - Support to establish cooperation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Find online match - Gradual release of data - Subscribe for information on specific materials flows
b. Construction and demolition sector		
c. Technology/Solution Providers (e.g. intermediate recycling firms)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify new secondary raw materials - Find market for material - Identify new costumers 	
d. Waste traders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Additional markets for products - Solution for materials without destination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Find online match based on EURAL codes - Provide information - Anonymous mailing systems indicating interesting material flows - Gradual release of data (confidentiality) - Subscribe for information on specific material flows

Challenges

While discussing expectations and functionality some additional challenges were identified.

- Industrial symbiosis aims at giving a higher value to waste from one company by using it as raw material for another, and thus contributing to a circular economy. The ICT-platform should be seen and used as a tool to enhance the valorisation of waste and not as a mere instrument to search for alternative/cheaper waste treatment solutions, without added value from an environmental or social perspective. How will the ICT-platform safeguard the higher valorisation of waste? Which indicators will be considered in the deliberation? When looking at it in an European context: how will transport/distance be taken into account?
As to avoid misuse of the platform it is considered essential to have a clear set of rules concerning the use of the platform and a clear engagement of the participating companies.
- In the long run it will be essential to guarantee the financial liveability of the ICT-platform. Since the success of the platform very much depends on the number of participating companies and the amount of available data, it is essential for companies to have free access to (at least parts of) the platform, to discover its potential and its added value. This should be possible even without registration. In a later phase, a system of (paying) membership to the platform could be envisaged.
- The ICT-platform is a matchmaking tool, facilitating companies to connect. The subsequent process leading to the realisation of the symbiosis, is a process between individual companies. In order to evaluate the success of the ICT-platform as a tool for industrial symbiosis, feedback is needed on the actual outcome of the initial contacts. This should be envisaged in the initial design of the ICT-platform.
- The ICT-platform should be more than just a platform connecting companies. It should be connected to a network offering advice or research on innovative opportunities, looking at ways to overcome practical barriers related to symbiosis, stimulating and supporting less obvious symbiosis initiatives. This 'help-function' could encourage potential participants to join the platform, even when a fee is envisaged.
- GIS-location
- The debate on industrial symbiosis and circular economy is still a very academic debate. In order to stimulate industrial symbiosis it is essential for the platform to be easy accessible and user-friendly.

Follow-up

Additional information about specific challenges and needs of the construction and demolition sector will be gathered during follow-up consultations.

Appendix 2 Belgium LL: Minutes of Living Labs Urban Mining

Living Lab: Urban Mining

About the Living Lab:

OVAM invited stakeholders from the construction and demolition sector, researchers and experts from the government to debate the concept of the urban environment as an urban mine.

Urban developments such as demographic growth but also climate change and circular economy challenge cities to re-think their urban planning and question how to adapt existing buildings and large infrastructures works to new and future realities. Renovation and large construction works will increase the demand for raw materials as building materials and at the same time make a large amount of 'waste' materials available. In a circular approach, we must endeavor to connect the demand and supply within the urban environment and as such close the cycle of materials. We aim for recycling and the optimal reuse of parts of a building, building elements, components and building materials. Our starting point for the debate is the 'as is' situation: the amount of materials already present in cities and its potential for reuse.

Two sessions took place at OVAM in Mechelen, on 25 August and 18 December 2017. The aim of both sessions was to get insight from different stakeholders:

- on the questions and challenges they encounter to (re)valorise resources/waste from construction and demolition,
- to identify research questions, to take up in follow-up labs and eventually in trial projects,
- to explore the willingness to engage and contribute to the follow-up process.

Participants

In total, some 50 participants attended the Living Labs. The intended diversity of the participant, closely monitored throughout the plenary session and the debates in smaller working groups, was considered a real added value. It offered the opportunity to consider different aspect and viewpoints and lead the way for an cross-sectorial and interdisciplinary debate.

SECTOR	COMPANY	
	Living Lab 25/08/2017	Living Lab 18/12/2017
Construction and demolition federations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vlaamse Confederatie Bouw (VBC), <i>Flemish Construction Federation</i> • Tracimat • Centrale Isolatie Raad (CIR), <i>Central Insulation Council</i> • Belgische Baksteen Federatie (BBF); <i>Belgian Brick Federation</i> • Confederatie aannemers sloop- en ontmantelingswerken (CASO), <i>Confederation of (controled) demolition contractors</i> • Belgische vereniging van producenten van geëxpandeerd polystyreen (Styfabel); <i>Belgian association of producers of expanded polystyrene</i> • Federatie van producenten van recycling granulaten (FPRG); <i>Federation of producers of recycling granulates</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federatie van producenten van recycling granulaten (FPRG); <i>Federation of producers of recycling granulates</i> • Centrale Isolatie Raad (CIR), <i>Central Insulation Council</i>

SECTOR	COMPANY	
	Living Lab 25/08/2017	Living Lab 18/12/2017
Material producer / contractors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foamglas : glass • Frisomat: steel • Unilin • Retail Insulation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FoamGlas: glass • BSV NV: soil <i>sanitation and waste treatment</i> • Speed Building System Belgium • Wienerberger: • Derbigum: • ISOVER: isolation materials • Xella: building blocks
Government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OVAM, <i>Public Waste Agency of Flanders</i> • Vlaanderen Circulair • Economie, Wetenschap en Innovatie (EWI), <i>Economy, Sciences and Innovation</i> • Agentschap Facilitair Bedrijf 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OVAM, <i>Public Waste Agency of Flanders</i> • Vlaanderen Circulair
Research institute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VUB-architecten: architects Free University Brussels • Centre d'Etudes, de Recherche et d'Action en Architecture (CERAA) • COPRO: controls of quality on construction products • WTCB/BRRI: Belgian Building Research Institute • Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch onderzoek (VITO): Flemish Institute for Technological Research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VUB • VKC-Centexbel • Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch onderzoek (VITO): Flemish Institute for Technological Research
Consultancy and others	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vlaams Instituut voor bio-ecologisch materiaal (VIBE): • Rotor: material flows in industry and construction. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycling Assistance • Rotor: material flows in industry and construction • Colruyt Group • A2O Architects • Recydata

Methodology and results

The aim of the first session was to get a grip on the challenges and questions from stakeholders working in an urban environment, and trying to improve the optimal (re)-use of materials.

Urban Mining, this is the rational exploitation of available elements, materials and raw materials in the existing patrimony, and the choice for dynamic building and living in the city are two essential factors to realise circular living and to close the materials cycle. In order to improve the recovery of elements and materials with a smaller impact on the environment and society, we must today make choices in the design of the buildings, the infrastructure and possibly the entire urban fabric.

This adaptable, dynamic way of building and living in the city needs input from the experience today with dismantling and demolishing buildings so that we can recover the elements and materials.

The first session focussed on the following issues:

- Selective demolition: its limits, necessary working conditions, difficult sites, tracing of secondary raw materials, implementation...

- Value chain of materials: challenges, cooperation and concertation, planning for reuse...
- Business model: cost – benefits along the value chain, opportunities, confidence of market...
- Vision of the future: design, urban planning

Based on the result from the first session the living lab of December focused on 5 challenges, presented in the form of a ‘challenge tree’. The following issues were addressed:

Challenges	
Demolition and treatment of materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Available space - Materials and techniques - Reuse - Scale site
Policy and regulations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Best practices (good examples) - Stimulate - Different (decision) levels - Quality guarantees
Business model / market	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial business model - Market - Value chain
Eco-innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trends - Dynamic building
Cooperation along the value chain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Re-use (market) - Cooperation and concertation

The participants had the opportunity to comment the different challenges during consecutive sessions.

The objective was to identify questions for further follow-up, to be addressed by scientific research, on small scale building and demolition sites or during future living labs.

Specific challenges

We focus on some of the challenges that are also relevant for industrial symbiosis.

- **Demolition and treatment of materials:** Small sites are confronted with specific challenges when engaging in selective demolition: from separate sorting on site (what are the best practises) to temporary storage of materials and transportation. Practical solutions need to be envisaged, taking into account local regulations. Certification and validation of secondary raw materials still remains a challenging issue. The use of particular building materials and techniques may have an adverse effect on the scope for selective demolition and recovery of materials. For the non-stony fraction the optimal organisation of transport to treatment plants remains a big challenge and restricts the opportunity to use them as secondary raw materials.
- **Business model:** Is there a market for secondary raw materials from construction and demolition sites: why or why not? How can we guarantee quality standards concerning security, safety... ? Where in the value chain are the cost and the benefits: can we develop a viable business model for all stakeholders involved? How can we stimulate a market for secondary raw materials: do we need to review the existing regulations, the financing policies?
- **Cooperation along the value chain:** While the concept of industrial symbiosis seems attractive at first sight, many practical problems remain to convert it to a business context. A platform is a useful tool to connect supply and demand, but will this be sufficient to realise symbiosis? Do we need brokers to accompany the process? How do we stimulate trust for recycled materials? How do we guarantee the quality of recycled content? How do we stimulate reuse for more generic materials? A model based on circular economy will need knowledge sharing and transparency between different stakeholder of the value chain: how can we improve this cooperation?

- **Social aspects:** urban mining, demolition with due consideration for re-use and recycling will create new and other job. Do we have a clear view on the necessary skill? Are those skills available and are there sufficient training opportunities to meet these newly created opportunities? How does this affect the already existing jobs? Demolition with due regard for re-use and recycling requires intensive manual labour and time. How does this affects the business model?

Follow-up

Based on the outcome of the living labs, a selection will be made of questions needing additional research, questions to be studied on site and some for which to organize an additional living lab. The selection and follow-up will take place in 2018 and 2019.

Appendix 3 Belgium LL: Challenge trees Urban Mining

Demolition and treatment of waste/materials

Business model

Policy and regulations

Cooperation along the value chain

Eco-design and material-design

Appendix 4 Hungary LL: Project descriptions

Sharing Materials to Minimize Waste: Industrial Symbiosis Project

The PANNON NOVUM WEST-TRANSDANUBIAN REGIONAL INNOVATION NON-PROFIT LTD is a Hungarian partner to the Interreg Europe project SYMBI (04/2016 to 03/2021) whose general objective is to empower regions to build sustainable economies, resilient to environmental pressures and climate change. The project supports the implementation of policy instruments and measures for the diffusion of industrial symbiosis, to add value, reduce production costs and relieve environmental pressures through increased resource efficiency and greenhouse gas emissions.

SYMBI aims at supporting the transition towards a resource-efficient economy through industrial symbiosis, establishing territorial synergies to manage waste and exchange energy & by-products as secondary raw resources

Furthermore, through the development of the activities, SYMBI will get:

- Encourage regional waste transformation systems;
- Promote the use of secondary raw materials and the emergence of regional secondary raw materials market;
- Prioritize green public procurement;
- Unlock investments by regional and local financial actors;
- Explore, assess, expand, and enhance current practices in ecosystems of industrial innovation;
- Raise public awareness on industrial symbiosis and circular economy.

Assessment of this project from FISSAC point: this project is very relevant therefore they were contacted to participate in the HU LL.

When it comes to recycling aluminium: Every Can Counts

Every Can Counts demonstrates the metal packaging industry's commitment to invest in programmes to drive lasting, positive behaviour change and maximise recycling performance. The UK based initiative aims to enable and encourage more people to recycle the drinks cans they use outside the home; specifically in workplaces and at locations and on occasions when people are 'on the go'. The programme offers advice and practical support to organisations wishing to improve their recycling. Developed and funded by the beverage can manufacturing and recycling industry, there are now 12 Every Can Counts programmes operating in 14 European countries. In Hungary Every Can Counts = "Minden Doboz Visszajar" (www.mindendoboz.hu) was launched in 2012 as the beverage can industry's effort to promote the voluntary joint can collection system. Operated by Returpack Ltd. beverage cans are now collected through Every Can Counts-branded "Voluntary-Take-Back-Machines" located mainly at retail outlets. Each can collected returns a voucher equivalent to 1 Euro-cent. Under the Every Can Counts brand consumers and collectors find all relevant information about can collection and recycling as well as locations of the 320 "Voluntary-Take-Back-Machines" spread across Hungary. In addition, activities focus largely on raising the awareness at festivals. Whilst the majority of beer sold at festivals is draft, visitors bring cans with them to the campsites, so running promotions there encourages good "on the go" recycling behaviour. Since 2016 Returpack pays major attention to targeting young adults to deepen the knowledge of recycling and raising "green awareness".

Assessment of this project from FISSAC point: the topic of this project is not relevant for FISSAC, however the network of the can collection system could be utilized to communicate FISSAC to the greater public for sensitizing, getting feedback and improving social acceptance.

Appendix 5 Hungary LL: Conference summary

Conference summary: The role of construction and demolition materials in the circular economy

A conference titled „[The role of construction and demolition materials in the circular economy](#)“ was organized for Hungarian stakeholders in Budapest by the [Association of Environmental Enterprises](#) and the Herman Otto Institute in October 2016. The presentations touched upon various legislative and practical technical challenges that are currently formulating areas - including certification of by-products, green public procurement, performance validation, national aggregate policies – all of which have effect on the whole system of waste management in the country. (Agenda and presentations in Hungarian are [available here](#).)

In his opening Zsolt V. Nemeth (minister of state for environment, agricultural development and [hungaricums](#)) pronounced that according to the EU legal obligation by the end of 2020 70% of the annually generated non-hazardous construction and demolition waste has to be recycled in Hungary (as set out under point 2 of paragraph 92 of the [CLXXXV/2012 Law on wastes](#)). The recycling performance in Hungary in this respect was over 60% in 2014. He pointed out that by considering social and environmental aspects adequately waste management in these sectors offers many opportunities for the economy in Hungary. Apart from meeting and obligation, it also brings advantages that can help to improve the competitiveness of our country. The main objective of the draft decree on construction and demolition wastes is to establish a self-sustaining system for material use that considers the construction industry, the needs of the demolition industry and of the public, in accordance with the environmental considerations.

Photo credits:
Figure 24: Hungary Living Lab. Minister of state speaks at the event

Jozsef Csaba Petrus, senior advisor at the Environmental Development Division, Ministry of Agriculture summarized the current prevailing domestic legal problems related to construction/demolition wastes and introduced the solutions suggested by the decree under construction.

Basic legislation and practical challenges include

- monitoring the handling of construction/demolition wastes is difficult,
- distribution of responsibilities and liabilities is unclear
- deficiencies in the field of data register and data reporting
- there is no distinct legislation for CDWs generated during major investments and for those coming from small scale constructions of citizens
- no rules for selecting waste during demolition
- no rules for handling CDW whose generation rate exceeds 10 tonnes per day
- in the current system landfill is dominating.

Challenges in the field of reusing materials from demolition and preparation of secondary raw materials for reuse:

- production of construction materials from secondary raw materials is currently costly
- no public procurement obligation exist currently to use recycled construction materials for construction works
- detailed rules for construction products from CDW raw materials are lacking
- system for certifying end-of-waste status is lacking.

Another challenge is that differing legislation regulates the very same raw material (e.g. stone, aggregates) dependent on whether it is from a quarry (mining waste) or from construction-demolition (CDW). There is continuous competition with low-priced primary mining products produced from primary raw materials. There is a need for developing a national aggregate policy. A main objective of the regulation that is under development is to improve the competitiveness of secondary raw materials and to improve the realization of the waste hierarchy and avoid waste generation. The regulation will determine legal instruments to prevent waste generation including e.g. non-waste status of construction/demolition scrap, selective demolition and selective collection, certification of pollution-free quality, criteria for end-of-waste, provisions of public authority powers, liabilities for keeping records and provision of data.

Further presentations touched upon for instance the following topics: showcase of international examples of secondary raw material use in constructions (presenter: [HuGBC](#)), the role of environment protection authorities in waste management licensing, end-of-waste EU criteria and requirements for building materials in other Member States (presenter: [KSZGYSZ](#)), performance certification of secondary raw materials for construction (presenter: [ÉMI](#)), secondary raw material use in road construction (presenter: [TLI](#)), international experiences with sustainable management in secondary aggregates use and aggregate policy (presenter: [MFGI](#))

Assessment of this conference from FISSAC point: some presentations of the conference are highly relevant to FISSAC. As a result, ÉMI was identified as potential key stakeholder to host the HU-LL, the Environment Development Division of the Ministry of Agriculture was first contacted in November 2017 and was informed about FISSAC and its LL objectives in HU that was well received.

Appendix 6 Hungary LL: Questionnaire

Please help with our opinion, professional work, definition of topics in our future forums by completing the following questionnaire!	total	%
How evident do you think is the realization of a circular economy in Hungary?		
(You can mark more than one answer!)	8	100
<input type="checkbox"/> I do not know what a circular economy is.	0	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> It is harmful if business and economy is limited with environment management.	0	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> I've heard about it, but I do not know about the details.	1	13%
<input type="checkbox"/> Unfortunately, I see that it is not yet evident, though some elements seem to have appeared.	5	63%
<input type="checkbox"/> We are very far from it, but I know that this approach is already known and better accepted abroad.	1	13%
<input type="checkbox"/> It's completely evident.	1	13%
<input type="checkbox"/> It is not evident at all.	0	0%
Where do you see the two most important shortcomings in moving towards circular economy in the domestic construction sector? (Please choose up to two answers!)	13	100
<input type="checkbox"/> Inadequate legal background.	4	31%
<input type="checkbox"/> Lack of financial resources.	1	8%
<input type="checkbox"/> Lack of information on the theory and specific technologies.	1	8%
<input type="checkbox"/> Lack of state assistance and appropriate motivational support.	5	38%
<input type="checkbox"/> All conditions are given.	1	8%
<input type="checkbox"/> There is no condition for it.	1	8%
<input type="checkbox"/> Other conditions are missing, namely:	0	0%
How important do you think waste management according to the waste hierarchy is for developing the competitiveness of the domestic construction industry? (You can mark more than one answer!)	8	100
<input type="checkbox"/> I do not know what waste hierarchy is.	1	13%
<input type="checkbox"/> I do not work for abroad, in which case that could be advantageous.	1	13%
<input type="checkbox"/> The gradual introduction of waste hierarchy management into sectoral programs could show towards improvement in competitiveness.	6	75%
<input type="checkbox"/> There are more important conditions that are missing.	0	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> The point is, that we can deposit waste cheaply.	0	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> This is not important at all.	0	0%
Why do you think industrial symbiosis relationships do not spread here?	9	100
<input type="checkbox"/> I do not know exactly what relationships this is about, certainly this is the elite club of wealthy companies run with lots of money.	0	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> There is no basic information available about the benefits, terms of access, organization, etc.	5	56%
<input type="checkbox"/> It is not well-organized, directed, has no stable, functioning nationwide network.	3	33%
<input type="checkbox"/> To sell or buy waste, does that make sense at all?	1	11%

Would it be realistic for your company to produce a product with using up waste?		
(Please select a single answer!)	7	100
<input type="checkbox"/> No, it impossible, no wealth can be built from waste.	0	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> No, it is impossible to produce the right quality.	0	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, because waste is nothing more than a substance to be used.	5	71%
<input type="checkbox"/> Not yet, but I plan to do so, I still have the conditions missing.	2	29%
<input type="checkbox"/> No, because until primary raw materials are available cheaply, it does are not worth it to deal with secondary raw materials.	0	0%
Would you participate with your company in a project mediating industrial symbiotic relationships?		
(Select a single answer!)	7	100
<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, but I do not know how and where to start.	5	71%
<input type="checkbox"/> No, because it is about giving out company information and data.	0	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> No, because there is competition on the market and not cooperation.	1	14%
<input type="checkbox"/> I do not know because I do not see how I would benefit from it.	1	14%
<input type="checkbox"/> To sell or buy waste, does that make sense?	0	0%
Do you think it would be important to introduce a selective demolition? (Select a single answer!)	7	100
<input type="checkbox"/> No, it's unnecessary to do it, things shall continue they did so far.	0	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> No, I have no idea what the selective demolition is.	0	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> No, it is enough to keep with the law, isn't it?	0	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> I do not know, but I am interested to know further details.	2	29%
<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, because it would facilitate the recycling of waste.	5	71%
Would you use glass foam products for your business? (Select a single answer!)	7	100
<input type="checkbox"/> No, because I do not know exactly what it could be used for.	2	29%
<input type="checkbox"/> No, because I do not know what are its advantages compared to traditional products.	1	14%
<input type="checkbox"/> No, because it is made of waste and one can not produce quality from waste.	0	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> I do not know really, I've heard about it, but it's certainly expensive and difficult, complicated to use.	1	14%
<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, because I already know that it is a high quality modern building material.	3	43%
Would you use polystyrene concrete? (Select a single answer!)	7	100
<input type="checkbox"/> No, because I do not know exactly what it could be used for.	1	14%
<input type="checkbox"/> No, because I do not know what are its advantages compared to traditional products.	0	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> No, because it is made of waste and one can not produce quality from waste.	0	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> I do not know really, I've heard about it, but it's certainly expensive and difficult, complicated to use.	1	14%
<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, because I already know that it is a high quality modern building material.	5	71%

Appendix 7 Hungary LL: Publications, photos related to the HU LL event

HU LL invitation flyer (complimentary EN version design)

FISSAC

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 642154.

fissacproject.eu

THE OBJECTIVE OF FISSAC

project is to develop and demonstrate a new methodology and a software platform to facilitate information exchange that can support the implementation of innovative industrial symbiosis networks towards a zero waste approach in the resource intensive industries of the extended construction value chain, leading to material closed-loop processes and moving to a circular economy.

SCIENTIFIC & TECHNICAL GOALS

- What is the role of circular economy and industrial symbiosis in the construction value chain?
- What are the requirements and tools necessary for moving towards industrial symbiosis?
- What are the factors hindering eco-innovation in the construction sector?
- How social acceptance can be handled?
- How others see the role of your company in the construction and demolition industry?

PARTICIPATE IN THE SERIES OF DISCUSSION FORA IN HUNGARY

FISSAC INTERACTIVE FORA IN HUNGARY

With organising meetings and presenting best practices our aim is to generate discussions among actors and stakeholders of the construction and demolition sector, legislators and academics in order to advance the understanding of complex challenges relevant to these sectors, and facilitate the co-creation of solutions to these challenges by thinking together.

fissacproject.eu/en/category/ll-hungary-en

ADVANTAGES OF PARTICIPATING

- Non-commercial environment facilitates participants to share freely
- Getting outside views on your organization can challenge how you and others see your role in the value chain
- New business opportunities
- Opportunity for joining new trends in international construction industry

CONTACTS: FORUM@FISSAC.GEONARDO.COM

Invitation to the 1st HU LL event and to the series of fora (complimentary EN version design)

INVITATION

RESOURCE EFFICIENCY IN THE DOMESTIC CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY

– Best practices in the circular economy and eco-innovation –

DATE 13 April 2018 (Friday) 9:30 –13:45	VENUE: HUNGEXPO Pavilion 'A', Gallery 2 <small>(1101 Budapest, Albertfalvi út 10., Hungary)</small>	ORGANISERS: Geonardo Ltd. <small>(FISSAC H2020 project)</small> Herman Otto Institute Nonprofit Ltd. <small>(TRIS Interreg Europe project)</small>
---	---	---

TOPIC OF THE CONFERENCE

Growing prosperity leads to the extraction and use of more resources and to the production of more waste. The EU is committed to implement the principles of the waste hierarchy, which implies the prevention of waste, its reuse and recycling where it is not prevented, and its energy recovery as sub-optimal option. This calls for eco-innovative solutions and resource-efficient products, processes and services, and their uptake which will be facilitated by new sustainable lifestyles and consumption behaviour. At the 1st event of this series we investigate through several topical examples how resource efficiency can be fostered in the extended construction sector in Hungary.

Participate in the series of discussion fora in Hungary. With organising meetings and presenting best practices our aim is to generate discussions among actors and stakeholders of the construction and demolition sector, legislators and academics in order to advance the understanding of complex challenges relevant to these sectors, and facilitate the co-creation of solutions to these challenges by thinking together.

At the very first event of a series of discussion fora we investigate, through several topical examples, how resource efficiency can be fostered in the extended domestic construction sector.

The language of the event is Hungarian.

Professional supporter:

Organizers:

WITH CONSTRUUMA PASS THE PARTICIPATION AT THE CONFERENCE IS FREE OF CHARGE, HOWEVER REGISTRATION IS REQUIRED.

PLEASE FILL IN THE REGISTRATION FORM AT <https://goo.gl/forms/RXdjLOq4QsiQbdN12>

REGISTRATION DEADLINE:
10 April 2018, Tuesday

FURTHER INFORMATION:
forum@fissac.geonardo.com
+36-20-4717-150

The event is realized with financial support from the European Commission (FISSAC H2020 GA No 642154, TRIS Interreg Europe). The views presented at this event are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union.

Programme of the 1st HU LL event (complimentary EN version design)

CONFERENCE PROGRAMME

9.30-10.00	REGISTRATION, COFFEE
10.00-10.10	OPENING Dr. András Rácz – Deputy Minister of State for Environmental Affairs, Ministry of Agriculture WELCOME Dr. András Báres – Deputy Executive Director, Herman Ottó Institute Nonprofit Ltd. Dr. Katalin Balázs – FISSAC project manager, Geonardo Ltd.
10.10-10.25	Construction and demolition waste in the circular economy – waste generation and management based on statistics, elements of the legislation underway László Skulmtil – Head of Department, Waste Management Department, Ministry of Agriculture
10.25-10.40	Construction and Demolition Waste Protocol in line with the EU requirements István Asztalos, member of the board, office manager, CeHBeton: Hungarian Cement Concrete and Lime Association
10.40-10.55	Quality assessment experiences of products from recycled construction-demolition waste Gyula Pekár, EMI Non-Profit Limited Liability Company for Quality Control and Innovation in Building (TBC)
10.55-11.15	The role of best practices in moving towards circular economy – introduction of the FISSAC, TRIS, SYMBI projects FISSAC: Geonardo Ltd., TRIS: IPKA Public Benefit Non-Profit Ltd. for the Development of Industry., SYMBI: Pannon Novum Nonprofit Ltd. (TBC)
11.15-11.25	QUESTIONS AND ANSWERS
11.25-11.40	COFFEE BREAK
11.40-11.55	Handling concrete waste – Professional reuse according to the MSZ 4798:2016 concrete standard Dr. Olivér Czoboly, head of laboratory, Beton Technology Centre Ltd.
11.55-12.10	Demolition and reuse of concrete structures – The example of the high building in Pécs Róbert Jakob, project leader, STRABAG_MML Ltd. and Land-Bau Ltd. consortium
12.10-12.25	The use of Energocell glass foam granules in construction industry – future developments Zoltán Vékony, sales manager, Daniella Industrial Park Ltd.
12.25-12.40	Polystyrol concrete in the world of construction materials – a family of modern construction materials using plastic waste from Hungary István Pethő, marketing director, WYW Block Zrt.
12.40-12.50	QUESTIONS AND ANSWERS
12.50-13.00	SUMMARY, FOLLOW-UP, CLOSURE

Professional supporter:

Organizers:

 The event is funded with financial support from the European Commission (FISSAC H2020 GA Nr. 842154, TRIS Interreg Europe). The views presented at this event are solely those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union.

Online registration page for the conference (in HU)

Erőforrás hatékonyság a hazai építőiparban: Jó gyakorlatok a körforgásos gazdaság és az ökoinnováció terén

Időpont: 2018. április 12. (péntek) 9:00-13:00
 Helyszín: CONSTRUMA 2018 - Hungexpo „A” pavilon II. galériás
 Szervező: Geonardo Kft. (FISSAC H2020 projekt), Herman Ottó Intézet Nonprofit Kft. (TRIS Interreg Europe projekt)
 A programot lezárhatja innen: <http://fiissacproject.eu/hu/2018/03/21/ingyenvizsgafomaz-bekelerol-as-epitesiparban-rol-18/>
 További információk: forum.fissac@geonardo.com +36-20-4717-180

Tisztelt Jelentkező! Kérjük, adja meg az érdeklődését, konferenciánki-bekérését. Várjuk fórumaorosztonunk következő, újsai rendezvényénél! Kérjük kövessze a FISSAC projektet hazai fórumoldalon foglalkozó lapján, amelyen friss információkat talál: <http://fiissacproject.eu/hu/telegy/2018/hu/>

***Kötelező:**

E-mail-cím *
 Az Ön email címe:

Név *
 Bejuttatás:

Szervezet *
 Bejuttatás:

Email *
 Bejuttatás:

Telefon
 Bejuttatás:

Széki társaságok:
ÉMI Építési Minisztérium
ColBeton az építés a legye

A rendezvény az Európai Bizottság pénzügyi támogatásával valósul meg (FISSAC H2020 GA 101042254, TRIS Interreg Europe), tartalma azonban nem feltétlenül tükrözi az Európai Bizottság véleményét, beleértve a programot nem terjed ki.

A vállalkozó másolatot küldünk a megadott címre.

Project leaflet in HU with customized last page for the HU LL purposes (in HU)

A FISSAC PROJEKT MAGYARORSZÁGON

Szakmai találkozók szervezésével és gyakorlatok bemutatásával indítunk párbeszédet az építő- és bontóipari szereplők, jogalkotók és a tudományos élet szereplői között annak érdekében, hogy az ágazatokat érintő összetett kihívások jobb megértését, és az azokra adott válaszok könnyebb meghozatalát közös gondolkodással segítsük elő.

- Mi a körforgásos gazdaság és az ipari szimbiózis szerepe az építőipari értékláncban?
- Melyek az ipari szimbiózis létrejöttéhez szükséges feltételek, eszközök?
- Melyek az öko-innovációt hátráltató tényezők az építőiparban?
- Hogyan kezelhető a társadalmi elfogadottság?
- Hogyan látják mások az ön vállalatának szerepét az építő- és bontóiparban?

www.fissacproject.eu

Az ipari szimbiózis előmozdítása a nyersanyag-intenzív iparágak fenntarthatóbb működése érdekében egy kiterjesztett építőipari értékláncban

VEGYENEK RÉSZT ÖNÖK IS A FISSAC HAZAI INTERAKTÍV FÓRUMÁN!

FISSAC HAZAI INTERAKTÍV FÓRUM

A RÉSZVÉTEL ELŐNYEI

- nem üzleti jellegű környezet: könnyebb a tudásmegosztás
- új nézőpontokat kaphat cége környezetvédelmi megítéléséhez
- új üzleti lehetőségek: kapcsolatteremtési lehetőség
- bekapcsolódási lehetőség nemzetközi építőipari trendekbe

ELÉRHETŐSÉG MAGYARORSZÁGON
 forum.fissac@geonardo.com
 fissacproject.eu/hu/category/ll-hungary-hu

A projekt támogatást kapott az Európai Unió Horizont 2020 kutatás és innovációs programja keretében, támogatási megállapodás száma: 642154.

©kép-fotó: Candy (Peter Czeven)

Technical questionnaire in Hungarian provided for HU LL participants in Google form (in HU)

"Erőforrás hatékonyság a hazai építőiparban" Konferencia - SZAKMAI KÉRDŐÍV

Időpont: 2018. április 13. (péntek) 9:30-13:45
Helyszín: CONSTRUMA 2018 – Hungexpo, „A” pavilon II. galéria
Szervezők: Geonardo Kft. (FISSAC H2020 projekt), Herman Ottó Intézet Nonprofit Kft. (TRIS Interreg Europe projekt)

Kérjük segítse véleményével szakmai munkánkat, a jövőben megrendezésre kerülő fórumaink tématerületeinek meghatározását az alábbi kérdőív kitöltésével!

***Kötelező**

A hazai gazdasági életben mennyire evidencia a körforgásos gazdaság megvalósítása?
(Több választ is megjelölhet!)

- Fogalmam sincs mi az a körforgásos gazdaság.
- Káros, ha a gazdaságot korlátozzák a környezetvédelemmel.
- Hallottam már róla, de a részleteket nem ismerem.
- Sainos azt látom, hogy még nem az, bár bizonyos elemei mintha már

FISSAC HU LL X banner (in HU)

fissacproject.eu/hu

A FISSAC PROJEKT CÉLJA

az építő- és bontóipari hulladékok másodnyersanyagként történő újrahasznosításának, valamint a zero-hulladék felé mutató körforgásos gazdaság létrejöttének előmozdítása érdekében az ágazatok közötti információcserét támogató módszertan és szoftver platform kialakítása.

TUDOMÁNYOS ÉS SZAKMAI CÉLOK

VEGYENEK RÉSZT ÖNÖK IS A FISSAC HAZAI INTERAKTÍV FÓRUMÁN!

FISSAC HAZAI INTERAKTÍV FÓRUM

Szakmai bizottsági szervezetekkel és jó gyakorlatok bemutatásával indítunk párbeszédet az építő- és bontóipari szereplők, jogi szabályozók és a tudományos élet szereplői között annak érdekében, hogy az ágazatokat érintő összetett kihívások jobb megértését, és az azokra adott válaszok könnyebb meghozatalát közös gondolkodással segítsük elő.

- Mi a körforgásos gazdaság és az ipari szimbólus szerepe az építőipari értékáncban?
- Melyek az ipari szimbólus létrejöttéhez szükséges feltételek, eszközök?
- Melyek az öko-innovációt hátráltató tényezők az építőiparban?
- Hogyan kezelhető a társadalmi elfogadottság?
- Hogyan látják mások az Ön vállalatának szerepét az építő- és bontóiparban?

HAZAI ÉKAPCSOLAT

PROJEKT PARTNEREK

Photos of the HU LL launching event (13/04/2018)

GEO Twitter post about the HU LL launching event

The screenshot shows a Twitter post from the account @GeoEnvTech, dated April 13th. The text of the tweet reads: "Full house in Budapest at #Costruma exhibition with #H2020 FISSAC project. Come and meet us! bit.ly/2GVllrs #H2020EE #H2020energy". The tweet includes three photographs: a large photo of an audience seated in a room facing a presentation screen, a smaller photo of the audience from a different angle, and a photo of a table with informational materials and a poster. The Twitter interface shows search and login options at the top.

HU LL event evaluation questionnaire (rough Google translation to EN)

Thank you for participating in our conference, and we hope you find it useful. In order to be able to arrange our events at a higher level, according to your needs in the future, please fill out the following questionnaire:

How do you evaluate the organization of a professional day? inadequate adequate good excellent

Preparation and implementation:

Location and circumstances of the event:

Mood of the event:

The usefulness of the information provided in the lectures:

Knowledge and experience exchange:

Please describe any positive (as you like) or negative (disliked) experience regarding the event.

Positive:.....

Negative:.....

In your opinion, which areas should we change to make our event more successful?

.....

In our next series of events, we plan to engage in small group discussions so that we can promote a better understanding of the complex challenges facing the sector and facilitate the sharing of responses to them. Are you planning to participate in our next event?

Yes No

If yes, please sign up for the conference registration to send you further information about our additional events or contact us at forum.fissac@geonardo.com or follow our forums at <http://fissacproject.eu/category/II-hungary-hu/> address.

Appendix 8 Hungary LL: References

Conference „[The role of construction and demolition materials in the circular economy October 2016 Budapest](#)

[CLXXXV/2012 Law on wastes](#)

[Database of the European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform](#)

[Interreg Europe project SYMBI](#)

Konferencia: Hogyan juthatunk el a körforgásos gazdasághoz, Budapest 2016.11.09. [Conference on how to move forward circular economy] <https://www.kszgysz.hu/hirek/archivum/2016/hogyan-juthatunk-el-a-korforgasos-gazdasaghoz/> / <http://www.vnemethzolt.hu/hu/hirek/64484/budapest-korforgasos-gazdasag-konferencia-20161109-1000>

József Csaba Petrus: [Az építési és bontási hulladékokkal kapcsolatos aktuális hazai problémák és a készülő rendelet megoldási javaslatai](#) [Domestic challenges related to CDW and potential solutions in the decree under development] conference The role of CDM in the circular economy. October 2016 Budapest

Miklós Galli: Hogyan juthatunk el a körforgásos gazdasághoz? Javaslatok szabályzórendszer módosítására 2016. november. MGYOSZ, CSAOSZ, KSZGYSZ <http://docplayer.hu/30196743-Hogyan-juthatunk-el-a-korforgasos-gazdasaghoz.html>

Ministry of Agriculture (2016) [Az építési és bontási hulladék körforgásos gazdaságba illesztése a feladat](#) [The task is to organize construction and demolition waste into circular economy]

Ministry for National Economy: [Hungary's construction sector boom continues](#)

Appendix 9 Spain LL: Templates

CIRCULAR SCENARIO

adaptación de CIRCULAR board

Appendix 10 Spain LL: Pictures from the first Living Lab Barcelona 23.01.2018

Appendix 11 Sweden LL: Summary of the First Living Lab Meeting

October 27th, 2016, hosted by Garveriet – a sustainable development and construction initiative in Floda *This is a summary of the discussions held during the meeting. A good addition to the presentations.*

PARTICIPANTS:

Anders Nyqvist, EcoCycle Design (architects and more); Anette Sandén, Hifab (consultants in industrial symbiosis, partner in FISSAC); Annika Gram, CBI (Swedish Cement and Concrete research institute); Johan Felix, Chalmers Industriteknik (near-academia consultants); Johan Torén, SP (Swedish state-owned research institute, partner in FISSAC); Jonas Brandström, Garveriet Floda (local initiative for circular economy); Josefin Lassbo, Garveriet Floda; Julia Jonasson, SP; Kadri Koppel, Hifab; Karin Forsberg, Garveriet Floda; Kersti Karltop, SP; Lena Larsson, Kynningsrud (Precast and foundations production); Lennart Larsson, Garveriet Floda; Lisa Apelman, Ronneby municipality; Marianne Hedberg, Swedish construction federation; Monica Brandström, Garveriet Floda; Mia Edofsson, Akademiska hus (large property owner); Pernilla Löfås, NCC (construction and property development company); Peter Carlsson, Hifab; Wolfram Oettel, CBI, Evelina Boija, Passivhuscentrum (competence centre on energy efficient buildings)

Introductory presentation – what is Industrial Symbiosis and Circular Economy?

In today's linear economy we use more than 1,5 times the planets annual resources.

- About 70% of all waste is created before it reaches the consumer
- Up to 99 per cent of a building can by one way or another be reused
- In the EU only 20-30 per cent of waste is currently recycled and the construction industry is responsible for a third of the total waste produced in the EU.
- Circular Economy has the potential in Sweden to give 100 000 new jobs, raise the GDP by 3% and reduce CO2 emissions by 70%.

Linear Economy

Circular Economy

An extract of reflections by the participants

- Today's business students have the right mindset, but not today's CEOs.
- So far it hasn't been profitable in business to recycle and reuse resources, in the future it hopefully will be.
- We have now started to calculate and consider new types of costs in an organisation that previously have not been included. These costs fall on those responsible, so a new mindset is beginning to occur. Big companies however have nice policydocuments, but they are not practiced in reality.
- Intrest in the topic of those that were invited to the first FISSAC Living lab meeting has been high, even if everyone couldn't join today. The invited actors will follow the process and join the discussions in the future.
- If we manage to make changes locally, we can reach a global market.
- We in Sweden have an opportunity to be the frontrunner.
- Circular Economy has to be clearly connected to business perspectiv

FISSAC – Fostering Industrial Symbiosis for a Sustainable Resource Intensive industry Across the Extended Construction Value Chain: a short presentation of the project

FISSAC:

- Is developing a method and a software platform for exchange of information and to support the development of industrial symbiosis and circular material flow
- Will demonstrate and validate products such as green concrete, eco cement, ceramic tiles and rubber-wood-plastic composites made of recycled materials
- Replicability assessment and development through Living lab

FISSAC Living Lab

A lot of organizations need to work together in order to create circular material flow. In the Living lab process it is valuable that the actors present come from different organizations, but the challenge is to be heading in the same direction. Every actor is in possession of important information that could be shared. We will experiment with different solutions and see what works and what doesn't.

An extract of participants' reflections

- Question: Who is the "head" of a Living lab? How can one create the willingness to continuously cooperate and work together? Trust is important.
- Answer: The project runs living lab meetings during the following 2 years. The goal is that the network created shall continue running after the end of the project. It is important that everyone feels that we are here to learn, network and exchange experiences.
- Answer: Hopefully will you and your organisations be finding possibilities for business development, in which case the following will happen outside the project. The usefulness and possible benefits from participating, lies in you.
- In order to circulate materials, we need a new system of (material) documentation
- It is a benefit to bring together a broad constellation of actors both from public and private sector
- We have good intentions to co-operate, but the challenge is to find a suitable business model for executing these plans.

Presentation round: reflection on interest and ongoing work with circular material flow

- Garveriet’s vision is to become a center of sustainable development – a kind of living lab. To attract ecosystem-inspired business models, which will create more jobs and better businesses. It is important to understand the context and think preventively. What is it that creates a sustainable society? Win-win is important for making progress.
- NCC is working with a new sustainability framework, a part of it focuses on material use. The idea is to consider the demolition of the house from the very beginning of the construction. **But altering the building process is challenging.**
- CBI role in FISSAC and in sister EU project is developing the recycling of concrete. Waste products to new materials and **to new users. Looking for and developing a business case to make it work.**
- Chalmers Industrial Technology is working with Mistra’s project “Closing the Loop”. How do we work when we are planning operations in a construction or demolition site, for example with logistics? It is important to develop both **business models** as well as **payment-models**. For example: insurance companies have contracts with companies that reuse and set in place recycled moduls.
- SP is part of FISSAC to develop models of visualizing **systemic changes** and conversion processes. Can contribute with structuring all the shared knowledge that is to be found here among the participants. In addition, SP works with policy instruments both on local and regional level. Environmental and sustainability assessment of the tested recycled materials within FISSAC (for example ceramic tiles and plastic composites).
- Swedish Construction Federation raises the importance of accurate inventory and promotes the use of a “logbook” for documenting the construction materials used. All the living lab participants are invited to give input to the updated version of the publication “Guidlines of Waste and Resource Management in Building and Demolition”
- Kynningsrud produces **prefab** concrete elements in Uddevalla. The company recycles its own leftover and waste materials in its production. **Today’s standards** however don’t allow to use so much residues, which is a challenge to work with.
- Akademiska hus is a big client - there is a lot of projects that are going to be built and a lot of existing real-estate that well be rebuilt. For a client developing a project, it is important to have the confidents that using innovative recycled materials is not going to somehow paralyse the project. Good examples are much needed.
- The municipality of Ronneby has circular ambitions. Yet it is difficult to get information on the history and consistents of the construction moduls and materials. The ambition is to think at the time of the construction how the blocks and the materials are set together and how can they one day be taken apart again. Material knowledge is important as well as registration of materials used during construction. **Reversibel building form and material passports.**
- **From word to action.** Architect Anders Nykvist works with Ecocycle design has been part of real-life circular buiding solutions from the scale of an off-grid castle in Holland to a family home built of reused materials, without having to lend a penny from a bank. Suggestion to the hosting organisation is to build **future housing** in Floda that shows how one can close the circle and build together with newly arrived immigrants – create a good example that can be evaluated and followed up in time. **Education** and spreading the word about everything that happens in the process is necessary. **The process itself** – how we work in construction sector, is important.

Innovation starts with questions! A question formulation exercise

Point of departure of the exercise:

How can we work together to reduce barriers that today keep us from using more waste as resources?

Design questions developed by the Living lab participants:

- How can we bring together the entire value chain to find the consensus to develop and improve the standards, laws and business models.
- How can we create meeting places for the entire value chain where the quality of the building materials receives unbiased evaluation and the users have adequate knowledge?

Challenges and propositions identified during the discussion

- To find a business case, a functioning business model is a challenge. Good examples of realized projects in the construction industry, that will inspire and motivate other actors are much needed.
- There is a need of free information flow between the different actors of the value chain and a co-operation platform that will make it easier to find each other.
- There is lack of knowledge on the topic – clients must set higher demands
- In some cases companies consider co-operation as competition. That needs to change and instead discover the benefits of cooperation.
- It is important to include the industry's umbrella organisations in the living lab process in order to lay a strong foundation to the continued work. Co-operation between the public sector and businesses is also a part of the solution.
- Improved policy instruments, law requirements and taxes are needed to speed up the change process
- An identified problem with the existing standards based on the example of producing concrete: there is a will to blend in more recycled material in production, but the existing standards don't allow that.
- Suggestion: Fissac living labs should bring together actors that together will work on proposition to improve the legislation. The proposal should be accepted by all the actors involved.
- Suggestion: Boverket (The Swedish National Board of Housing, Planning and Development) shall establish a requirement of filling in the "logbook" (declaration of construction materials).

Appendix 12 Sweden LL: Summary of LL2- 2017-02-01

FISSAC Living Lab meeting #2, 2017-02-01

Summary

The discussion question of FISSAC Living Lab meeting #2 in Sweden was:

“Logbook of the Future - what kind of information should it entail and how should it be used so that it would function as a helpful tool for increasing circular material flow in the construction sector?”

The discussion topic was proposed by the Swedish Construction Industries during Living Lab meeting #1 and welcomed by the other Living lab participants.

Participants of the Living Lab meeting #2

In total 20 persons: **Ylva Wilder**, Master Student specialised in circular material flows in construction sector; **Peter Selberg**, R&D Strategist Johanneberg Science Park and Riksbyggen; **Lisa Elfström**, Vice President and Marketing Director at SundaHus (company providing tools for conscious material choices in construction; also participant in the Horizon2020-financed project BAMB); **Wolfram Oettel**, researcher at Swedish Cement and Concrete Research Institute; **Pernilla Johansson**, researcher at Technical Research Institute of Sweden; **Johan Felix**, consultant at Chalmers Industriteknik; **Carina Loh**

Lindholm, Project Manager at IVL Swedish Environmental Research Institute, work particularly with Basta, an on-line guidance to sustainable building and construction materials); **Kadri Koppel**, sustainability consultant from Hifab; **Monica Brandström**, Garveriet AB, a local development initiative focusing on circular economy and sustainable development; **Jonas Brandström**, Garveriet AB; **Linnea Lindkvist**, sustainability consultant from Hifab; **Anders Nyqvist**, architect focusing on sustainable construction; **Evdoxia Kouraki**, Johanneberg Science Park and HSB Living Lab, a research and demonstration arena including homes for students; **Elsa Fahlén**, NCC, construction and property development company; **Ulf Gustafsson**, Head of Sales at SUEZ Recycling AB; **Björn Cederlind**, SUEZ Recycling AB; **Malin Sävinger**, sustainability consultant from Hifab; **Julia Jonasson**, researcher at Technical Research Institute of Sweden; **Marianne Hedlund**, Swedish Construction Federation; **Stina Rydberg**, sustainability consultant Hifab.

Presentations of the day

- Presentation by Stina Rydberg (Hifab) about FISSAC and circular material flow in the construction value chain (see attached ppt).
- Presentation by Lisa Elfström (SundaHus/BAMB project) on Material passports as a way of creating circular material flow (see attached ppt).
- Presentation by Elsa Fahlén (NCC) about a feasibility study that they are starting now, Design for Deconstruction (see attached ppt).
- Presentation “Logbook for dummies” by Malin Sävinger (Hifab), the workshop leader (see attached ppt).

Workshop task

The participants were divided into three groups in line with different phases of the construction value chain: (1) engineering & construction; (2) material production (3) demolishing/recycling. The task was to imagine oneself to the given role and discuss input-output of information: What type of information would one desire to get from the “future logbook” and what kind of information would one register itself in order to give good input to others actors in the value chain. All in order to fulfil the scenario of FISSAC ★★.

FISSAC ★ ★ ★

is a future scenario proposed for the workshop according to which:

1. 25% of recycled materials are use during the building of a new house
2. 50% of materials will be possible to recycle at the end of its life -span
3. In case of renovation and refurbishing 70% of materials need to be recyclable

Summary of the discussions

After having heard the presentation of BAMB project (buildings as material banks) (Lisa Elfström's presentation) the participants seemed to agree that the material passports that are being developed should be included as one part of the future logbook for more comprehensive information on the content of the used materials.

A general interest of standardizing information about material content and characteristics was expressed. The former was followed by a discussion on the question of independent evaluation and the type of organization needed for carrying out the evaluation of the (recycled) materials on quality, characters, content etc.

One of the proposed ideas was to create or enjoin an existing public actor to take on the task of guaranteeing the independent evaluation.

“The program of the building”

One wider idea proposed by a Living Lab participant was to begin every building project and logbook by putting together a “program of the building” that will become a *shared knowledge* by all the actors involved in realizing a construction project. In order to realize such a vision, all the actors (or as many as possible) involved in a lifespan of a building need to be gathered in an early phase of the process and agree on the “idea” of the building. What is the building about? Who will live there? Who will use it? What are the goals to be met during the building phase? Goals during the user phase? How can the building be efficiently renovated; remodeled and demoted? “The program of the building” would also include different information on systems & infrastructure as:

ventilation, plumbing as well as environmental technologies and materials used, social consequences analysis and life-cycle analysis. “The program of the building” would also function as an information and education tool to all the parties involved: from the project owner to building manager and all the way to the building site workers.

“The program of the building” is a way of raising the understanding of why a particular way of building, a technique or choice of materials is implemented.

It is recognized that the more all actors in different roles working with the realization of a building project understand the functions, choices and use of the building, the better quality will be delivered during the construction & production of the project by all the actors in the value chain. That also means higher volumes of recyclable materials to foster circular material flow.

Reversal of knowledge

The logbook could also be a tool that mediates information on materials and methods that is discovered during renovation, demolishing and demoting of a building. It is only by registering and inserting this information back to the cycle will we know and learn, what really happened to a material/ building element and how a chosen building method actually worked.

One can learn a lot when one renovates for example a bathroom: what do the walls and floors look like behind the waterproofed layer? Is the chosen type of isolation the best one to be used? Precisely in this phase of the construction chain a lot of knowledge is created that rarely finds its way back to the decision making phase (beginning of the building process).

More such feedback and sharing of knowledge would lead to better choices of materials as well as a better management of the building process as experiences and lessons learned would be woven into creating the new. Such a reversal of knowledge could then become a key data input for “the program of the building” both when building new and when renovating.

Next Living Lab meetings

The last discussion point of the day was to find an interesting focus topic for the coming Living Lab meetings. One that was very warmly welcomed by all the participants was to follow a material through the entire construction value chain – all the way from extracting from nature to demolishing of the building and recycling of the material.

A recycling entrepreneur present at the meeting proposed choosing gypsum/plaster boards – calcium sulfate dihydrate (used for drywalls, wall panels, plaster boards etc) as it is a widely used building material/element with a high recycling potential. Today, however, the recycling rate of plasterboards is unnecessarily low.

As the participants present at the #2 Living Lab meeting considered this proposal interesting, it was decided by the organizers (SP/RISE and Hifab) to continue the Living Lab process with these suggestions in mind and plan the “material journey” for next meetings through videos, study visits and discussion groups.

Appendix 13 Sweden LL: Summary of LL3-2017-05-02

FISSAC Living Lab #3, 2017-05-02

Summary

The third Living Lab meeting on the 2nd of May was conducted in Suez recycling center in Kovik, Stockholm. The aim of the day was to study gypsum/gypsum plasterboard as a common building material with a high recycling potential. The topic of the Living Lab was jointly decided at the previous meeting (Living Lab #2) by the participants and the recycling company SUEZ. The life cycle of the gypsum plasterboards will be discussed also in the following Living Lab meetings #4 and #5.

Participants of the Living Lab meeting #3

In total 11 participants: **Pernilla Johansson**, researcher at RISE, Research Institutes of Sweden; **Johan Sidenmark**, NCC; **Tommy Haglund**, business developer at Gyproc; **Merit Kaal**, sustainability consultant at Hifab; **Joa Ivarsson**, leader of the sustainability development at Framtiden Byggutveckling; **Ulf Gustafsson**, sales manager at SUEZ Recycling AB; **Björn Cederlind**, SUEZ Recycling AB; **Magnus Skoglund**, site manager at SUEZ Recycling Kovik; **Linnea Lindkvist**, sustainability consultant at Hifab; **Julia Jonasson**, project manager at RISE; **Kersti Karltorp**, project manager at RISE.

Presentations of the day

- Introduction by Linnea Lindkvist (Hifab) (see attached pdf)
- Presentation by Ulf Gustafsson and Magnus Skoglund (SUEZ) about SUEZ and recycling plant in Kovik (Värmdö, Stockholm) (see attached pdf)
- Guided tour at the recycling center by Magnus Skoglund (SUEZ)
- Presentation of the videos about gypsum handling at the construction and demolition site as well as group discussions by Julia Jonasson (RISE) and Linnea Lindkvist (Hifab) (see attached pdf, movies are not included)

Highlights of the guided tour

During the Living Lab #3, the participants had a guided tour at SUEZ recycling plant in Kovik. The facility is run privately and serves both private and business customers.

The gypsum waste is left directly by the customers at the designated location at the recycling plant where it is cleaned mechanically from other waste materials. For example, plastic bags or plastic bands that were used to collect and/or transport the gypsum waste. The recycled gypsum is delivered by truck to Knauf in Åhus with whom SUEZ has a collaboration agreement. Knauf is using recycled gypsum from SUEZ as a raw material in their production of new plasterboards. As an alternative the gypsum waste may be collected by GipsRecycling.

Figure 1: Sorted gypsum waste for recycling

Additionally to the special gypsum waste collection points, it can be seen in a mix of waste that goes for landfilling as well as in the combustion fraction. However, neither landfill nor incineration is an appropriate way to handle the gypsum waste. Magnus Skoglund, SUEZ site manager in Kovik, made a resemblance to gypsum as a "poison". By this he meant that sorted gypsum posed problems in their process, such as low pH in the leachate from the landfill and that the boilers were damaged during combustion. So, in addition to the fact that the material is remarkably suitable for recycling, since it can be used repeatedly without quality deteriorating, there are also other reasons why the plaster should be sorted out.

Video session and a group discussion

Before the Living Lab #3, Hifab and RISE had prepared video material about handling the gypsum plasterboards at a construction site and a demolition site. The video clips included interviews with a carpenter, construction project manager and a demolition worker. The issues discussed in the videos were following:

- How the material is handled at the workplace
- How the transport and delivery of gypsum plasterboards is done
- How the sorting of gypsum waste is done at the construction site
- How much gypsum waste is generated
- How the gypsum waste is handled after collection by the recycling company
- Is there any alternative for traditional gypsum demolition

After the presentations and the video clips, the groups were discussing the following issues:

Roles: Both the carpenter and the demolition worker said that the roles in the construction value chain are firmly delineated. What consequences may that impose on material recycling?

Economic focus: We optimize for production when building and a demolition worker does not disassemble. How is the building chain affected by the fact that each link is optimized?

Participants were also asked to give a personal reflection about the day and what new they had learn.

Summary of the group discussions

Reduce the amounts of waste

According to the information shared during the discussions, about 20% of all gypsum used at the construction site becomes spill. In a way that means that every fifth plasterboard is manufactured unnecessarily.

Design: design right and order correctly

There is a widespread cost awareness and this along with solid roles may lead to suboptimization and, in the long run, unnecessary material waste.

Example:

The material manufacturer can produce custom made plasterboards, but it requires a more specific order. Here the purchasing organization can be an obstacle since they have negotiated prices for specific products and only those are available for purchase. Dimensionally adjusted material becomes a little more expensive in purchasing, but the working time for performing customization is shifted from the construction site to the plasterboard factory, and this probably creates higher efficiency at the construction site.

Planning of the work: If the work is done on time it is possible to avoid unnecessary material spills. Digitalization can facilitate planning and avoid collisions.

Example:

The carpenter points to a conflict with other disciplines, such as perforation of already assembled plasterboards to be able to install cables. This will lead to increased amount of waste.

Knowledge

The interviewees in the movies gave similar answers to the question of what happened to the plaster after it was thrown - hoping it was recycled, but did not really know. Suez told that they are offering trainings to their customers, which are major construction companies, and expected the level of knowledge to be higher. But according to the interviewed carpenter, it was less important to be careful with materials as plasterboards and therefore producing more waste. Is it possible that knowledge about how the material is recycled may lead to a counter-productive behavior, making it more likely to discard more because the material is still recycled?

Increased recycling

Gypsum is 100% recyclable but due to the spills and inefficient waste handling a lot of gypsum is lost in the value chain. Tommy Haglund from Gyproc believes that only about 10% of gypsum waste is recycled today and added that there is a deficit of recycled material. Today, about 25-30% of recycled gypsum is used in the production of new plasterboards, however, it would be possible to make a new plasterboard out of 100% of recycled gypsum.

According to SUEZ, there is no good statistics on how much of the total amount of gypsum received that goes in the wrong fraction, unable to recycle. More information and data about gypsum waste and recycling rates could potentially help to increase the recycling of plasterboards. In addition, good data could help to organize the gypsum waste from the incorrect fractions, landfilling and combustion, to recycling fraction. Therefore, the data is important to know.

In addition, Magnus Skoglund (SUEZ), added that the sorting of the gypsum should be done correctly already at the demolishing/construction site because gypsum is a very porous material that is decomposed to powder during the mechanical handling. Due to that, more spills can occur.

Opportunities to increase the gypsum recycling:

- Developed methods for dismantling. Materials development
- Can increased specialization also at demolition be an opportunity for increased recycling? Compare how new construction takes place; one bathroom 11 activities and 8 disciplines. But when it's demolished it's just one discipline.
- Increasing the knowledge about how to use the results of Life Cycle analysis (LCA)
- Using Life Cycle Costing (LCC) helps to consider all costs that will occur during the lifetime of the product, work or service, including end-of-life costs like decommissioning or disposal

- Classifying the recycled gypsum as a raw material? Today the recycled gypsum is sold to the plasterboard companies at no cost.

Next Living Lab meetings

On the next meeting (Living Lab #4) the journey of gypsum plasterboards will continue with a study visit to the manufacturer of gypsum plasterboards, Gyproc. The event is scheduled for Tuesday, June 13th and “save a date” has been sent to all participants.

Examples of question that will be addressed at upcoming meetings:

- Gypsum plasterboards as building material – something that will continue?
- What is required for the material to be classified / equated as raw material?
- How big is actually the environmental impact of gypsum plasterboards?
- Gypsum is a finite resource. How is this addressed by the industry?

The aim of the Living Lab #5, that is scheduled preliminary in September, will be analysing and concluding the main findings of the meetings of Living Labs #3 and #4.

Appendix 14 Sweden LL:Summary of LL4 2017-06-17

FISSAC Living Lab #4, 2017-06-13 - Summary

The fourth Living Lab meeting on the 13th of June was conducted in the plasterboards manufacturing company, Gyproc, in Bålsta. It was a continuation of the journey through the value chain of gypsum plasterboards, that was already started in the Living Lab #3. The aim of the visit was to get more detailed overview of the production of gypsum plasterboards, including the logistics of the raw material to the plant and finished boards out from the industry.

It was a small group of people taking part in the Living Lab #4, but nevertheless the day was very interesting, educative and the participants got a good overview of the production of gypsum plasterboards.

Participants of the Living Lab meeting #4

In total 9 participants: **Thomas Karlsson**, Stena Recycling; **Tommy Haglund**, business developer at Gyproc, **Merit Kaal**, sustainability consultant at Hifab; **Pernilla Löfås**, NCC; **Lars Lundberg**, VD Gyproc; **Peter Örn**, Saint-Gobain Sweden; **Linnea Lindkvist**, sustainability consultant at Hifab; **Julia Jonasson**, project leader at RISE; **Kersti Karltorp**, project leader at RISE.

Agenda

- Introduction by Linnea Lindkvist (Hifab), see attached pdf
 - Due to train delays, the meeting started later than planned and only the main issue was presented; what opportunities are there for increased inflow of recycled raw material?
- Presentation by Tommy Haglund and Lars Lundberg (Gyproc), see attached pdf.
- Guided tour in the factory
- Lunch
- Group discussion

Highlights of the study visit

During the day, the participants had a guided tour in the Gyproc's facility, being able to follow the whole production line, beginning with the raw material input and ending with the finished plasterboards.

The primary raw material (PRM) is transported to the facility by boat and is stored as rocks (figure 1) in the outdoor storage. Then, the raw material is crushed and moved under the roof in order to keep it dry. The secondary raw material (SRM), recycled gypsum partly from Gyproc's own production and partly from construction and demolition sites, is crushed and screened into fine powder. The recycled gypsum must be kept dry in order for the crush to work. Separated carton from plasterboards have previously been used as soil improver, but now they are making attempts to use this material in the production of new carton. Processed SRM is stored under roof (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Gypsum, virgin raw material

20 Figure 2. Intermediate storage of different fractions of crushed gypsum. On the left hand side of the picture, SRM is shown and PRM to the right.

Figure 3. Spraying the gypsum blend to the cardboard

Figure 4. Gypsum plasterboards on the conveyor belt

The powdered gypsum (both, virgin and recycled, in the ratio of about 75/25) is mixed with water and additives and the prepared slurry is then sprayed onto the cardboard (figure 3). The plasterboard material then goes on a 300 m long conveyor belt, where it gradually becomes harder (drainage occurs during the retention time on the conveyor belt) (Figure 4). Thereafter, the material is passing through a dryer to obtain the right moisture content. Finally, the boards are cut into the right size and prepared for the transport.

Group discussion

After being invited for lunch at Gyproc's canteen, the group discussion session was conducted. We began to reconnect with previous meetings with the Living Lab-group, partly from the first meeting when the design questions were formulated and partly with the lessons learned during Living Lab #3 - the first stop in the material journey.

Summary of reflections and thoughts of participants – Lessons learnt:

- **Logistics and roles:** There are too few places to leave recycled gypsum and plasterboards, which drives costs and makes landfill a more attractive option. Perhaps the intervention of an operator specialized in logistics is needed in order to increase the recovery. Or would it be possible for an existing actor in the value chain to take on an expanded role and responsibility?
- **Suboptimisation:** This becomes a barrier between different actors, but also within an organization. At the Living Lab #3 it was discussed that using customized material would reduce the amounts of waste from construction sites. During Living Lab # 4 we saw the material manufacturer's view, where the sales organization is pro customization, but the production organization is not as positive, as standardized products more easily provide for an efficient production.
- **Tools:** Legislation and standards (e.g environmental certification) must be developed in order to achieve higher rates of recycling. It should also be more expensive to leave recyclable waste to landfill instead of recycling it.
- **Documentation:** The documentation systems must be further developed and become less time consuming to use, compared to the current situation. Google has developed a material documentation system that, according to one of the participants, has great potential. Google is specialized in managing large amounts of data. Could this be an example of a missing feature today?
- **Requirements:** Could the requirements for recycled raw materials be simplified? The requirements are set both for technical reasons (wet recycled material clogs the crusher) and for competitive reasons (accepting only your own brand). How do we overcome these barriers?

Upcoming FISSAC Living Labs meeting

Planning for Living Lab #5 has already started and the date is decided to be on September 28th. During this meeting, we plan to end the material journey and conclude upon the findings and lessons learnt from the two previous meetings in our case study "The Road of Gypsum/Plaster- Through the Construction Process". Most likely, we meet in Gothenburg to further discuss barriers and opportunities to increase recycling of building materials. Hopefully, we can find answers to at least part of all the questions that have arisen so far during the journey. Keep a look out for the invitation for this interesting day in your email!

NB! Do not forget to follow us in Medium: <https://medium.com/@fissaclivinglab/>.

[T7.2 Report on Use of Adapted TIS Analysis in the FISSAC Project \(PDF\); http://fissacproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/FISSAC-2018-Use-of-Adapted-TIS-Analysis-in-the-FISSAC-Project.pdf](http://fissacproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/FISSAC-2018-Use-of-Adapted-TIS-Analysis-in-the-FISSAC-Project.pdf)

Appendix 15 UK LL: Brains storming 1

Appendix 16 UK Living Labs: Brain Storming 2

Appendix 17 Opportunities and challenges

Appendix 3

Opportunities	Area	
Use of existing delivery network	Logistics	
Improve infrastructure	Logistics	
Construction site disposal and collection	Logistics	
BAMB 2020 *reversible building design*	C&D	Logistics
By-product development	C&D	
Training architects	C&D	
Large projects governed by CSR	C&D	Social
Social value (SR01)	Social	
sustainability education	Social	
Improve education	Social	
Changing the mindset	Social	
Job creations	Social	Economic
Environmental credentials	Social	Economic
Tax breaks	Economic	
Save landfill tax	Economic	
Cost savings, added revenues	Economic	
Expanded products	Economic	
Business model creation	Economic	
New customers	Economic	
Energy reduction	Economic	Environmental
Reduce CO2	Environmental	
Reduction in raw materials	Environmental	
Landfill reduction	Environmental	
Producer responsibility legislation	Legislation	
Legislating for change	Legislation	
Be ahead of legislation	Legislation	
Glass landfill ban	Legislation	

Challenges	Area	
Contamination	Quality	
Source segregation	Quality	
Locations of new sorting facilities	Logistics	
Responsibility	Logistics	
Facilitation of process	Logistics	
Collection of waste	Logistics	
Space for SMEs to segregate and store	Logistics	
Infrastructure	Logistics	
Recycling centres	Logistics	
Population centre	Logistics	Economic
viability of smaller waste generators	Logistics	Economic
Cost viability	Economic	
Free-riders	Economic	

Challenges	Area
Admin	Economic
Scalability	Economic
Payment	Economic
Procurement	Economic
Creating a level playground	Economic
No consistent policy for recycling C&D waste	Legislation
Cant currently use domestic tips	Legislation
Health and safety	Legislation
Weak legislation	Legislation
Changing attitudes (ie construction)	Social
Education	Social

Appendix 18 CEIF Calls Proposal

Flat Glass Recovery Network

Rationale, Background & Context

The Scottish glass industry manufactures over 400,000 tonnes of glass each year, the majority of which is clear glass for the bottle industry. The majority of the flat and clear glass is manufactured using virgin materials, but good quality glass recyclate can be used. Using recycled glass has a number of advantages, less energy is required to remelt glass therefore less carbon per tonne of new glass, less virgin materials are used protecting our natural resources and less waste is sent to landfill. All of these points result in reduced costs to the industry protecting their economic viability. The main barrier is the lack of good quality recovered glass (cullet).

Dismantling of the window, glazing or other flat glass products from a building is the first step towards achieving the highest recycling rates of building glass, but despite its recyclability, flat glass waste is seldom recycled into an equivalent value product. The majority of it is crushed together with other building materials and used as aggregate or put in landfills. A Dutch collection model demonstrates that 90% of this flat glass could be recovered and recycled in glass furnaces. The introduction of the Dutch system was partly driven by the glass manufacturing industry who entered into a voluntary agreement to support the sorting and recycling of end-of-life building glass, and to use it in its manufacturing processes.

The Waste Framework Directive establishes specific targets for the reuse and recycling of building waste including glass and aims to place recycling and a high level of resource efficiency. The Scottish Zero Waste Plan sets out the Scottish Government's vision for a zero waste society, where waste is seen as a resource.

In 2012 a number of the UK's largest window manufactures launched the "Windows Sustainability Action Plan". This was a UK Government supported project to drive sustainability within the construction and glass industries. The programme ran over 2012 and achieved a number of successes. These included the first Life Cycle Analysis for thermally efficient flat glass, and the collection and recycling of 25,479 tonnes of post-consumer PVC window frames from demolition waste. The programme was supported by WRAP and faded when WRAP stepped away from the construction sector. The Glass sector remains keen to take action in this area and with British Glass as partners in this project we will have the support of all of their members which include the majority of Scotland's glass manufacturing sector.

Glass waste from construction is comparatively low in comparison to other construction waste streams. SEPA 2016 data shows that 5,549 tonnes was generated in 2016 with a very small percentage of this going to landfill. These figures do not however show the volume of glass in mixed waste streams which is lost to the economy through disposal in landfills or used for low grade use such as aggregates. If appropriately collected on site this can be improved collecting large volumes of flat glass, which can then be utilised to make higher value products such as flat glass, clear bottles, insulation or glass beads.

In 2000, the Dutch began working on a flat glass collection programme. They now have a fully operational national programme that recovers more than 70,000 tonnes of flat glass per year recycling 90% of it back into glass.

Approach and Resourcing Strategy

Figure 1 The flow of recovered flat glass for recycling

WRAP Flat Glass Recycle Best practice guide

Flat glass is an important material in construction and demolition waste streams. Improvements in the end of life management of these waste streams can achieve major savings in waste and increase the availability of good quality recycled cullet. The flat glass industry is willing to increase the quantity of recycled glass in its production processes and therefore expanding the availability of high quality recycled cullet will reduce both waste going to landfill and the use of virgin raw materials. Action in this area can contribute to Scotland's Circular Economy and low carbon goals.

Improving the collection of flat glass to improve recovery and quality requires a number of steps. Strong market demand and stakeholder buy-in are key. Once stakeholders agree to work together to find a solution, the first challenge is to identify how glass recycling can be increased in an economically sustainable way, and who does what. Quality of segregation is important with great care required to ensure minimum levels of contamination. Eligible projects for increasing flat glass recycling can include:

- Recycling trials in individual cities or companies.
- The setting up of a Scotland wide recycling scheme that collects waste flat glass from construction processes and from demolition.
- Demonstration of innovative technologies or practices that can significantly improve the business case for collecting and recycling flat glass e.g. by making it easier, quicker or more economically viable.

The Glass for Europe report "Recycling of end-of-life building glass" recognised that increased waste recycling, among other measures, will contribute to a competitive construction sector. This objective is in line with the basic requirement set out in the Construction Products Regulation concerning sustainable use of natural resources, and the Raw Materials Initiative (RMI). Development of best practices in the collection and treatment of waste, recovery/reuse of valuable materials from waste and research and economic incentives for recycling/recovery is important.

The use of recycled cullet reduces the cost to industry in terms of raw material use and energy costs as glass from recycled cullet uses less energy to make. The environment benefits through less use of natural materials, less waste to landfill and reductions in carbon emissions.

Call

Zero Waste Scotland invites an SME or third sector organisation to develop, a collection and recycling scheme for Scotland. Focusing on close loop recycling, learning lessons from other national systems such as the one operated in the Netherlands.

The applicant must be an SME or third sector organisation, but can work with a non-SME as part of a consortium they lead.

Within the outline of your proposal we wish to see how you propose to set up the infrastructure required to operate the scheme, and how this will be managed. We also wish to understand the timeframes around the setup of the national system of collection and recovery.

The broad range of buildings and glass types and the fact that glass is usually part of a framed window and not a 'stand-alone' product makes a collection scheme complex. We wish to understand from your submission how you intend to reflect this in your proposed collecting, sorting, treating and final recycling of the glass.

Once the glazing and/or windows are dismantled from the building, proper sorting and collection at the earliest stage is essential to avoid the breakage and potential contamination of the glass by other building components that would make efficient recycling more difficult. For deconstruction projects it is preferable for glass containers and/or collection points to be made available on site in order to allow efficient sorting and collection.

Building refurbishment particularly in the domestic market will not justify on site collection containers, therefore a network of collection points will be needed across the country.